

The Dark Sides of Modern Science: Knowledge Production and Authoring

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Abstract: Despite its flashy image and good reputation among the general public as well as among the majority of scholars and intellectuals, science - like any other field of human activity - suffers from serious shortcomings and defects related to moral, ethical, professional and legal aspects and perspectives, where the generally approved standards, rules and values are - deliberately or non-deliberately, with or without good intention - infringed and violated by the individuals and institutions who produce, curate and promote science (i.e. academics, researchers, universities, scholarly journals, funding bodies, and so on). In this series of “The Dark Sides of Modern Science” we try to shed light on some of these negative aspects and downsides of modern science where we provide curated lists of references, in the form of scholarly journal articles and online sources, related to the topics of this subject. This compilation aims to raise awareness of this important issue among the general public as well as among scholars and specialists. Additionally, the series serves as a valuable starting point for researchers and writers who wish to explore the topics of this subject further and in greater detail. In this paper (which is the first in this series) we investigate the dark sides of knowledge production and authoring. Our intention is to investigate in the following papers of this series other dark sides of modern science related, for instance, to publishing, credit attribution and morality.

Keywords: Ethics of science, ethics of knowledge, morality in science, academic misconduct, corruption in science, knowledge production, authoring.

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1 Introduction

The idea of this series was initiated as a project for writing a book about the dark sides of modern science in which I present my personal experience as well as the knowledge I gathered from reading the specialized and general literature of science during the last twenty years of my life as a postgraduate student, researcher, reviewer, author and scientist. However, on inspecting the general literature about this subject I noticed that almost all my experiences and knowledge in this regard are well investigated and documented by other scholars who, mostly, are specialized in these subjects. Therefore, I concluded that it is more useful and less labor-intensive to convert this project to an essentially bibliographic work where I provide lists of academic references (as well as general online articles which are mostly written by academics and experts in this field) that present and highlight the issues and experiences that I want to present and document. The objective of this is that on inspecting the references (as depicted by their titles, possibly with accessing and reading their abstracts) and skim reading the online articles of any titled section, the inspector gets a good idea about the nature and gravity of the problematic issues of the titled subject.

Before starting our investigation it is useful to be aware of the following remarks:

1. “Science” in the title and text of this paper should include all the entities and aspects related to knowledge, knowledge production and authoring.^[1] So, it should include for instance academics and researchers (whether individuals or groups), academic and research institutions (such as universities and research centers), scholarly publishing outlets (such as scholarly journals, publishing houses and university presses), conferences and similar venues related to academic and research activities, research funding bodies (whether private or public), quality of produced knowledge, morality of produced knowledge, and so on.
2. As indicated already, the present article is of bibliographic nature. It is intended to be an initial reference to those who are interested in investigating the dark sides of modern science^[2] as well as an educational document to raise awareness among the general public and scholars of the downsides of modern science.
3. The references (as well as the URL addresses or links to the online articles) are hyper-linked to facilitate the access to these references and articles with minimal effort.

^[1]This should also apply to the upcoming subjects of this series such as publishing, credit attribution and morality.

^[2]In fact, this investigation can be seen as a structured and focused literature review where researchers in this field can benefit from this investigation as a starting point.

4. In each section, references (i.e. journal articles, books, book chapters and conference proceedings) are listed first followed by online articles (where the latter occasionally include videos and podcasts).
5. Most of the titled sections in this article have too many references and online articles to be cited all, and hence what we included is a sample that in our view represents the titled subject fairly and balancedly and hence provide sufficient materials for understanding the concerned issues and appreciating their extent and gravity. Anyway, it is important to consider inspecting the references of the cited references and articles since they provide many more references and articles that can be used for further and detailed research and investigation.
6. The references are cited with only authors, title, year of publication and Digital Object Identifier (DOI).^[3] This is to reduce the amount of work required (noting that we provide hyperlinked DOI from which it is easy to get other bibliographic information immediately if needed).
7. All the cited online materials are accessed during the preparation and writing of this paper (i.e. July 2025).
8. References are ordered chronologically while online articles and items are not.
9. Online articles and items (as well as some research and review papers) are included for the purpose of providing general background knowledge and hence the materials and claims of these articles and items should be treated with care and caution (e.g. fact and credibility checks should be applied to verify the sources and contents).
10. Chronological inspection of the cited papers and articles reveals that most of the down-sides of modern science related to knowledge production and authoring have emerged or aggravated in the last two or three decades (which may imply that science is recently moving in the wrong direction).

^[3] Other identifiers or URLs are provided when DOI is missing. For books, we use ISBN instead of DOI.

2 Paper Mills

1. L.P. Stavisky. Term Paper "Mills," Academic Plagiarism, and State Regulation, 1973. DOI: [10.2307/2148993](https://doi.org/10.2307/2148993)
2. C.R. Campbell; C.O. Swift; L. Denton. Cheating Goes Hi-Tech: Online Term Paper Mills, 2000. DOI: [10.1177/105256290002400605](https://doi.org/10.1177/105256290002400605)
3. K. Ritter. The Economics of Authorship: Online Paper Mills, Student Writers, and First-Year Composition, 2005. DOI: [10.58680/ccc20054824](https://doi.org/10.58680/ccc20054824)
4. M. Hvistendahl. China's Publication Bazaar, 2013. DOI: [10.1126/science.342.6162.1035](https://doi.org/10.1126/science.342.6162.1035)
5. R. Stone. In Iran, a shady market for papers flourishes, 2016. DOI: [10.1126/science.353.6305.1197](https://doi.org/10.1126/science.353.6305.1197)
6. J.A. Byrne; J. Christopher. Digital magic, or the dark arts of the 21st century – how can journals and peer reviewers detect manuscripts and publications from paper mills?, 2020. DOI: [10.1002/1873-3468.13747](https://doi.org/10.1002/1873-3468.13747)
7. S. Mallapaty. China's research-misconduct rules target 'paper mills' that churn out fake studies, 2020. DOI: [10.1038/d41586-020-02445-8](https://doi.org/10.1038/d41586-020-02445-8)
8. S. Heck; F. Bianchini; N.Y. Souren; C. Wilhelm; Y. Ohl; C. Plass. Fake data, paper mills, and their authors: The International Journal of Cancer reacts to this threat to scientific integrity, 2021. DOI: [10.1002/ijc.33604](https://doi.org/10.1002/ijc.33604)
9. H. Else; R. Van Noorden. The fight against fake-paper factories that churn out sham science, 2021. DOI: [10.1038/d41586-021-00733-5](https://doi.org/10.1038/d41586-021-00733-5)
10. J.A.T. da Silva. Paper mill-derived cancer research: the improbability of prostate cancer in women, and ovarian and breast cancer in men, 2021. DOI: [10.5603/NJO.a2021.0039](https://doi.org/10.5603/NJO.a2021.0039)
11. J.A.T. da Silva. Paper mills and on-demand publishing: Risks to the integrity of journal indexing and metrics, 2021. DOI: [10.1016/j.mjafi.2020.08.003](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mjafi.2020.08.003)
12. B.A. Sabel; R. Seifert. How criminal science publishing gangs damage the genesis of knowledge and technology – a call to action to restore trust, 2021. DOI: [10.1007/s00210-021-02158-3](https://doi.org/10.1007/s00210-021-02158-3)
13. J.A.T. da Silva. Abuse of ORCID's weaknesses by authors who use paper mills, 2021. DOI: [10.1007/s11192-021-03996-x](https://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-021-03996-x)
14. J. Christopher. The raw truth about paper mills, 2021. DOI: [10.1002/1873-3468.14143](https://doi.org/10.1002/1873-3468.14143)
15. R. Seifert. How Naunyn-Schmiedeberg's Archives of Pharmacology deals with fraudulent papers from paper mills, 2021. DOI: [10.1007/s00210-021-02056-8](https://doi.org/10.1007/s00210-021-02056-8)
16. A.R. Memon; F.A. Rathore. The rising menace of scholarly black-market: Challenges and solutions for improving research in low- and middle-income countries, 2021. PMID:

34111064

17. I. Pérez-Neri; C. Pineda; H. Sandoval. Threats to scholarly research integrity arising from paper mills: a rapid scoping review, 2022. DOI: [10.1007/s10067-022-06198-9](https://doi.org/10.1007/s10067-022-06198-9)
18. C. Candal-Pedreira; J.S. Ross; A. Ruano-Ravina; et al. Retracted papers originating from paper mills: cross sectional study, 2022. DOI: [10.1136/bmj-2022-071517](https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj-2022-071517)
19. J.A. Byrne; Y. Park; R.A.K. Richardson; et al. Protection of the human gene research literature from contract cheating organizations known as research paper mills, 2022. DOI: [10.1093/nar/gkac1139](https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkac1139)
20. D.S. Chawla. How a site peddles author slots in reputable publishers' journals, 2022. DOI: [10.1126/science.abq4276](https://doi.org/10.1126/science.abq4276)
21. J.A.T. da Silva. When academic papers' stated emails do not match authors' affiliations: A new budding crisis in paper mill-ridden academic publishing?, 2022. DOI: [10.12681/eml.31441](https://doi.org/10.12681/eml.31441)
22. P. Smart. Paper mills, fraudulent authors, and editorial responses, 2023. DOI: [10.6087/kcse.314](https://doi.org/10.6087/kcse.314)
23. T. Wykes; A. Parkinson. The anxiety of the lone editor: fraud, paper mills and the protection of the scientific record, 2023. DOI: [10.1080/09638237.2023.2232217](https://doi.org/10.1080/09638237.2023.2232217)
24. A. Abalkina. Publication and collaboration anomalies in academic papers originating from a paper mill: Evidence from a Russia-based paper mill, 2023. DOI: [10.1002/leap.1574](https://doi.org/10.1002/leap.1574)
25. A. Abalkina. Paper mills: a novel form of publishing malpractice affecting psychology, 2023. DOI: [10.15626/MP.2022.3422](https://doi.org/10.15626/MP.2022.3422)
26. R. Van Noorden. How big is science's fake-paper problem?, 2023. DOI: [10.1038/d41586-023-03464-x](https://doi.org/10.1038/d41586-023-03464-x)
27. C. Bricker-Anthony; R.W. Herzog. Distortion of journal impact factors in the era of paper mills, 2023. DOI: [10.1016/j.ymthe.2023.05.008](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ymthe.2023.05.008)
28. D. Bishop. Red flags for paper mills need to go beyond the level of individual articles: a case study of Hindawi special issues, 2023. DOI: [10.31234/osf.io/6mbgv](https://doi.org/10.31234/osf.io/6mbgv)
29. J. Brainard. Fake scientific papers are alarmingly common, 2023. DOI: [10.1126/science.adi6523](https://doi.org/10.1126/science.adi6523)
30. B.A. Sabel; E. Knaack; G. Gigerenzer; M. Bilc. Fake Publications in Biomedical Science: Red-flagging Method Indicates Mass Production, 2023. DOI: [10.1101/2023.05.06.23289563](https://doi.org/10.1101/2023.05.06.23289563)
31. H. Else. Multimillion-dollar trade in paper authorships alarms publishers, 2023. DOI: [10.1038/d41586-023-00062-9](https://doi.org/10.1038/d41586-023-00062-9)

32. H. Chambers. Unmasking the fraud: How paper mills are undermining scientific publishing, 2024. DOI: [10.1111/dmcn.15997](https://doi.org/10.1111/dmcn.15997)
33. D. Kizilova; A. Shulzhenko. Paper Mills: A New Challenge to Academic Integrity in the Context of the Sustainable Development Goals, 2024. DOI: [10.52244/c.2024.11.10](https://doi.org/10.52244/c.2024.11.10)
34. P.S. Deo; P. Hangsing. Preserving Academic Integrity: Combating the Proliferation of Paper Mills in Scholarly Publishing, 2024. DOI: [10.1080/15424065.2024.2388039](https://doi.org/10.1080/15424065.2024.2388039)
35. C. Brundy; J.B. Thornton. The paper mill crisis is a five-alarm fire for science: what can librarians do about it?, 2024. DOI: [10.1629/uksg.659](https://doi.org/10.1629/uksg.659)
36. S. Nagarkar. "Research paper mills": A factory outlet for dubious research, 2024. DOI: [10.20529/IJME.2024.025](https://doi.org/10.20529/IJME.2024.025)
37. A. Abalkina. Commercialization of scientific misconduct: the challenge of paper mills, 2024. DOI: [10.1093/eurpub/ckae144.679](https://doi.org/10.1093/eurpub/ckae144.679)
38. C. Candal-Pedreira; C. Guerra-Tort; A. Ruano-Ravina; et al. Retracted papers originating from paper mills: a cross-sectional analysis of references and citations, 2024. DOI: [10.1016/j.jclinepi.2024.111397](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclinepi.2024.111397)
39. J.P. Cardenuto; D. Moreira; A. Rocha. Unveiling scientific articles from paper mills with provenance analysis, 2024. DOI: [10.1371/journal.pone.0312666](https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0312666)
40. L. Parker; S. Boughton; L. Bero; J.A. Byrne. Paper mill challenges: past, present, and future, 2024. DOI: [10.1016/j.jclinepi.2024.111549](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclinepi.2024.111549)
41. K. Sanderson. Science's fake-paper problem: high-profile effort will tackle paper mills, 2024. DOI: [10.1038/d41586-024-00159-9](https://doi.org/10.1038/d41586-024-00159-9)
42. J.P. Cardenuto; D. Moreira; A. Rocha. Unveiling scientific articles from paper mills with provenance analysis, 2024. DOI: [10.1371/journal.pone.0312666](https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0312666)
43. D.E. Wright. Five problems plaguing publishing in the life sciences-and one common cause, 2024. DOI: [10.1002/1873-3468.15018](https://doi.org/10.1002/1873-3468.15018)
44. D.E. Wright. Five problems plaguing publishing in the life sciences-and one common cause, 2024. DOI: [10.1002/1873-3468.15018](https://doi.org/10.1002/1873-3468.15018)
45. J.A. Byrne; A. Abalkina; O. Akinduro-Aje; et al. A call for research to address the threat of paper mills, 2024. DOI: [10.1371/journal.pbio.3002931](https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pbio.3002931)
46. D.S. Chawla. Fake research papers flagged by analysing authorship trends, 2024. DOI: [10.1038/d41586-024-00344-w](https://doi.org/10.1038/d41586-024-00344-w)
47. S.J. Porter; L.D. McIntosh. Identifying fabricated networks within authorship-for-sale enterprises, 2024. DOI: [10.1038/s41598-024-71230-8](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-024-71230-8)
48. J. Wittau; R. Seifert. How to fight fake papers: a review on important information sources and steps towards solution of the problem, 2024.

[DOI: 10.1007/s00210-024-03272-8](https://doi.org/10.1007/s00210-024-03272-8)

49. F. Joelsing. Paper trail, 2024. [DOI: 10.1126/science.ado0309](https://doi.org/10.1126/science.ado0309)
50. A.G. Mainous III. Papermills as another challenge to research integrity and trust in science, 2025. [DOI: 10.3389/fmed.2025.1557024](https://doi.org/10.3389/fmed.2025.1557024)
51. J.B. Soriano; A. Ruano-Ravina. The rising threat of predatory journals and paper mills in respiratory medicine and research, 2025. [DOI: 10.1016/S2213-2600\(25\)00117-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2213-2600(25)00117-1)
52. T. Suchak; A.E. Aliu; C. Harrison; et al. Explosion of formulaic research articles, including inappropriate study designs and false discoveries, based on the NHANES US national health database, 2025. [DOI: 10.1371/journal.pbio.3003152](https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pbio.3003152)
53. T.K. Goswami. Patent Mill and Paper Mill: Can it Build the Scientific Career or Act as an Academic Barrier, 2025. [DOI: 10.31080/ASMS.2025.09.2089](https://doi.org/10.31080/ASMS.2025.09.2089)
54. U.S. House of Representatives Committee on Science, Space, and Technology Subcommittee on Investigations and Oversight.
55. Paper mills bribe editors to pass peer review, and detecting tumors with a blood draw.
56. Dealing with the perils of "paper mills": How the Bioengineered journal fights fake science.
57. Action against paper mills.
58. The Perils of 'Paper Mills': How Low-Quality Research Endangers Autistic People.
59. Paper mills and the erosion of research credibility: Researchers beware.
60. Addressing Paper Mills and a Way Forward for Journal Security.
61. The Perils and Pitfalls of Special Issues and How to Avoid Them.
62. Industrialized Cheating in Academic Publishing: How to Fight "Paper Mills".
63. Publishing ethics and research integrity.
64. Publishing ethics committee warns of 'problematic pollution' of the scholarly record.
65. Fake academic papers are on the rise: why they're a danger and how to stop them.
66. Paper mills: The 'cartel-like' companies behind fraudulent scientific journals.
67. Paper Mills - The Dark Side of the Academic Publishing Industry.
68. Anyone can start a papermill!.
69. How paper mills damage scholarly work and public trust in science.
70. Building Trust and Strengthening Research Integrity: Trust Markers in the Fight Against Paper Mills.
71. Research with integrity - GenAi, paper mills and inclusivity.
72. End paper mills menace to protect research integrity.
73. Paper Mills: What is this about?.

74. Paper mills pose threat to scientific scholarship.
75. Tackling paper mills and bogus research: Some things are better done together.
76. One academic paper's journey through the mill.
77. Paper mill hits RSC journals.
78. Paper mills: the 'cartel-like' companies behind fraudulent scientific journals.
79. A Paper Mill Target Reflects.
80. Tackling the paper mill proliferation.
81. Research paper mill.
82. Advancing our Understanding of Systematic Manipulation & Paper Mills: Wiley & CWTS Partnership.
83. Paper Mills and Research Misconduct: Facing the Challenges of Scientific Publishing.
84. Plagiarism, paper mills and profit: These scientists are fighting the epidemic of fraudulent science research.
85. The threat of paper mills.
86. Systematic manipulation of the publishing process via 'paper mills'.
87. Russian site peddles paper authorship in reputable journals for up to \$5000 a pop.
88. Want to earn \$10k per month? Join the "journals mafia".
89. The Tadpole Paper Mill.
90. 'The situation has become appalling': fake scientific papers push research credibility to crisis point.
91. The Iranian Plant Paper Mill.
92. The Stock Photo Paper Mill.
93. Trouble at paper mill.
94. The Chinese Paper Mill Industry: Interview with Smut Clyde and Tiger BB8.
95. Modern Science Has a Publish-or-Perish Problem.
96. Correcting the record: retracting papermill articles.
97. Wiley's 'fake science' scandal is just the latest chapter in a broader crisis of trust universities must address.
98. Wiley shuts 19 scholarly journals amid AI paper mill problems.
99. Wiley Launches Paper Mill Detection Tool after Losing Millions Due to Fraudulent Journal Submissions.
100. Nineteen journals shut down by Wiley following delisting and paper mill problems.
101. Plagiarism, Paper Mills, and Profit: These Scientists Are Fighting the Epidemic of Fraudulent Research.
102. Tackling publication manipulation at scale: Hindawi's journey and lessons for academic

- publishing.
103. Hindawi reveals process for retracting more than 8,000 paper mill articles.
 104. Hindawi's mass retraction of "Special Issues" papers.
 105. Hindawi shuttering four journals overrun by paper mills.
 106. A Tale of Two Publishing Models: The Impact of Paper Mills and the Guest Editor Model.
 107. The Hindawi Files. Part 1: The Timeline.
 108. The Hindawi Files. Part 2: Hindawi.
 109. The Hindawi Files. Part 3: Wiley.
 110. Publisher shuts 19 journals amid AI paper mill problems.
 111. Publisher shuts 19 journals amid AI paper mill problems.
 112. Reading the Leaves of Publishing Speed: The Cases of Hindawi, Frontiers, and PLOS.
 113. Wiley and Hindawi to retract 1,200 more papers for compromised peer review.
 114. Hindawi Garbage Sorting System, Based on Citations.
 115. More is not better: the developing crisis of scientific publishing.
 116. News Feature: Predatory Journals and Paper Mills.
 117. Fake peer review and paid authorship in Educational Technology research.
 118. Fake Science: Where is academic integrity heading?.
 119. Dealing with the perils of "paper mills": How the Bioengineered journal fights fake science.
 120. Academic Misconduct in Research: Fabrication/Falsification/Plagiarism/Paper Mills.
 121. An epidemic of scientific fakery threatens to overwhelm publishers.
 122. Journal plagued with problematic papers, likely from paper mills, pauses submissions.
 123. Researcher Claims 2% of Published Papers Resemble Paper Mill Works.
 124. Up to one in seven submissions to hundreds of Wiley journals flagged by new paper mill tool.
 125. China's fake science industry: how 'paper mills' threaten progress.
 126. Study reveals scale of 'science scam' in academic publishing.

3 Contract Cheating and Essay Mills

1. R. Clarke; T. Lancaster. Commercial aspects of contract cheating, 2013.
DOI: [10.1145/2462476.2462497](https://doi.org/10.1145/2462476.2462497)
2. C. Ellis; I.M. Zucker; D. Randall. The infernal business of contract cheating: under-

- standing the business processes and models of academic custom writing sites, 2018. DOI: [10.1007/s40979-017-0024-3](https://doi.org/10.1007/s40979-017-0024-3)
3. T. Bretag; R. Harper; M. Burton; et al. Contract cheating and assessment design: exploring the relationship, 2018. DOI: [10.1080/02602938.2018.1527892](https://doi.org/10.1080/02602938.2018.1527892)
 4. P.M. Newton. How Common Is Commercial Contract Cheating in Higher Education and Is It Increasing? A Systematic Review, 2018. DOI: [10.3389/feduc.2018.00067](https://doi.org/10.3389/feduc.2018.00067)
 5. E.J. Morris. Academic integrity matters: five considerations for addressing contract cheating, 2018. DOI: [10.1007/s40979-018-0038-5](https://doi.org/10.1007/s40979-018-0038-5)
 6. D. Medway; S. Roper; L. Gillooly. Contract cheating in UK higher education: A covert investigation of essay mills, 2018. DOI: [10.1002/berj.3335](https://doi.org/10.1002/berj.3335)
 7. M.J. Draper; C. Reid-Hutchings. Are essay mills committing fraud? A further analysis of their behaviours vs the 2006 fraud act (UK), 2019. DOI: [10.1007/s40979-019-0050-4](https://doi.org/10.1007/s40979-019-0050-4)
 8. M. Naughton. Why Do University Students in the UK Buy Assignments from Essay Mills?, 2020. DOI: [10.14288/ce.v11i10.186534](https://doi.org/10.14288/ce.v11i10.186534)
 9. T. Lancaster. Academic Discipline Integration by Contract Cheating Services and Essay Mills, 2020. DOI: [10.1007/s10805-019-09357-x](https://doi.org/10.1007/s10805-019-09357-x)
 10. T. Lancaster. Commercial contract cheating provision through micro-outsourcing web sites, 2020. DOI: [10.1007/s40979-020-00053-7](https://doi.org/10.1007/s40979-020-00053-7)
 11. J. Yorke; L. Sefcik; T. Veeran-Colton. Contract cheating and blackmail: a risky business?, 2020. DOI: [10.1080/03075079.2020.1730313](https://doi.org/10.1080/03075079.2020.1730313)
 12. C. Scurr. Reflections on academic integrity during COVID-19, 2020. DOI: [10.11575/cpai.v3i2.71647](https://doi.org/10.11575/cpai.v3i2.71647)
 13. G.J. Curtis; M. McNeill; C. Slade; et al. Moving beyond self-reports to estimate the prevalence of commercial contract cheating: an Australian study, 2021. DOI: [10.1080/03075079.2021.1972093](https://doi.org/10.1080/03075079.2021.1972093)
 14. I.D. Erguvan. The rise of contract cheating during the COVID-19 pandemic: a qualitative study through the eyes of academics in Kuwait, 2021. DOI: [10.1186/s40468-021-00149-y](https://doi.org/10.1186/s40468-021-00149-y)
 15. K. Ahsan; S. Akbar; B. Kam. Contract cheating in higher education: a systematic literature review and future research agenda, 2021. DOI: [10.1080/02602938.2021.1931660](https://doi.org/10.1080/02602938.2021.1931660)
 16. G. Hill; J. Mason; A. Dunn. Contract cheating: an increasing challenge for global academic community arising from COVID-19, 2021. DOI: [10.1186/s41039-021-00166-8](https://doi.org/10.1186/s41039-021-00166-8)
 17. M. Draper; T. Lancaster; S. Dann; R. Crockett; I. Glendinning. Essay mills and other contract cheating services: to buy or not to buy and the consequences of students changing their minds, 2021. DOI: [10.1007/s40979-021-00081-x](https://doi.org/10.1007/s40979-021-00081-x)

18. C. Crook; E. Nixon. How internet essay mill websites portray the student experience of higher education, 2021. DOI: [10.1016/j.iheduc.2020.100775](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.iheduc.2020.100775)
19. T. Lancaster; C. Cotarlan. Contract cheating by STEM students through a file sharing website: a Covid-19 pandemic perspective, 2021. DOI: [10.1007/s40979-021-00070-0](https://doi.org/10.1007/s40979-021-00070-0)
20. C. McCarthy. Address the rise in contract cheating amid the virtual learning environment, 2021. DOI: [10.1002/say.30877](https://doi.org/10.1002/say.30877)
21. R. Comas-Forgas; T. Lancaster; A. Calvo-Sastre; J. Sureda-Negre. Exam cheating and academic integrity breaches during the COVID-19 pandemic: An analysis of internet search activity in Spain, 2021. DOI: [10.1016/j.heliyon.2021.e08233](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2021.e08233)
22. B.C. Gray. Ethics, EdTech, and the Rise of Contract Cheating, 2021. DOI: [10.11575/cpai.v4i2.74106](https://doi.org/10.11575/cpai.v4i2.74106)
23. C. Parnther. The Rise of Contract Cheating in Graduate Education, 2022. DOI: [10.1007/978-3-031-12680-2_17](https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-12680-2_17)
24. J.A. Byrne; Y. Park; R.A.K. Richardson; et al. Protection of the human gene research literature from contract cheating organizations known as research paper mills, 2022. DOI: [10.1093/nar/gkac1139](https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkac1139)
25. R. Awdry; B. Ives. International Predictors of Contract Cheating in Higher Education, 2022. DOI: [10.1007/s10805-022-09449-1](https://doi.org/10.1007/s10805-022-09449-1)
26. I.D. Erguvan. University students' understanding of contract cheating: a qualitative case study in Kuwait, 2022. DOI: [10.1186/s40468-022-00208-y](https://doi.org/10.1186/s40468-022-00208-y)
27. R. Kjellgren; N. Hamilton-Smith; A. Fraser. Criminal Grades? Contract cheating and student exploitation in Higher Education, 2022. DOI: [10.15496/PUBLIKATION-73679](https://doi.org/10.15496/PUBLIKATION-73679)
28. S.E. Eaton; G.J. Curtis; B.M. Stoesz; et al. (Editors). *Contract Cheating in Higher Education: Global Perspectives on Theory, Practice, and Policy*. 2022. ISBN: [9783031126796](https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-12679-6)
29. G.J. Curtis; J. Clare; E. Vieira; E. Selby; P.K. Jonason. Predicting contract cheating intentions: Dark personality traits, attitudes, norms, and anticipated guilt and shame, 2022. DOI: [10.1016/j.paid.2021.111277](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.paid.2021.111277)
30. S. Sweeney. Who wrote this? Essay mills and assessment - Considerations regarding contract cheating and AI in higher education, 2023. DOI: [10.1016/j.ijme.2023.100818](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijme.2023.100818)
31. K.A.A. Gamage; S.C. P. Dehideniya; Z. Xu; X. Tang. Contract cheating in higher education: Impacts on academic standards and quality, 2023. DOI: [10.37074/jalt.2023.6.2.24](https://doi.org/10.37074/jalt.2023.6.2.24)
32. Y. Xiong; Z. Pan; L. Yang. Did Online Education Exacerbate Contract Cheating During COVID19 in China? Evidence From Sina Weibo, 2023. DOI: [10.28945/5181](https://doi.org/10.28945/5181)
33. S.E. Eaton; J.J. Carmichael. Fake Degrees and Credential Fraud, Contract Cheating, and Paper Mills: Overview and Historical Perspectives, 2023.

- [DOI: 10.1007/978-3-031-21796-8_1](https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-21796-8_1)
34. R. Rahimi; J. Jones; C. Bailey. Exploring contract cheating in further education: student engagement and academic integrity challenges, 2024.
[DOI: 10.1080/17449642.2023.2299193](https://doi.org/10.1080/17449642.2023.2299193)
 35. N. Gaumann; M. Veale. AI providers as criminal essay mills? Large language models meet contract cheating law, 2024. [DOI: 10.1080/13600834.2024.2352692](https://doi.org/10.1080/13600834.2024.2352692)
 36. L.P. Hollis. Contracting During COVID-19: Why Academic Integrity Issues Spread with the Pandemic?, 2024. [DOI: 10.1007/978-3-031-54144-5_115](https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-54144-5_115)
 37. T.P. Johnson-Clements; G.J. Curtis; J. Clare. Testing a Psychological Model of Post-Pandemic Academic Cheating, 2024. [DOI: 10.1007/s10805-024-09561-4](https://doi.org/10.1007/s10805-024-09561-4)
 38. P.M. Newton; K. Essex. How Common is Cheating in Online Exams and did it Increase During the COVID-19 Pandemic? A Systematic Review, 2024.
[DOI: 10.1007/s10805-023-09485-5](https://doi.org/10.1007/s10805-023-09485-5)
 39. B. Mtshweni. A theoretical review of contract cheating in master's and doctoral studies: Some global trends and perspectives, 2024. [DOI: 10.20853/38-6-5942](https://doi.org/10.20853/38-6-5942)
 40. C. Ellis. Understanding Contract Cheating Businesses, 2024.
[DOI: 10.1007/978-3-031-54144-5_109](https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-54144-5_109)
 41. N. Liyanagamage; E. Asylguzhina; P. Vel; et al. Methodological and Ethical Approaches to Studying Contract Cheating: A Systematic Literature Review, 2025.
[DOI: 10.1007/s10805-025-09599-y](https://doi.org/10.1007/s10805-025-09599-y)
 42. [The Devil's in the Detail – Counting Unique and Organic Contract Cheating Sites Targeting Higher Education Students in the UAE as a Call to Delegitimize Them.](#)
 43. [Contract cheating.](#)
 44. [Contracting to Cheat in Higher Education.](#)
 45. [Essay mill.](#)
 46. [Contract cheating.](#)
 47. [Combatting contract cheating: Legislation, research, and institutional action.](#)
 48. [Contract Cheating.](#)
 49. [What is contract cheating? What does it have to do with academic integrity?.](#)
 50. [Higher Education Cheating Services Prohibition Bill.](#)
 51. [The rise of contract cheating in higher education: academic fraud beyond plagiarism.](#)
 52. [Contract cheating: How academic dishonesty could endanger national security.](#)
 53. [Contract cheating - a problem that probably won't cool down anytime soon.](#)
 54. [What can essay mills teach us about artificial intelligence?.](#)

55. [Essay mills explained: What they are and why you should avoid them.](#)
56. [Essay mills and their growing threat to UK academic integrity.](#)
57. [Using the law to tackle essay mills.](#)
58. [Essay mills to be banned under plans to reform post-16 education.](#)
59. [Essay mills and academic integrity.](#)
60. ["Universities to blame" for profiteering essay mills.](#)
61. [‘Essay Mills’ Pose Serious Risk to Scottish Universities.](#)
62. [The essay mills undermining academic standards around the world.](#)
63. [Latest study reveals sharp rise in essay cheating globally, with millions of students involved.](#)
64. [Academic Integrity and the Management of Essay Mills.](#)
65. [The importance of academic integrity: AI and essay mills.](#)
66. [Important notice: Essay writing services now illegal in the UK.](#)
67. [Essay Mills \(Prohibition\).](#)
68. [Tackling Contract Cheating, Ghostwriters and Essay Mills in Higher Education.](#)
69. [A small victory against the essay mill profiteers.](#)
70. [Our exemplary work map/ Samples of our work.](#)
71. [Contract cheating: a hornet’s nest further stirred up by Covid-19.](#)
72. [The challenges of contract cheating in education and solutions to overcome them.](#)
73. [Covid-19 is threatening to unleash a pandemic of cheating.](#)
74. [Has the pandemic driven more students to cheat?.](#)
75. [Trouble at mill: protecting students from contract cheating.](#)
76. [Contract Cheating: The Pandemic with no Vaccine and Pakistan Higher Education.](#)
77. [Contract cheating is now a mainstream issue says ICAI.](#)
78. [Rise in student cheating during the Covid-19 pandemic, say universities.](#)
79. [Impact of COVID-19 on Contract Cheating.](#)
80. [Essay mills ‘targeting students’ as pandemic crisis shifts HE online.](#)
81. [Pandemic sees rise in suspected exam cheating and collusion cases.](#)
82. [Let’s Talk About the Other Pandemic: Academic Cheating.](#)
83. [How Bad Was the Pandemic for Academic Integrity?.](#)
84. [TNE academic integrity under threat from contract cheating.](#)
85. [Rise in "pay to cheat" university assignments during pandemic.](#)
86. [The dangers of contract cheating companies.](#)
87. [Cheating on the rise in UK universities during Covid, say researchers.](#)
88. [COVID-19 creates a new marketplace for contract cheating.](#)

89. UK students are being hit by a wave of essay-writing scammers.
90. COVID-19, Contract Cheating and Academic Integrity in Online Courses: What you need to know.
91. EdTech Goes Undercover: An Insider’s View of What Students Post on Contract Cheating Sites.
92. The Rise of Plagiarism: Contract Cheating.
93. How the ‘Contract Cheating’ Industry Has Gotten More Aggressive in Recruiting Students.
94. The Student Cheating Surge Lurking in the Shadows of COVID-19.
95. A decade of international student cheating scandals.
96. Academic cheating skyrockets during pandemic: UCalgary researcher.
97. Essay mills are now illegal - Skills Minister calls on internet service platforms to crack down on advertising.
98. Prosecution of contract cheating.

4 Role of Artificial Intelligence in Knowledge Production

1. C. Labbe; D. Labbe; F. Portet. Detection of Computer-Generated Papers in Scientific Literature, 2016. DOI: [10.1007/978-3-319-24403-7_8](https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-24403-7_8)
2. E. Abd-Elaal; S.H.P.W. Gamage; J.E. Mills. Artificial Intelligence Is a Tool for Cheating Academic Integrity, 2019. https://aaee.net.au/wp-content/uploads/2020/07/AAEE2019_Annual_Conference_paper_180.pdf
3. G. Cabanac; C. Labbé; A. Magazinov. Tortured phrases: A dubious writing style emerging in science. Evidence of critical issues affecting established journals, 2021. DOI: [10.48550/arXiv.2107.06751](https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2107.06751)
4. H. Else. ‘Tortured phrases’ give away fabricated research papers, 2021. DOI: [10.1038/d41586-021-02134-0](https://doi.org/10.1038/d41586-021-02134-0)
5. J. Gu; X. Wang; C. Li; et al. AI-enabled image fraud in scientific publications, 2022. DOI: [10.1016/j.patter.2022.100511](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.patter.2022.100511)
6. Y. Gendron; J. Andrew; C. Cooper. The perils of artificial intelligence in academic publishing, 2022. DOI: [10.1016/j.cpa.2021.102411](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cpa.2021.102411)
7. J.A. Oravec. AI, biometric analysis, and emerging cheating detection systems: The engineering of academic integrity?, 2022. DOI: [10.14507/epaa.30.5765](https://doi.org/10.14507/epaa.30.5765)

8. Editorial. Tools such as ChatGPT threaten transparent science; here are our ground rules for their use, 2023. DOI: [10.1038/d41586-023-00191-1](https://doi.org/10.1038/d41586-023-00191-1)
9. F.R. Elali; L.N. Rachid. AI-generated research paper fabrication and plagiarism in the scientific community, 2023. DOI: [10.1016/j.patter.2023.100706](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.patter.2023.100706)
10. C. Stokel-Walker. ChatGPT listed as author on research papers: many scientists disapprove, 2023. DOI: [10.1038/d41586-023-00107-z](https://doi.org/10.1038/d41586-023-00107-z)
11. M.A. Yeo. Academic integrity in the age of Artificial Intelligence (AI) authoring apps, 2023. DOI: [10.1002/tesj.716](https://doi.org/10.1002/tesj.716)
12. M.M. Mijwil; K.K. Hiran; R. Doshi; et al. ChatGPT and the Future of Academic Integrity in the Artificial Intelligence Era: A New Frontier, 2023. DOI: [10.55145/ajest.2023.02.02.015](https://doi.org/10.55145/ajest.2023.02.02.015)
13. D.R.E. Cotton; P.A. Cotton; J.R. Shipway. Chatting and cheating: Ensuring academic integrity in the era of ChatGPT, 2023. DOI: [10.1080/14703297.2023.2190148](https://doi.org/10.1080/14703297.2023.2190148)
14. G. Currie; C. Singh; T. Nelson; et al. ChatGPT in medical imaging higher education, 2023. DOI: [10.1016/j.radi.2023.05.011](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.radi.2023.05.011)
15. H. Liu; M. Azam; S. Bin Naeem. An overview of the capabilities of ChatGPT for medical writing and its implications for academic integrity, 2023. DOI: [10.1111/hir.12509](https://doi.org/10.1111/hir.12509)
16. E.P.H. Choi; J.J. Lee; M.-H. Ho; J.Y.Y. Kwok; K.Y.W. Lok. Chatting or cheating? The impacts of ChatGPT and other artificial intelligence language models on nurse education, 2023. DOI: [10.1016/j.nedt.2023.105796](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nedt.2023.105796)
17. S.A. Bin-Nashwan; M. Sadallah; M. Bouteraa. Use of ChatGPT in academia: Academic integrity hangs in the balance, 2023. DOI: [10.1016/j.techsoc.2023.102370](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techsoc.2023.102370)
18. J. Miao; C. Thongprayoon; S. Suppadungsuk; et al. Ethical Dilemmas in Using AI for Academic Writing and an Example Framework for Peer Review in Nephrology Academia: A Narrative Review, 2023. DOI: [10.3390/clinpract14010008](https://doi.org/10.3390/clinpract14010008)
19. S. Sweeney. Who wrote this? Essay mills and assessment - Considerations regarding contract cheating and AI in higher education, 2023. DOI: [10.1016/j.ijme.2023.100818](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijme.2023.100818)
20. M. Perkins. Academic Integrity considerations of AI Large Language Models in the post-pandemic era: ChatGPT and beyond, 2023. DOI: [10.53761/1.20.02.07](https://doi.org/10.53761/1.20.02.07)
21. D. Birks; J. Clare. Linking artificial intelligence facilitated academic misconduct to existing prevention frameworks, 2023. DOI: [10.1007/s40979-023-00142-3](https://doi.org/10.1007/s40979-023-00142-3)
22. **Chan2023**
23. M. Rodrigues; R. Silva; A.P. Borges; M. Franco; C. Oliveira. Artificial intelligence: threat or asset to academic integrity? A bibliometric analysis, 2024. DOI: [10.1108/k-09-2023-1666](https://doi.org/10.1108/k-09-2023-1666)

24. K.M. Hammond; P. Lucas; A. Hassouna; S. Brown. A Wolf in Sheep's Clothing? Critical Discourse Analysis of Five Online Automated Paraphrasing Sites, 2024. DOI: [10.53761/1.20.7.08](https://doi.org/10.53761/1.20.7.08)
25. A. Bozkurt. GenAI et al.: Cocreation, Authorship, Ownership, Academic Ethics and Integrity in a Time of Generative AI, 2024. DOI: [10.55982/openpraxis.16.1.654](https://doi.org/10.55982/openpraxis.16.1.654)
26. D. Kwon. AI is complicating plagiarism. How should scientists respond?, 2024. DOI: [10.1038/d41586-024-02371-z](https://doi.org/10.1038/d41586-024-02371-z)
27. V.R. Lee; D. Pope; S. Miles; R.C. Zarate. Cheating in the age of generative AI: A high school survey study of cheating behaviors before and after the release of ChatGPT, 2024. DOI: [10.1016/j.caeai.2024.100253](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.caeai.2024.100253)
28. E. Martel; M. Lentschat; C. Labbe. Detection of tortured phrases in scientific literature, 2024. DOI: [10.48550/arXiv.2402.03370](https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2402.03370)
29. N. Gaumann; M. Veale. AI providers as criminal essay mills? Large language models meet contract cheating law, 2024. DOI: [10.1080/13600834.2024.2352692](https://doi.org/10.1080/13600834.2024.2352692)
30. Y.K. Dwivedi; T. Malik; L. Hughes; M.A. Albashrawi. Scholarly Discourse on GenAI's Impact on Academic Publishing, 2024. DOI: [10.1080/08874417.2024.2435386](https://doi.org/10.1080/08874417.2024.2435386)
31. C. Zhai; S. Wibowo; L.D. Li. The effects of over-reliance on AI dialogue systems on students' cognitive abilities: a systematic review, 2024. DOI: [10.1186/s40561-024-00316-7](https://doi.org/10.1186/s40561-024-00316-7)
32. C.K.Y. Chan. Students' perceptions of 'AI-giarism': investigating changes in understandings of academic misconduct, 2024. DOI: [10.1007/s10639-024-13151-7](https://doi.org/10.1007/s10639-024-13151-7)
33. Z. Chen; C. Chen; G. Yang; et al. Research integrity in the era of artificial intelligence: Challenges and responses, 2024. DOI: [10.1097/MD.00000000000038811](https://doi.org/10.1097/MD.00000000000038811)
34. H.M. Nguyen; D. Goto. Unmasking academic cheating behavior in the artificial intelligence era: Evidence from Vietnamese undergraduates, 2024. DOI: [10.1007/s10639-024-12495-4](https://doi.org/10.1007/s10639-024-12495-4)
35. C. Gonsalves. Addressing student non-compliance in AI use declarations: implications for academic integrity and assessment in higher education, 2024. DOI: [10.1080/02602938.2024.2415654](https://doi.org/10.1080/02602938.2024.2415654)
36. R. Padillah. Ghostwriting: a reflection of academic dishonesty in the artificial intelligence era, 2024. DOI: [10.1093/pubmed/fdad169](https://doi.org/10.1093/pubmed/fdad169)
37. J. Haider; K.R. Soderstrom; B. Ekstrom; M. Rodl. GPT-fabricated scientific papers on Google Scholar: Key features, spread, and implications for preempting evidence manipulation, 2024. DOI: [10.37016/mr-2020-156](https://doi.org/10.37016/mr-2020-156)
38. D. Kwon. Is it OK for AI to write science papers? Nature survey shows researchers are

- split, 2025. DOI: [10.1038/d41586-025-01463-8](https://doi.org/10.1038/d41586-025-01463-8)
39. D. Spinellis. False authorship: an explorative case study around an AI-generated article published under my name, 2025. DOI: [10.1186/s41073-025-00165-z](https://doi.org/10.1186/s41073-025-00165-z)
 40. H. Balalle; S. Pannilage. Reassessing academic integrity in the age of AI: A systematic literature review on AI and academic integrity, 2025. DOI: [10.1016/j.ssaho.2025.101299](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ssaho.2025.101299)
 41. G.J. Curtis. The two-lane road to hell is paved with good intentions: why an all-or-none approach to generative AI, integrity, and assessment is insupportable, 2025. DOI: [10.1080/07294360.2025.2476516](https://doi.org/10.1080/07294360.2025.2476516)
 42. J. Song; S. Liu. Dark personality traits are associated with academic misconduct, frustration, negative thinking, and generative AI use habits: the case of Sichuan art universities, 2025. DOI: [10.1186/s40359-025-02949-w](https://doi.org/10.1186/s40359-025-02949-w)
 43. C. O'Grady. Low-quality papers surge thanks to public data and AI, 2025. DOI: [10.1126/science.adz1715](https://doi.org/10.1126/science.adz1715)
 44. T. Suchak; A.E. Aliu; C. Harrison; et al. Explosion of formulaic research articles, including inappropriate study designs and false discoveries, based on the NHANES US national health database, 2025. DOI: [10.1371/journal.pbio.3003152](https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pbio.3003152)
 45. [The promise and perils of generative AI: Experts weigh in.](#)
 46. [The real threat of AI-Powered research paper mills to academic publishers.](#)
 47. [AI-generated content vs plagiarism: where do we draw the line?.](#)
 48. [What is the potential of AI writing? Is cheating its greatest purpose?.](#)
 49. [How much are students using AI in their writing?.](#)
 50. [What's Your Source? Plagiarism, AI, and the Mess We've Created.](#)
 51. [AI makes plagiarism harder to detect, argue academics - in paper written by chatbot.](#)
 52. [Artificial intelligence and academic integrity, post-plagiarism.](#)
 53. [What happens when a machine can write as well as an academic?.](#)
 54. [Australian universities to return to 'pen and paper' exams after students caught using AI to write essays.](#)
 55. [Mathgen paper accepted!.](#)
 56. [In the beginning it was just plagiarism - now its computer-generated fake papers as well.](#)
 57. [Dr Assignment: Assignment & Essay Writing Help.](#)
 58. ["Publish-or-perish" and ChatGPT: a dangerous mix.](#)
 59. [Beyond Burnout: AI as an Academic Ally in the "Publish or Perish" Culture.](#)
 60. [Wiley shuts 19 scholarly journals amid AI paper mill problems.](#)
 61. [The Plagiarism Pandemic: How AI is Infecting Academic Integrity.](#)

62. [ChatGPT Is a Plague Upon Education.](#)
63. [From Open Access Pioneer to Retraction Scandal: The Fall of Hindawi.](#)
64. [Retractions Increase 10-Fold in 20 Years - and Now AI is Involved.](#)
65. [AI Chatbots Have Thoroughly Infiltrated Scientific Publishing.](#)
66. [As scientists explore AI-written text, journals hammer out policies.](#)
67. [AI plagiarism changers: What academic leaders need to know.](#)
68. [AI plagiarism changers: How academic leaders can prepare institutions.](#)
69. [The Challenges of AI Plagiarism in Academia.](#)
70. [Revealed: Thousands of UK university students caught cheating using AI.](#)
71. [‘I massively regret using AI to cheat at uni’.](#)
72. [Cheating or Plagiarizing with AI Made Easy: There’s Software for That Now.](#)
73. [‘Nobody is blind to it’: mass cheating through AI puts integrity of Australian universities at risk, academics claim.](#)
74. [What do AI chatbots really mean for students and cheating?.](#)
75. [NYC education department blocks ChatGPT on school devices, networks.](#)
76. [AI is shaking cheating prevention: We need to redefine the solution!.](#)
77. [Everyone Is Cheating Their Way Through College: ChatGPT has unraveled the entire academic project.](#)
78. [Tortured phrases: common behavior of language models.](#)
79. [Tortured phrases: What they are, how they are detected, and how to avoid them.](#)
80. [Using Tortured Phrases to Spot Problematic Papers.](#)
81. [Morressier teams up with academic fraud sleuths to bring tortured-phrase detection to publishing workflows.](#)
82. [Plagiarism and Academic Misconduct: Artificial Intelligence.](#)
83. [Academic Dishonesty Using Generative AI.](#)
84. [The financial impact of AI on institutions through breaches of academic integrity.](#)
85. [Educators Battle Plagiarism As 89% Of Students Admit To Using OpenAI’s ChatGPT For Homework.](#)
86. [Generative AI should mark the end of a failed war on student academic misconduct.](#)
87. [What can essay mills teach us about artificial intelligence?.](#)
88. [The importance of academic integrity: AI and essay mills.](#)
89. [Academic Publishers Are Missing the Point on ChatGPT.](#)
90. [Generative AI Has a Visual Plagiarism Problem: Experiments with Midjourney and DALL-E 3 show a copyright minefield.](#)
91. [The financial impact of AI on institutions through breaches of academic integrity.](#)

92. Risks of AI-enabled academic misconduct flagged in new study.
93. AI Has Hurt Academic Integrity in College Courses but Can Also Enhance Learning, Say Instructors, Students.
94. Generative AI and academic misconduct: Helping students to navigate the grey.
95. The evolving risk to academic integrity posed by generative artificial intelligence: Options for immediate action.
96. University creates 'AI' category for academic misconduct after rise in cases.
97. AI in universities: the fine line between help and misconduct.
98. Artificial Intelligence Is a Tool for Cheating Academic Integrity.
99. From plagiarism to AI: the changing face of academic dishonesty.
100. The Negative Impact of AI on Academic Integrity in Tertiary Education.
101. Successfully Overturning an AI-Related Academic Misconduct Allegation.
102. Universities struggle to keep pace with AI integrity challenges.
103. How AI Has Undermined the Integrity of Academic Research and Writing Originality.
104. The software says my student cheated using AI. They say they're innocent. Who do I believe?.
105. New Data Reveal How Many Students Are Using AI to Cheat.
106. Use of AI apps is fuelling plagiarism, as barrister warns more needs to be done to stop online exam cheating.
107. Now AI can write students' essays for them, will everyone become a cheat?.
108. ChatGPT May Be Eroding Critical Thinking Skills, According to a New MIT Study.

5 Questionable Authorship Practices

1. R.T. Pennock. Inappropriate Authorship in Collaborative Science Research, 1996. Source: <https://www.jstor.org/stable/40435966>
2. A. Flanagan; L.A. Carey; P.B. Fontanarosa; S.G. Phillips; B.P. Pace; G.D. Lundberg; D. Rennie. Prevalence of articles with honorary authors and ghost authors in peer-reviewed medical journals, 1998. DOI: [10.1001/jama.280.3.222](https://doi.org/10.1001/jama.280.3.222)
3. G. Mowatt; L. Shirran; J.M. Grimshaw; et al. Prevalence of Honorary and Ghost Authorship in Cochrane Reviews, 2002. DOI: [10.1001/jama.287.21.2769](https://doi.org/10.1001/jama.287.21.2769)
4. D.M. Bennett; D.M. Taylor. Unethical practices in authorship of scientific papers, 2003. DOI: [10.1046/j.1442-2026.2003.00432.x](https://doi.org/10.1046/j.1442-2026.2003.00432.x)
5. S.S. Hwang; H.H. Song; J.H. Baik; et al. Researcher Contributions and Fulfillment of

- ICMJE Authorship Criteria: Analysis of Author Contribution Lists in Research Articles with Multiple Authors Published in Radiology, 2003. DOI: [10.1148/radiol.2261011255](https://doi.org/10.1148/radiol.2261011255)
6. S. Ngai; J.L. Gold; S.S. Gill; P.A. Rochon. Haunted Manuscripts: Ghost Authorship in the Medical Literature, 2005. DOI: [10.1080/08989620590957175](https://doi.org/10.1080/08989620590957175)
 7. L.S. Kwok. The White Bull effect: abusive coauthorship and publication parasitism, 2005. DOI: [10.1136/jme.2004.010553](https://doi.org/10.1136/jme.2004.010553)
 8. P. Borry; P. Schotsmans; K. Dierickx. Author, contributor or just a signer? A quantitative analysis of authorship trends in the field of bioethics, 2006. DOI: [10.1111/j.1467-8519.2006.00496.x](https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-8519.2006.00496.x)
 9. P.C. Gotzsche; A. Hrobjartsson; H.K. Johansen; et al. Ghost Authorship in Industry-Initiated Randomised Trials, 2007. DOI: [10.1371/journal.pmed.0040019](https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pmed.0040019)
 10. B. Moffatt; C. Elliott. Ghost marketing: pharmaceutical companies and ghostwritten journal articles, 2007. DOI: [10.1353/pbm.2007.0009](https://doi.org/10.1353/pbm.2007.0009)
 11. M. Greene. The demise of the lone author, 2007. DOI: [10.1038/4501165a](https://doi.org/10.1038/4501165a)
 12. C. Baethge. Publish Together or Perish, 2008. DOI: [10.3238/arztebl.2008.0380](https://doi.org/10.3238/arztebl.2008.0380)
 13. K. Strange. Authorship: why not just toss a coin?, 2008. DOI: [10.1152/ajpcell.00208.2008](https://doi.org/10.1152/ajpcell.00208.2008)
 14. E. Berger. Ghostwriters, Data Manipulation and Dollar Diplomacy: How Drug Companies Pull the Strings in Clinical Research, 2008. DOI: [10.1016/j.annemergmed.2008.06.009](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.annemergmed.2008.06.009)
 15. V. Barbour; J. Clark; S. Jones; et al. Ghostwriting: The Dirty Little Secret of Medical Publishing That Just Got Bigger, 2009. DOI: [10.1371/journal.pmed.1000156](https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pmed.1000156)
 16. P.C. Gotzsche; J.P. Kassirer; K.L. Woolley; et al. What Should Be Done To Tackle Ghostwriting in the Medical Literature?, 2009. DOI: [10.1371/journal.pmed.1000023](https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pmed.1000023)
 17. P.K. Baskin; R.A. Gross. Honorary and ghost authorship, 2011. DOI: [10.1136/BMJ.D6223](https://doi.org/10.1136/BMJ.D6223)
 18. R.L. Eisenberg; L. Ngo; P.M. Boiselle; A.A. Bankier. Honorary Authorship in Radiologic Research Articles: Assessment of Frequency and Associated Factors, 2011. DOI: [10.1148/radiol.11101500](https://doi.org/10.1148/radiol.11101500)
 19. J.S. Wislar; A. Flanagan; P.B Fontanarosa; C.D. Deangelis. Honorary and ghost authorship in high impact biomedical journals: a cross sectional survey, 2011. DOI: [10.1136/bmj.d6128](https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.d6128)
Also see DOI: [10.1136/bmj.d7677](https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.d7677)
 20. B. Dotson; R.L. Slaughter. Prevalence of articles with honorary and ghost authors in three pharmacy journals, 2011. DOI: [10.2146/ajhp100583](https://doi.org/10.2146/ajhp100583)

21. S.A. Zaki. Gift authorship - A cause for concern, 2011. DOI: [10.4103/0970-2113.83994](https://doi.org/10.4103/0970-2113.83994)
22. V. Barbour; J. Clark; S. Jones; et al. Ghostwriting Revisited: New Perspectives but Few Solutions in Sight, 2011. DOI: [10.1371/journal.pmed.1001084](https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pmed.1001084)
23. S.B. Bavdekar. Authorship issues, 2012. DOI: [10.4103/0970-2113.92371](https://doi.org/10.4103/0970-2113.92371)
24. F.S. Chew. Coauthorship in radiology journals, 2012. DOI: [10.2214/ajr.150.1.23](https://doi.org/10.2214/ajr.150.1.23)
25. S. Bonekamp; V.G. Halappa; C.P. Corona-Villalobos; et al. Prevalence of Honorary Coauthorship in the American Journal of Roentgenology, 2012. DOI: [10.2214/AJR.11.8253](https://doi.org/10.2214/AJR.11.8253)
26. P. Greenland; P.B. Fontanarosa. Ending Honorary Authorship, 2012. DOI: [10.1126/science.1224988](https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1224988)
27. X. Bosch; J.S. Ross. Ghostwriting: research misconduct, plagiarism, or fool's gold?, 2012. DOI: [10.1016/j.amjmed.2011.07.015](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.amjmed.2011.07.015)
28. A.Y. Gasparyan; L. Ayvazyan; G.D. Kitas. Authorship problems in scholarly journals: considerations for authors, peer reviewers and editors, 2012. DOI: [10.1007/s00296-012-2582-2](https://doi.org/10.1007/s00296-012-2582-2)
29. R.M. Slone. Coauthors' contributions to major papers published in the AJR: frequency of undeserved coauthorship, 2013. DOI: [10.2214/ajr.167.3.8751654](https://doi.org/10.2214/ajr.167.3.8751654)
30. S. Stern; T. Lemmens. Legal remedies for medical ghostwriting: Imposing fraud liability on guest authors of ghostwritten articles, 2013. DOI: [10.1179/2047480613Z.000000000164](https://doi.org/10.1179/2047480613Z.000000000164)
31. M.S. Kennedy; J. Barnsteiner; J. Daly. Honorary and Ghost Authorship in Nursing Publications, 2014. DOI: [10.1111/jnu.12093](https://doi.org/10.1111/jnu.12093)
32. S. Rajasekaran; R.L.P. Shan; J.T. Finnoff. Honorary Authorship: Frequency and Associated Factors in Physical Medicine and Rehabilitation Research Articles, 2014. DOI: [10.1016/j.apmr.2013.09.024](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apmr.2013.09.024)
33. J. Schofferman; F.T. Wetzell; C. Bono. Ghost and Guest Authors: You Can't Always Trust Who You Read, 2015. DOI: [10.1111/pme.12579](https://doi.org/10.1111/pme.12579)
34. J.W. Jones; L.B. McCullough. Is a gift authorship really a gift authorship?, 2015. DOI: [10.1016/j.jvs.2015.02.006](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jvs.2015.02.006)
35. B. Macfarlane. The ethics of multiple authorship: power, performativity and the gift economy, 2015. DOI: [10.1080/03075079.2015.1085009](https://doi.org/10.1080/03075079.2015.1085009)
36. S. Syed; D.Q. Tran; A.R. Kemper; J.W. St Geme III; J.D. Lantos. Authorship Concerns and Who Truly Owns a Research Idea?, 2015. DOI: [10.1542/peds.2015-1421](https://doi.org/10.1542/peds.2015-1421)
37. F.E. Vera-Badillo; M. Napoleone; M.K. Krzyzanowska; et al. Honorary and ghost authorship in reports of randomised clinical trials in oncology, 2016.

- DOI: [10.1016/j.ejca.2016.06.023](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejca.2016.06.023)
38. E.A. Fong; A.W. Wilhite. Authorship and citation manipulation in academic research, 2017. DOI: [10.1371/journal.pone.0187394](https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0187394)
39. L.A. Harvey. Gift, honorary or guest authorship, 2018. DOI: [10.1038/s41393-017-0057-8](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41393-017-0057-8)
40. S. Yadav; G. Rawal. Ghostwriters in the scientific world, 2018. DOI: [10.11604/pamj.2018.30.217.16312](https://doi.org/10.11604/pamj.2018.30.217.16312)
41. I. Masic. The Malversations of Authorship - Current Status in Academic Community and How to Prevent It, 2018. DOI: [10.5455/aim.2018.26.4-9](https://doi.org/10.5455/aim.2018.26.4-9)
42. W. Bulow; G. Helgesson. Hostage authorship and the problem of dirty hands, 2018. DOI: [10.1177/1747016118764305](https://doi.org/10.1177/1747016118764305)
43. B.L. Tang. Responding to devious demands for co-authorship: A rejoinder to Bulow and Helgesson's 'dirty hands' justification, 2018. DOI: [10.1177/1747016118798876](https://doi.org/10.1177/1747016118798876)
44. H. Rivera. Inappropriate Authorship and Kinship in Research Evaluation, 2018. DOI: [10.3346/jkms.2018.33.e105](https://doi.org/10.3346/jkms.2018.33.e105)
45. G. Helgesson; N. Juth; J. Schneider; et al. Misuse of Coauthorship in Medical Theses in Sweden, 2018. DOI: [10.1177/1556264618784206](https://doi.org/10.1177/1556264618784206)
46. L.A. Maggio; A.R. Artino Jr; C.J. Watling; E.W. Driessen; B.C. O'Brien. Exploring researchers' perspectives on authorship decision making, 2019. DOI: [10.1111/medu.13950](https://doi.org/10.1111/medu.13950)
47. S.-K. Min. Unjustified Authorship such as Gift Authorship for Your Kids: It Is a Crime, Professor, 2019. DOI: [10.5758/vsi.2019.35.4.181](https://doi.org/10.5758/vsi.2019.35.4.181)
48. H. Rivera. Fake Peer Review and Inappropriate Authorship Are Real Evils, 2019. DOI: [10.3346/jkms.2019.34.e6](https://doi.org/10.3346/jkms.2019.34.e6)
49. V. Ranieri. Questionable authorship and the problem of dirty hands: throwing missing authorship into the ring. In response to both Bulow and Helgesson, and Tang, 2019. DOI: [10.1177/1747016119865728](https://doi.org/10.1177/1747016119865728)
50. G. Helgesson; S. Eriksson. Authorship order, 2019. DOI: [10.1002/leap.1191](https://doi.org/10.1002/leap.1191)
51. J.A.T. da Silva. Is there a need for creators of imaginary authors to face legal consequences?, 2020. DOI: [10.3325/cmj.2020.61.561](https://doi.org/10.3325/cmj.2020.61.561)
52. M.C. Burger. Caught between a ghost and a gift: Navigating authorship issues, 2020. DOI: [10.17159/2309-8309/2020/v19n3a0](https://doi.org/10.17159/2309-8309/2020/v19n3a0)
53. G. Helgesson. Authorship order and effects of changing bibliometrics practices, 2020. DOI: [10.1177/1747016119898403](https://doi.org/10.1177/1747016119898403)
54. E. Quaia; F. Crimi. Honorary Authorship: Is There Any Chance to Stop It? Analysis of the Literature and a Personal Opinion, 2021. DOI: [10.3390/tomography7040067](https://doi.org/10.3390/tomography7040067)

55. K. Bisht. Don't make early career researchers 'ghost authors'. Give us the credit we deserve, 2021. DOI: [10.1126/science.caredit.acx9061](https://doi.org/10.1126/science.caredit.acx9061)
56. S. Miles; A. Renedo; C. Marston. Reimagining authorship guidelines to promote equity in co-produced academic collaborations, 2021. DOI: [10.1080/17441692.2021.1971277](https://doi.org/10.1080/17441692.2021.1971277)
57. F. Hesselmann; C. Schendzielorz; N. Sorgatz. Say my name, say my name: Academic authorship conventions between editorial policies and disciplinary practices, 2021. DOI: [10.1093/reseval/rvab003](https://doi.org/10.1093/reseval/rvab003)
58. A. Ruben. Why scientific journal authorship practices make no sense et al. 2021. DOI: [10.1126/science.acx9504](https://doi.org/10.1126/science.acx9504)
59. C. Ni; E. Smith; H. Yuan; et al. The gendered nature of authorship, 2021. DOI: [10.1126/sciadv.abe4639](https://doi.org/10.1126/sciadv.abe4639)
60. G. Pruschak; C. Hopp. And the credit goes to ... - Ghost and honorary authorship among social scientists, 2022. DOI: [10.1371/journal.pone.0267312](https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0267312)
61. M.J. Ali; A. Djalilian. Readership Awareness Series - Paper 1: Ghost Authorship, 2022. DOI: [10.1080/08820538.2022.2112852](https://doi.org/10.1080/08820538.2022.2112852)
62. G.A. Justin; S.C. Miller; B. Tsou; et al. Ghost and Honorary Authorship in Ophthalmology: A Cross-Sectional Survey, 2022. DOI: [10.1016/j.ajo.2022.02.012](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ajo.2022.02.012)
63. R.M. Reynders; G. ter Riet; N. Di Girolamo; M. Malicki. Honorary authorship in health sciences: a protocol for a systematic review of survey research, 2022. DOI: [10.1186/s13643-022-01928-1](https://doi.org/10.1186/s13643-022-01928-1)
64. J. Brainard. 'Honorary authors' of scientific papers abound-but they probably shouldn't, 2022. DOI: [10.1126/science.adf0963](https://doi.org/10.1126/science.adf0963)
65. P. Khezzr; V. Mohan. The vexing but persistent problem of authorship misconduct in research, 2022. DOI: [10.1016/j.respol.2021.104466](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.respol.2021.104466)
66. M. Kandil. Honorary Authorship in Biomedical Journals: The Endless Story, 2022. DOI: [10.32388/UUBXG8.3](https://doi.org/10.32388/UUBXG8.3)
67. K. Thompson; L. Corrin; J.M. Lodge; G.-J. Hwang. Authorship practices in educational technology research, 2022. DOI: [10.14742/ajet.7980](https://doi.org/10.14742/ajet.7980)
68. D.B. Nikumbh. Ghost authorship Vs Gift authorship, 2022. DOI: [10.18231/j.achr.2022.033](https://doi.org/10.18231/j.achr.2022.033)
69. P. Nelson; M.G. Petrova. Research assistants: Scientific credit and recognized authorship, 2022. DOI: [10.1002/leap.1467](https://doi.org/10.1002/leap.1467)
70. D.H. Whetstone; L.E. Ridenour; H. Moulaison-Sandy. Questionable authorship practices across the disciplines: Building a multidisciplinary thesaurus using evolutionary concept analysis, 2022. DOI: [10.1016/j.lisr.2022.101201](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lisr.2022.101201)

71. S.H. Kim; J.I. Jung. Authorship and Inappropriate Authorship from an Ethical Publication Perspective, 2022. DOI: [10.3348/jksr.2022.0040](https://doi.org/10.3348/jksr.2022.0040)
72. Z. Barta. Publication games: In the web of reciprocity, 2022. DOI: [10.1371/journal.pone.0270618](https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0270618)
73. A.A. Khalifa. Losing young researchers in the authorship battle, under-reported casualties, 2022. DOI: [10.1016/j.jemep.2021.100735](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jemep.2021.100735)
74. T. Shamim. Authorship disputes and amicable solutions in scholarly publication: the road ahead, 2023. DOI: [10.22034/ncm.2023.410729.1109](https://doi.org/10.22034/ncm.2023.410729.1109)
75. D. Stockemer; T. Reidy. Academic misconduct, fake authorship letters, cyber fraud: Evidence from the International Political Science Review, 2023. DOI: [10.1002/leap.1587](https://doi.org/10.1002/leap.1587)
76. T.C. Kwee; M.T. Almaghrabi; R.M. Kwee. Scientific Fraud, Publication Bias, and Honorary Authorship in Nuclear Medicine, 2023. DOI: [10.2967/jnumed.122.264679](https://doi.org/10.2967/jnumed.122.264679)
77. D.S. Chawla. Unearned authorship pervades science, 2023. DOI: [10.1038/d41586-023-00016-1](https://doi.org/10.1038/d41586-023-00016-1)
78. M.P. Goddixsen; M.W. Johansen; A.C. Armond; et al. "The person in power told me to" - European PhD students' perspectives on guest authorship and good authorship practice, 2023. DOI: [10.1371/journal.pone.0280018](https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0280018)
79. S. De Peuter; J. Reck; S. Bellekens; G. Storms. Gift and ghost authorship and the use of authorship guidelines in psychology journals: A cross-sectional survey, 2024. DOI: [10.1177/17470161241262244](https://doi.org/10.1177/17470161241262244)
80. R.A.M. Reynders; G. ter Riet; N. Di Girolamo; et al. Honorary authorship is highly prevalent in health sciences: systematic review and meta-analysis of surveys, 2024. DOI: [10.1038/s41598-024-54909-w](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-024-54909-w)
81. E. Picano. Who is the author: genuine, honorary, ghost, gold, and fake authors?, 2024. DOI: [10.37349/ec.2024.00024](https://doi.org/10.37349/ec.2024.00024)
82. M. Hosseini; A.O. Holcombe; M. Kovacs; et al. Group authorship, an excellent opportunity laced with ethical, legal and technical challenges, 2024. DOI: [10.1080/08989621.2024.2322557](https://doi.org/10.1080/08989621.2024.2322557)
83. G. Young; A. Serbati; K.N. Sim. Collaboration and co-authorship in academic development: what should we be considering?, 2024. DOI: [10.1080/1360144X.2024.2397418](https://doi.org/10.1080/1360144X.2024.2397418)
84. H. Zwart; Y. Tenhagen; M. Hosseini; J. Dore. Consortium Authorship: Ethical Tensions in Emerging Authorship Practices in Interdisciplinary Collaborative Research, 2024. DOI: [10.1007/s10805-024-09592-x](https://doi.org/10.1007/s10805-024-09592-x)
85. S.J. Porter; L.D. McIntosh. Identifying fabricated networks within authorship-for-sale enterprises, 2024. DOI: [10.1038/s41598-024-71230-8](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-024-71230-8)

86. L.I. Meho; E.A. Akl. Using Bibliometrics to Detect Unconventional Authorship Practices and Examine Their Impact on Global Research Metrics, 2019-2023, 2024. DOI: [10.48550/arXiv.2407.18331](https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2407.18331)
87. R. Padillah. Ghostwriting: a reflection of academic dishonesty in the artificial intelligence era, 2024. DOI: [10.1093/pubmed/fdad169](https://doi.org/10.1093/pubmed/fdad169)
88. M. Kumar. Handle with care: authorship challenges and conflicts in research publication, 2024. DOI: [10.18203/2394-6040.ijcmph20243677](https://doi.org/10.18203/2394-6040.ijcmph20243677)
89. D. Spinellis. False authorship: an explorative case study around an AI-generated article published under my name, 2025. DOI: [10.1186/s41073-025-00165-z](https://doi.org/10.1186/s41073-025-00165-z)
90. M. Khodakarami; F. MohammadRezaei; A. Sarlak; M. Garg; Z. Rezaee. Free-riding in academic co-authorship: The marginalization of research students, 2025. DOI: [10.1016/j.respol.2024.105165](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.respol.2024.105165)
91. H. Else. Does sharing first authorship on a paper carry a penalty? What the research says, 2025. DOI: [10.1038/d41586-025-00869-8](https://doi.org/10.1038/d41586-025-00869-8)
92. L.I. Meho; E.A. Akl. Using bibliometrics to detect questionable authorship and affiliation practices and their impact on global research metrics: A case study of 14 universities, 2025. DOI: [10.1162/qss_a_00339](https://doi.org/10.1162/qss_a_00339)
93. V. Pallotti; V.A. Caroselli; M.E. Esandi; M. del Carmen Esandi. Questionable Practices Concerning Authorship and Their Prevalence: An Umbrella Review of Evidence, 2025. DOI: [10.1007/s10805-025-09656-6](https://doi.org/10.1007/s10805-025-09656-6)
94. S. Macdonald. Authorship in Academic Publishing and the Thirst for Citation, 2025. DOI: [10.2139/ssrn.5134231](https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.5134231)
95. G. Abramo; C.A. D'Angelo. Hyperprolific authorship: Unveiling the extent of extreme publishing in the 'publish or perish' era, 2025. DOI: [10.1016/j.joi.2025.101658](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.joi.2025.101658)
96. [Honorary and Ghost Authorship: Is it Ethical?.](#)
97. [Ghost Authorship, Gift Authorship, Guest Authorship - 3 Practices to Avoid.](#)
98. [The Difference Between Honorary and Ghost Authorship in Scientific Research.](#)
99. [One in five medical journal articles include honorary and ghost authors, study finds.](#)
100. [Honorary and Ghost Authorship: Is it Ethical?.](#)
101. ['Salami slicing' and improper authorship plague Italian research.](#)
102. [Tackling Contract Cheating, Ghostwriters and Essay Mills in Higher Education.](#)
103. [The Difference Between Honorary and Ghost Authorship in Scientific Research.](#)
104. [Honorary or gift authorship: What is this about?.](#)
105. [The Ethical Dilemma of Honorary Authorship in Academic Research.](#)

106. Types of authorship misconduct.
107. Does authorship mean anything when academic papers are simply citable tokens?.
108. Ghost Authorship, Gift Authorship, Guest Authorship - 3 Practices to Avoid.
109. Is there any one to defend Honorary (forced) authorship? if not why we practice it!.
110. Authorship resources.
111. What is Ghost, Guest, and Gift Authorship in Research?.
112. What is Ghost Authorship in Scholarly Publishing?.
113. Authorship in Academia: Ghost, Guest, and Gift Authorship.
114. Ghostwriting in academic journals: How can we mitigate its impact on research integrity?.
115. Ghost Authorship in Journal Manuscripts.
116. Halloween Special: The Ghosts and Guests of Academia.
117. The ghost author: would be the worst authorship irregularity?.
118. Academic authorship.
119. The Ethics of Authorship: Is Ghostwriting Plagiarism?.
120. One in five medical journal articles include honorary and ghost authors.
121. Faking it in academia - the rise of authorship fraud.
122. Dealing With Fake Co-Authors: A New Publishing Problem.
123. Preventing Authorship Fraud: Tips for Academic Publishers.
124. What's in a Name: Fictitious Authors in Science.
125. The gift of paper authorship.
126. How & Why Are Researchers Faking Co-Authors on Research Papers?.
127. Authorship: contributions, disputes, and misconduct.
128. A Field Guide to Authorship Fraud.
129. Fake peer review and paid authorship in Educational Technology research.
130. Retraction of false authorship.
131. The challenge of Fake authors in journals.
132. "A new form of plagiarism": When researchers fake co-authors' names.
133. A new way to fake authorship: Submit under a prominent name, then say it was a mistake.
134. Paid Co-Authors or Guest Authors: a Problem of Scientific Publishing.
135. What's in a Name: Fictitious Authors in Science.
136. 'My professor demands to be listed as an author on many of my papers'.
137. My master's thesis advisor just asked me to share a first-authorship with another student; should I?.

138. Order of authors.
139. False affiliations and fake authors.
140. Fake attributions: a persistent and evolving research integrity problem.
141. How to Identify Gift and Paid Authorships in Research Articles.
142. 7 signs a scientific paper's authorship was bought.
143. Adding scientists to a paper because the added author will pay APC charges.
144. Russian website offers authorship for a fee in papers accepted for publication.
145. Authorship For Sale. Papers For Sale. Everything For Sale.
146. Authorship for sale: Some journals willing to add authors to papers they didn't write.
147. Science Publisher Company: Detailed description of the co-authorship service.
148. Co-authorship.
149. Who is in Charge? Understanding Authorship Order Changes in Academic Publishing.
150. Questionable authorship information.
151. How ethical is the practice of including spouses as co-authors when they are in the same field?.
152. Charlotte Bronte authors a paper on pesticides: The role of forged authorship in predatory publishing.

6 Self-Plagiarism and Text Recycling

1. C. Binder. Self-plagiarism and multiple publications: Negligence or epidemic disease?, 1990. DOI: [10.1530/acta.0.1220007](https://doi.org/10.1530/acta.0.1220007)
2. D.M. Bennett; D.M. Taylor. Unethical practices in authorship of scientific papers, 2003. DOI: [10.1046/j.1442-2026.2003.00432.x](https://doi.org/10.1046/j.1442-2026.2003.00432.x)
3. L. Green. Reviewing the Scourge of Self-Plagiarism, 2005. DOI: [10.5204/mcj.2426](https://doi.org/10.5204/mcj.2426)
4. P.M. Scanlon. Song From Myself: An Anatomy of Self-Plagiarism, 2007. Source: <http://hdl.handle.net/2027/spo.5240451.0002.007>
5. T. Bretag; S. Carapiet. A Preliminary Study to Identify the Extent of Self-Plagiarism in Australian Academic Research, 2007. Source: <https://quod.lib.umich.edu/p/plag/5240451.0002.010/>
6. J.G. Baggs. Issues and rules for authors concerning authorship versus acknowledgements, dual publication, self plagiarism, and salami publishing, 2008. DOI: [10.1002/nur.20280](https://doi.org/10.1002/nur.20280)
7. M. Errami; H. Garner. A tale of two citations, 2008. DOI: [10.1038/451397a](https://doi.org/10.1038/451397a)

8. K. Bazdaric; L. Bilic-Zulle; G. Brumini; M. Petroveckii. Prevalence of Plagiarism in Recent Submissions to the Croatian Medical Journal, 2011. DOI: [10.1007/s11948-011-9347-2](https://doi.org/10.1007/s11948-011-9347-2)
9. D.A. Bonnell; J.M. Buriak; J.H. Hafner; et al. Recycling Is Not Always Good: The Dangers of Self-Plagiarism, 2012. DOI: [10.1021/nm3000912](https://doi.org/10.1021/nm3000912)
10. B.R. Martin. Whither research integrity? Plagiarism, self-plagiarism and coercive citation in an age of research assessment, 2013. DOI: [10.1016/j.respol.2013.03.011](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.respol.2013.03.011)
11. S. Harriman; J. Patel. Text recycling: acceptable or misconduct?, 2014. DOI: [10.1186/s12916-014-0148-8](https://doi.org/10.1186/s12916-014-0148-8)
12. T.M. Culley. APPS's stance on self-plagiarism: Just say no, 2014. DOI: [10.3732/apps.1400055](https://doi.org/10.3732/apps.1400055)
13. J.L. Callahan. Creation of a Moral Panic? Self-Plagiarism in the Academy, 2014. DOI: [10.1177/1534484313519063](https://doi.org/10.1177/1534484313519063)
14. E. Wager. Why Is Redundant Publication a Problem?, 2015. PMID: [25588220](https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/25588220/)
15. B. Joob; V. Wiwanitkit. Scientific misconduct and self-plagiarism, 2016. DOI: [10.1016/j.ajog.2015.12.011](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ajog.2015.12.011)
16. C. Moskovitz. Self-Plagiarism, Text Recycling, and Science Education, 2016. DOI: [10.1093/biosci/biv160](https://doi.org/10.1093/biosci/biv160)
17. R.H. Thurman; F.A. Chervenak; L.B. McCullough; S. Halwani; D. Farine. Self-plagiarism: a misnomer, 2016. DOI: [10.1016/j.ajog.2015.09.004](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ajog.2015.09.004)
18. J.L. Callahan. The retrospective (im)moralization of self-plagiarism: Power interests in the social construction of new norms for publishing, 2017. DOI: [10.1177/1350508417734926](https://doi.org/10.1177/1350508417734926)
19. C. Moskovitz. Text recycling in health sciences research literature: a rhetorical perspective, 2017. DOI: [10.1186/s41073-017-0025-z](https://doi.org/10.1186/s41073-017-0025-z)
20. S. Hall; C. Moskovitz; M.A. Pemberton. Attitudes toward text recycling in academic writing across disciplines, 2018. DOI: [10.1080/08989621.2018.1434622](https://doi.org/10.1080/08989621.2018.1434622)
21. S.P.J.M. Horbach; W. Halffman. The extent and causes of academic text recycling or 'self-plagiarism', 2019. DOI: [10.1016/j.respol.2017.09.004](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.respol.2017.09.004)
22. L.K. Burdine; M.B. de Castro Maymone; N.A. Vashi. Text recycling: Self-plagiarism in scientific writing, 2019. DOI: [10.1016/j.ijwd.2018.10.002](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijwd.2018.10.002)
23. I.G. Anson; C. Moskovitz. Text recycling in STEM: A text-analytic study of recently published research articles, 2020. DOI: [10.1080/08989621.2020.1850284](https://doi.org/10.1080/08989621.2020.1850284)
24. M. Krokoszcz. Plagiarism in articles published in journals indexed in the Scientific Periodicals Electronic Library (SPELL): a comparative analysis between 2013 and 2018,

2021. DOI: [10.1007/s40979-020-00063-5](https://doi.org/10.1007/s40979-020-00063-5)
25. J. Geraldi. Self-Plagiarism in Project Studies: A Call for Action and Reflection, 2021. DOI: [10.1177/8756972820982445](https://doi.org/10.1177/8756972820982445)
 26. C. O’Grady. When is ‘self-plagiarism’ OK? New guidelines offer researchers rules for recycling text, 2021. DOI: [10.1126/science.abk1548](https://doi.org/10.1126/science.abk1548)
 27. A. Muraleedharan; B.A. Kumar. The malady of redundant publications: Common yet poorly understood, 2022. DOI: [10.4103/jcrsm.jcrsm_85_22](https://doi.org/10.4103/jcrsm.jcrsm_85_22)
 28. C. Moskovitz; S. Hall; M. Pemberton. Common Misconceptions about Text Recycling in Scientific Writing, 2022. DOI: [10.1093/biosci/biac090](https://doi.org/10.1093/biosci/biac090)
 29. K.D. Klika. Text Recycling and Excessive Attribution: A Pragmatic Perspective, 2022. DOI: [10.3138/jsp-2022-0026](https://doi.org/10.3138/jsp-2022-0026)
 30. S.K. Yadav. Redundant Publications, 2023. DOI: [10.1007/978-3-031-26971-4_6](https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-26971-4_6)
 31. R.A. Isaacson. Text Recycling in Scientific Writing: What Editors Need to Know, 2023. DOI: [10.36591/SE-D-4603-10](https://doi.org/10.36591/SE-D-4603-10)
 32. C. Moskovitz; D.R. Hansen; M. Yelverton. Legalize text recycling, 2023. DOI: [10.1002/leap.1550](https://doi.org/10.1002/leap.1550)
 33. Editorial. When it is and isn’t OK to recycle text in scientific papers, 2024. DOI: [10.1038/s41562-024-01862-3](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41562-024-01862-3)
 34. Y.V. Sevryugina; Y. Li. Self-plagiarism: A retrospective study of its prevalence and patterns across scientific disciplines, 2025. DOI: [10.1080/08989621.2025.2472016](https://doi.org/10.1080/08989621.2025.2472016)
 35. [A preliminary study to identify the extent of self-plagiarism in Australian academic research.](#)
 36. [Self-Plagiarism and Self-Citation: A Practical Guide Based on Underlying Principles.](#)
 37. [Fresh concerns raised over academic conduct of major US nutrition and behaviour lab.](#)
 38. [Retractions arrive in plagiarism scandal involving economist Nijkamp.](#)
 39. [Least publishable unit.](#)
 40. [Misconduct and redundant publication.](#)
 41. [‘Salami slicing’ and improper authorship plague Italian research.](#)
 42. [What is the Impact of Self-Plagiarism for Researchers?.](#)
 43. [Self Plagiarism.](#)
 44. [Addressing misunderstandings around self-plagiarism and inadvertent plagiarism in research.](#)
 45. [self plagiarism and online publication... some musings.](#)
 46. [Self-Plagiarism: How to Define It and Why You Should Avoid It.](#)

47. Problematic nature of self-plagiarism: An ethical grey area.
48. Text recycling and self-plagiarism in research.
49. Text recycling guidelines for editors.
50. Clearing Up the Murky Rules Around "Self-Plagiarism".
51. How can text recycling be harmful? Text recycling as a questionable research practice.
52. Copyright Infringement, Fair Use, and Plagiarism.
53. Self-plagiarism or fair use?.
54. Copyright issues and Self-Plagiarism in the PhD Thesis.
55. UGC mandate against self-plagiarism to prevent 'pay and publish trash culture'.

7 Plagiarism

1. D. Nitterhouse. Plagiarism - Not Just an "Academic" Problem, 2003.
DOI: [10.1023/A:1025017019246](https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1025017019246)
2. G.A. Hoover. Whose Line Is It? Plagiarism in Economics, 2004.
DOI: [10.1257/0022051041409066](https://doi.org/10.1257/0022051041409066)
3. D.A. Thomas. How Educators Can More Effectively Understand and Combat the Plagiarism Epidemic, 2004.
Source: https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=1185782
4. L. Bilic-Zulle; V. Frkovic; T. Turk; J. Azman; M. Petrovecki. Prevalence of plagiarism among medical students, 2005. PMID: [15726686](https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/15726686/)
5. M.P. Anderson. Plagiarism, Copyright Violation, and Dual Publication: Are you guilty?, 2006. DOI: [10.1111/j.1745-6584.2006.00246.x](https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1745-6584.2006.00246.x)
6. K. Vessal; F. Habibzadeh. Rules of the game of scientific writing: fair play and plagiarism, 2007. DOI: [10.1016/S0140-6736\(07\)60307-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(07)60307-9)
7. P. Wicker. Plagiarism: Understanding and Management, 2007.
DOI: [10.1177/175045890701700802](https://doi.org/10.1177/175045890701700802)
8. G. Brumfiel. Turkish physicists face accusations of plagiarism, 2007.
DOI: [10.1038/449008b](https://doi.org/10.1038/449008b)
9. I. Yilmaz. Plagiarism? No, we're just borrowing better English, 2007.
DOI: [10.1038/449658a](https://doi.org/10.1038/449658a)
10. S. Zwagerman. The Scarlet P: Plagiarism, Panopticism, and the Rhetoric of Academic, 2008. DOI: [10.58680/ccc20086674](https://doi.org/10.58680/ccc20086674)
11. L.J. Murray. Plagiarism and Copyright Infringement: The Costs of Confusion, 2008.

- DOI: [10.2307/j.ctv65sxk1.18](https://doi.org/10.2307/j.ctv65sxk1.18)
12. B. Derby. Duplication and plagiarism increasing among students, 2008.
DOI: [10.1038/452029c](https://doi.org/10.1038/452029c)
 13. S. Vasconcelos; J. Leta; L. Costa; A. Pinto; M.M. Sorenson. Discussing plagiarism in Latin American science. Brazilian researchers begin to address an ethical issue, 2009.
DOI: [10.1038/embor.2009.134](https://doi.org/10.1038/embor.2009.134)
 14. R.J. Rohrich; D. Sullivan. Plagiarism and Dual Publication: Review of the Issues and Policy Statement, 2009. DOI: [10.1097/PRS.0b013e3181b59d42](https://doi.org/10.1097/PRS.0b013e3181b59d42)
 15. R. Sinha; G. Singh; C. Kumar. Plagiarism and unethical practices in literature, 2009.
PMC: [2812776](https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/2812776/)
 16. Y. Zhang. Chinese journal finds 31% of submissions plagiarized, 2010.
DOI: [10.1038/467153d](https://doi.org/10.1038/467153d)
 17. D. Butler. Journals step up plagiarism policing, 2010. DOI: [10.1038/466167a](https://doi.org/10.1038/466167a)
 18. V. Pupovac; L. Bilic-Zulle; M. Mavrinac; M. Petroveckii. Attitudes toward plagiarism among pharmacy and medical biochemistry students - cross-sectional survey study, 2010. DOI: [10.11613/BM.2010.039](https://doi.org/10.11613/BM.2010.039)
 19. B.K. McFarlin; T.S. Lyons; J.W. Navalta. Prevalence of Plagiarism in Manuscript Submissions and Solutions, 2010. DOI: [10.70252/TETR5308](https://doi.org/10.70252/TETR5308)
 20. C. Park. In Other (People's) Words: Plagiarism by university students—literature and lessons, 2010. DOI: [10.1080/02602930301677](https://doi.org/10.1080/02602930301677)
 21. R. Comas-Forgas; J. Sureda-Negre; F. Salva-Mut. Academic plagiarism prevalence among Spanish undergraduate students: an exploratory analysis, 2010.
DOI: [10.11613/BM.2010.038](https://doi.org/10.11613/BM.2010.038)
 22. K. Bazdaric; L. Bilic-Zulle; G. Brumini; M. Petroveckii. Prevalence of Plagiarism in Recent Submissions to the Croatian Medical Journal, 2011.
DOI: [10.1007/s11948-011-9347-2](https://doi.org/10.1007/s11948-011-9347-2)
 23. M.S. Anderson; N.H. Steneck. The problem of plagiarism, 2011.
DOI: [10.1016/j.urolonc.2010.09.013](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.urolonc.2010.09.013)
 24. T. Ahmad; I. Ghosh. Plagiarism and Copyright Infringement, 2011.
DOI: [10.2139/ssrn.1839353](https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.1839353)
 25. B. Honig; A. Bedi. The Fox in the Hen House: A Critical Examination of Plagiarism Among Members of the Academy of Management, 2012. DOI: [10.5465/amle.2010.0084](https://doi.org/10.5465/amle.2010.0084)
 26. S.F. Karabag; C. Berggren. Retraction, Dishonesty and Plagiarism: Analysis of a Crucial Issue for Academic Publishing, and the Inadequate Responses from Leading Journals in Economics and Management Disciplines, 2012.

Source: https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=2190694

27. D.C. Ison. Not Just a Student Problem: Plagiarism in Aviation Academic Research, 2012. DOI: [10.15394/jaaer.2012.1408](https://doi.org/10.15394/jaaer.2012.1408)
28. T.A. Voelker; L.G. Love; I. Pentina. Plagiarism: What Don't They Know?, 2012. DOI: [10.1080/08832323.2011.552536](https://doi.org/10.1080/08832323.2011.552536)
29. I. Masic. Plagiarism in Scientific Publishing, 2012. DOI: [10.5455/aim.2012.20.208-213](https://doi.org/10.5455/aim.2012.20.208-213)
30. M. Biagioli. Recycling Texts or Stealing Time?: Plagiarism, Authorship, and Credit in Science, 2012. DOI: [10.1017/S0940739112000276](https://doi.org/10.1017/S0940739112000276)
31. B.R. Martin. Whither research integrity? Plagiarism, self-plagiarism and coercive citation in an age of research assessment, 2013. DOI: [10.1016/j.respol.2013.03.011](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.respol.2013.03.011)
32. Y. Li. Text-Based Plagiarism in Scientific Publishing: Issues, Developments and Education, 2013. DOI: [10.1007/s11948-012-9367-6](https://doi.org/10.1007/s11948-012-9367-6)
33. L. Yusuf; A. Aseffa. Plagiarism - time to strike at the epidemic, 2013. Source: <https://ejhd.org/index.php/ejhd/article/view/174>
34. R.M.V.R. Almeida; K. de Albuquerque Rocha; F. Catelani; et al. Plagiarism Allegations Account for Most Retractions in Major Latin American/Caribbean Databases, 2015. DOI: [10.1007/s11948-015-9714-5](https://doi.org/10.1007/s11948-015-9714-5)
35. R.A.A. Mohammed; O.M. Shaaban; D.G. Mahran; et al. Plagiarism in medical scientific research, 2015. DOI: [10.1016/j.jtumed.2015.01.007](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jtumed.2015.01.007)
36. S.V. Shankar; K. Amita. Plagiarism in Medical Research: Knowns and Unknowns, 2015. DOI: [10.46347/jmsh.2015.v01i03.001](https://doi.org/10.46347/jmsh.2015.v01i03.001)
37. S. Natarajan. Plagiarism - one disease, many manifestations, 2015. DOI: [10.4103/0301-4738.158060](https://doi.org/10.4103/0301-4738.158060)
38. C.J. Debnath. Plagiarism: A silent epidemic in scientific writing - Reasons, recognition and remedies, 2016. DOI: [10.1016/j.mjafi.2016.03.010](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mjafi.2016.03.010)
39. B. Martin. Plagiarism, Misrepresentation, and Exploitation by Established Professionals: Power and Tactics, 2016. DOI: [10.1007/978-981-287-098-8_75](https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-287-098-8_75)
40. J.R. Higgins; F.-C. Lin; J.P. Evans. Plagiarism in submitted manuscripts: incidence, characteristics and optimization of screening-case study in a major specialty medical journal, 2016. DOI: [10.1186/s41073-016-0021-8](https://doi.org/10.1186/s41073-016-0021-8)
41. M. Enserink. Popular French physicist accused of plagiarizing colleagues and famous writers, 2016. DOI: [10.1126/science.aal0481](https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aal0481)
42. M.A. Deshmukh; A.S. Dodamani; M.R. Khairnar; R.G. Naik. Research Misconduct: A Neglected Plague, 2017. DOI: [10.4103/0019-557X.200255](https://doi.org/10.4103/0019-557X.200255)
43. M. Enserink. French physicist accused of plagiarism seems set to lose prestigious job,

2017. DOI: [10.1126/science.aal1011](https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aal1011)
44. S.S. Khadilkar. The Plague of Plagiarism: Prevention and Cure!!!, 2018. DOI: [10.1007/s13224-018-1182-9](https://doi.org/10.1007/s13224-018-1182-9)
45. A. Benmesmoudi. An Epidemic of Plagiarism Strikes our Universities the Current Threat and the Delayed Treatment: A Literature Review Analysis, 2018. DOI: [10.33685/1316-000-048-010](https://doi.org/10.33685/1316-000-048-010)
46. M.F. Abad-Garcia. Plagiarism and predatory journals: A threat to scientific integrity, 2019. DOI: [10.1016/j.anpede.2018.11.006](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.anpede.2018.11.006)
47. B. Hoanca. Combating Plagiarism: A Three-Pronged Approach to Reducing Prevalence in Higher Education, 2019. DOI: [10.4018/978-1-5225-8057-7.ch025](https://doi.org/10.4018/978-1-5225-8057-7.ch025)
48. S. Baskaran; A. Agarwal; M.K.P. Selvam; et al. Is there plagiarism in the most influential publications in the field of andrology?, 2019. DOI: [10.1111/and.13405](https://doi.org/10.1111/and.13405)
49. M.G. Tolsgaard; R. Ellaway; N. Woods; G. Norman. Salami-slicing and plagiarism: How should we respond?, 2019. DOI: [10.1007/s10459-019-09876-7](https://doi.org/10.1007/s10459-019-09876-7)
50. S.-K. Min. Plagiarism in Medical Scientific Research: Can Continuing Education and Alarming Prevent This Misconduct?, 2020. DOI: [10.5758/vsi.203621](https://doi.org/10.5758/vsi.203621)
51. S. Nabee; J. Mageto; N. Pisa. Investigating Predictors of Academic Plagiarism among University Students, 2020. DOI: [10.26803/ijlter.19.12.14](https://doi.org/10.26803/ijlter.19.12.14)
52. O.O. Ogunsuji; O.F. Fagbule. Plagiarism: The Curse of Internet in African Academia?, 2020. PMID: [PMC8369403](https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/8369403/)
53. Z. Toprak; V. Yucel. A peculiar practice of academic writing: Epidemic writing in the Turkish graduate education, 2020. DOI: [10.1080/2331186X.2020.1774098](https://doi.org/10.1080/2331186X.2020.1774098)
54. A.R. Memon. Similarity and Plagiarism in Scholarly Journal Submissions: Bringing Clarity to the Concept for Authors, Reviewers and Editors, 2020. DOI: [10.3346/jkms.2020.35.e217](https://doi.org/10.3346/jkms.2020.35.e217)
55. M.B. Rokni; N. Bizhani; F. Habibzadeh; et al. Comprehensive Survey of Plagiarism in Iran, 2020. DOI: [10.12669/pjms.36.7.3456](https://doi.org/10.12669/pjms.36.7.3456)
56. V. Pupovac. The frequency of plagiarism identified by text-matching software in scientific articles: a systematic review and meta-analysis, 2021. DOI: [10.1007/s11192-021-04140-5](https://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-021-04140-5)
57. N.-E Hafsa. Plagiarism: A Global Phenomenon, 2021. DOI: [10.7176/JEP/12-3-08](https://doi.org/10.7176/JEP/12-3-08)
58. M. Krokosz. Plagiarism in articles published in journals indexed in the Scientific Periodicals Electronic Library (SPELL): a comparative analysis between 2013 and 2018, 2021. DOI: [10.1007/s40979-020-00063-5](https://doi.org/10.1007/s40979-020-00063-5)
59. M.S. Simatupang; R. Peter; E. Murniarti; H. Male; G. Tambunsaribu. The Plagiarism

- Tendency During Covid-19 Pandemic, 2021. DOI: [10.17762/turcomat.v12i14.11381](https://doi.org/10.17762/turcomat.v12i14.11381)
60. M. Radike; C.F. Camm. Plagiarism in medical publishing: each of us can do something about it, 2022. DOI: [10.1093/ehjcr/ytac137](https://doi.org/10.1093/ehjcr/ytac137)
 61. H. Bayram; F. Tikman. Determining Student Teachers' Rates of Plagiarism During the Distance Education and Investigating Possible Reasons for Plagiarism, 2022. DOI: [10.17718/tojde.1050398](https://doi.org/10.17718/tojde.1050398)
 62. R. Menshawey; E. Menshawey; A. Mitkees; B.A. Mahamud. A plagiarism paperdemic: determining plagiarism among COVID-19 articles in infectious disease journals between 2020 and 2021, 2023. DOI: [10.1186/s42269-023-01129-3](https://doi.org/10.1186/s42269-023-01129-3)
 63. Y. Eshet. The plagiarism pandemic: Inspection of academic dishonesty during the COVID-19 outbreak using originality software, 2023. DOI: [10.1007/s10639-023-11967-3](https://doi.org/10.1007/s10639-023-11967-3)
 64. J.A.T. da Silva. "Tortured phrases" in preprints, 2023. DOI: [10.1080/03007995.2023.2201098](https://doi.org/10.1080/03007995.2023.2201098)
 65. D.O. Mireku; P.D. Dzamesi; B. Bervell. Plagiarism in Higher Education (PLAGiHE) within Sub-Saharan Africa: A systematic review of a decade (2012-2022) literature, 2023. DOI: [10.1177/17470161231189646](https://doi.org/10.1177/17470161231189646)
 66. I.E. Putra; N.I. Jazilah; M.S. Adishesa; et al. Denying the accusation of plagiarism: power relations at play in dictating plagiarism as academic misconduct, 2023. DOI: [10.1007/s10734-022-00875-z](https://doi.org/10.1007/s10734-022-00875-z)
 67. S. Deslauriers. Academic Plagiarism: When It Involves Professors, 2024. DOI: [10.15640/jehd](https://doi.org/10.15640/jehd)
 68. M. Sozon; O.H.M. Alkharabsheh; P.W. Fong; S.B. Chuan. Cheating and plagiarism in higher education institutions (HEIs): A literature review, 2024. DOI: [10.12688/f1000research.147140.2](https://doi.org/10.12688/f1000research.147140.2)
 69. E. Martel; M. Lentschat; C. Labbe. Detection of tortured phrases in scientific literature, 2024. DOI: [10.48550/arXiv.2402.03370](https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2402.03370)
 70. A. Abalkina. Prevalence of plagiarism in hijacked journals: A text similarity analysis, 2024. DOI: [10.1080/08989621.2024.2387210](https://doi.org/10.1080/08989621.2024.2387210)
 71. H. Ahmad; M.A. Fauzi. Plagiarism in Academic Writing in Higher Education Institutions: A Bibliometric Analysis, 2024. DOI: [10.46328/ijonses.623](https://doi.org/10.46328/ijonses.623)
 72. R. Mulenga; H. Shilongo. Academic Integrity in Higher Education: Understanding and Addressing Plagiarism, 2024. DOI: [10.53623/apga.v3i1.337](https://doi.org/10.53623/apga.v3i1.337)
 73. K.S. Guba; A.O. Tsivinskaya. Ambiguity in Ethical Standards: Global Versus Local Science in Explaining Academic Plagiarism, 2024. DOI: [10.1007/s11948-024-00464-6](https://doi.org/10.1007/s11948-024-00464-6)
 74. D. Kwon. AI is complicating plagiarism. How should scientists respond?, 2024. DOI:

[10.1038/d41586-024-02371-z](https://doi.org/10.1038/d41586-024-02371-z)

75. Y. Eshet. Examining the dynamics of plagiarism: a comparative analysis before, during, and after the COVID-19 pandemic, 2025. DOI: [10.1007/s40979-024-00178-z](https://doi.org/10.1007/s40979-024-00178-z)
76. B.L. Tang. Authorship credit disputes should all be considered potential cases of plagiarism unless proven otherwise, 2025. DOI: [10.3897/ese.2025.e151110](https://doi.org/10.3897/ese.2025.e151110)
77. [The Plague of Plagiarism: Academic Plagiarism Defined](#). Originally published as "On Plagiarism and Integrity".
78. [Retractions arrive in plagiarism scandal involving economist Nijkamp](#).
79. [Plagiarism is rife in academia, so why is it rarely acknowledged?](#).
80. [The Problems Only Start With Plagiarism](#).
81. [Plagiarism in Academia](#).
82. [Plagiarism, its Types, Consequences, & Prevention](#).
83. [An enduring problem in academia: professors also plagiarize but get away with it](#).
84. [Plagiarism Statistics: An Insight into Issue](#).
85. [Prevalence of Plagiarism in Students Research Papers](#).
86. [Plagiarism is a symptom not a disease](#).
87. [Plagiarism seen to be aiding drop in education standards](#).
88. [What Do We Know about Plagiarism These Days?](#).
89. [The Plagiarism Epidemic: A Threat to Population Research](#).
90. [UK universities in 'plagiarism epidemic' as almost 50,000 students caught cheating over last 3 years](#).
91. [Educators Battle Plagiarism As 89% Of Students Admit To Using OpenAI's ChatGPT For Homework](#).
92. [Plagiarism, Paper Mills, and Profit: These Scientists Are Fighting the Epidemic of Fraudulent Research](#).
93. [Academic integrity: Whose writing is it? Can we stop the plagiarism pandemic?](#).
94. [The Plagiarism Pandemic: How AI is Infecting Academic Integrity](#).
95. [The 'epidemic' of plagiarism at universities](#).
96. [How Bad Was the Pandemic for Academic Integrity?](#).
97. [The Plagiarism Epidemic in Russia](#).
98. [Plagiarism in Master of Education Studies at Selected East African Universities](#).
99. [Embattled Harvard honesty professor accused of plagiarism](#).
100. [Academic Dishonesty and COVID-19: A Biological Explanation](#).
101. [The Rise of Plagiarism: Contract Cheating](#).

102. [Medical writer loses COVID-19-cancer paper for plagiarism.](#)
103. [Plagiarism: a misplaced emphasis.](#)
104. [AI plagiarism changers: What academic leaders need to know.](#)
105. [AI plagiarism changers: How academic leaders can prepare institutions.](#)
106. [The Challenges of AI Plagiarism in Academia.](#)
107. [Tortured phrases: What they are, how they are detected, and how to avoid them.](#)
108. [Detecting tortured phrases to unmask fake science.](#)
109. [Using Tortured Phrases to Spot Problematic Papers.](#)
110. [Addressing misunderstandings around self-plagiarism and inadvertent plagiarism in research.](#)
111. [Morressier teams up with academic fraud sleuths to bring tortured-phrase detection to publishing workflows.](#)
112. [Copyright Infringement, Fair Use, and Plagiarism.](#)
113. ["A new form of plagiarism": When researchers fake co-authors' names.](#)
114. [The Plague of Plagiarism.](#)
115. [The Plagiarism Plague: Declining standards make getting caught the primary offense.](#)
116. [Dealing with the Plague of Plagiarism in Nigeria.](#)
117. [Plagiarism - What Can Curb The Scourge?.](#)
118. [Nigerian universities and the plague of plagiarism.](#)
119. [Copyright infringement vs plagiarism.](#)
120. [Understanding the Distinction between Plagiarism and Copyright Infringement.](#)
121. [Plagiarism vs Copyright Infringement.](#)
122. [Study finds high plagiarism levels in 'hijacked journals'.](#)
123. [Plagiarism Cases in Academic Publishing.](#)
124. [The Economy of Fraud in Academic Publishing in China.](#)
125. [Plagiarism Statistics: An Insight into Issue.](#)
126. [Sample records for plagiarism cases reported.](#)
127. [What Do We Know about Plagiarism These Days?.](#)
128. [Should we be worried about plagiarism in peer review?.](#)
129. [The Common Types of Plagiarism.](#)
130. [7 Common Types of Plagiarism, With Examples.](#)
131. [Types of plagiarism.](#)
132. [The 5 Types of Plagiarism | Explanations & Examples.](#)
133. [Understanding Plagiarism: Forms, Consequences, and How to Avoid It.](#)
134. [The Difference Between Plagiarism and Copyright Infringement.](#)

135. [Understanding the Distinction between Plagiarism and Copyright Infringement.](#)
136. [Famous Plagiarists.](#)
137. [Copycat: 15 Examples of Plagiarism Throughout History.](#)
138. [How a Sharp-Eyed Scientist Became Biology's Image Detective.](#)
139. [Europe's Biggest Plagiarism Cases.](#)
140. [The 10 worst academic plagiarism scandals in history.](#)
141. [Cases of Plagiarism Handled by the United States Office of Research Integrity 1992-2005.](#)
142. [Another Wegman plagiarism copying-without-attribution, and further discussion of why scientists cheat.](#)
143. [Plagiarism \(The Scientist\).](#)
144. [Scientific plagiarism in India.](#)
145. [A Short History of Academic Plagiarism.](#)
146. [Generative AI Has a Visual Plagiarism Problem: Experiments with Midjourney and DALL-E 3 show a copyright minefield.](#)

8 Salami Slicing

1. W.J. Broad. The Publishing Game: Getting More for Less: Meet the Least Publishable Unit, one way of squeezing more papers out of a research project, 1981. DOI: [10.1126/science.7008199](https://doi.org/10.1126/science.7008199)
2. R.W. Buddemeier. Least Publishable Unit, 1981. DOI: [10.1126/science.212.4494.494.a](https://doi.org/10.1126/science.212.4494.494.a)
3. J. Roth. Least Publishable Unit, 1981. DOI: [10.1126/science.212.4494.494.b](https://doi.org/10.1126/science.212.4494.494.b)
4. J. Maddox. Is the salami sliced too thinly?, 1989. DOI: [10.1038/342733a0](https://doi.org/10.1038/342733a0)
5. T. Jefferson. Redundant publication in biomedical sciences: Scientific misconduct or necessity?, 1998. DOI: [10.1007/s11948-998-0043-9](https://doi.org/10.1007/s11948-998-0043-9)
6. G. Walter. Salami: kosher and unkosher, 1999. DOI: [10.1080/0004867990471](https://doi.org/10.1080/0004867990471)
7. S.M. Mojon-Azzi; D.S. Mojon. Scientific Misconduct: From Salami Slicing to Data Fabrication, 2004. DOI: [10.1159/000076104](https://doi.org/10.1159/000076104)
8. Editorial. The cost of salami slicing, 2005. DOI: [10.1038/nmat1305](https://doi.org/10.1038/nmat1305)
9. L. Brochard; C. Brun-Buisson. Salami publication: a frequent practice affecting readers' confidence, 2007. DOI: [10.1007/s00134-007-0539-9](https://doi.org/10.1007/s00134-007-0539-9)
10. J.D. Hoit. Salami science, 2007. DOI: [10.1044/1058-0360\(2007/013\)](https://doi.org/10.1044/1058-0360(2007/013))
11. J.G. Baggs. Issues and rules for authors concerning authorship versus acknowledgements, dual publication, self plagiarism, and salami publishing, 2008.

[DOI: 10.1002/nur.20280](https://doi.org/10.1002/nur.20280)

12. I. Norman; P. Griffiths. Duplicate publication and ‘salami slicing’: Ethical issues and practical solutions, 2008. [DOI: 10.1016/j.ijnurstu.2008.07.003](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijnurstu.2008.07.003)
13. G.I. Spielmans; T.L. Biehn; D.L. Sawrey. A Case Study of Salami Slicing: Pooled Analyses of Duloxetine for Depression, 2009. [DOI: 10.1159/000270917](https://doi.org/10.1159/000270917)
14. T. Stankus. Are "Least Publishable Unit" Brief Communications Articles Still Appearing Sooner After Acceptance in this Era of E-Publishing Ahead of Print? Evidence from Three Bellwether Pairs of Life Science Journals that Feature Separate Editions for Full-Length Articles and Letters Papers, 2009. [DOI: 10.1080/03615260802669128](https://doi.org/10.1080/03615260802669128)
15. P.M. Sherman; S.R. Daniels; S.S. Long; T.R. Welch. Notice: The importance of adhering to The Journal’s Guide for Authors, 2010. [DOI: 10.1016/j.jpeds.2010.02.061](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpeds.2010.02.061)
16. B. Britigan; A. Strauss; J. Susman. Salami science or editorial imperialism?, 2010. [DOI: 10.1016/j.jpeds.2010.07.034](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpeds.2010.07.034)
17. W.J. Dupps Jr.; B.J. Randleman. The perils of the least publishable unit, 2012. [DOI: 10.1016/j.jcrs.2012.07.020](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcrs.2012.07.020)
18. V.S. Smolicic. Salami publication: definitions and examples, 2013. [DOI: 10.11613/BM.2013.030](https://doi.org/10.11613/BM.2013.030)
19. D. Jackson; G. Walter; J. Daly; M. Cleary. Editorial: Multiple outputs from single studies: acceptable division of findings vs. ‘salami’ slicing, 2013. [DOI: 10.1111/jocn.12439](https://doi.org/10.1111/jocn.12439)
20. J. Karlsson; P. Beaufiles. Legitimate division of large data sets, salami slicing and dual publication, where does a fraud begin?, 2013. [DOI: 10.1007/s00167-013-2413-3](https://doi.org/10.1007/s00167-013-2413-3)
21. D.B. Elliott. Salami slicing and the SPU: Publish or Perish?, 2013. [DOI: 10.1111/opo.12090](https://doi.org/10.1111/opo.12090)
22. A.A. Klein; A. Pozniak; J.J. Pandit. Salami slicing or living off the fat? Justifying multiple publications from a single HIV dataset, 2014. [DOI: 10.1111/anae.12603](https://doi.org/10.1111/anae.12603)
23. R. Watson; R. Pickler; J. Noyes; et al. How many papers can be published from one study?, 2014. [DOI: 10.1111/jan.12600](https://doi.org/10.1111/jan.12600)
24. A. Le; C.M.P. Moran; M. Bezuhy; P. Hong. Duplicate publications and related problems in published papers on oral and maxillofacial surgery, 2015. [DOI: 10.1016/j.bjoms.2015.03.008](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bjoms.2015.03.008)
25. V. Menon; A. Muraleedharan. Salami Slicing of Data Sets: What the Young Researcher Needs to Know, 2016. [DOI: 10.4103/0253-7176.194906](https://doi.org/10.4103/0253-7176.194906)
26. B. Happell. Salami: By the slice or swallowed whole?, 2016. [DOI: 10.1016/j.apnr.2015.08.011](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apnr.2015.08.011)
27. S. Natarajan. Salami publishing: Walking on thin (sl)ice, 2016.

[DOI: 10.4103/0301-4738.198848](https://doi.org/10.4103/0301-4738.198848)

28. R. Gray; C. Baker. Salami slicing, 2016. [DOI: 10.1111/jpm.12290](https://doi.org/10.1111/jpm.12290)
29. M.B. Wallace; D. Bowman; H. Hamilton-Gibbs; P.D. Siersema. Ethics in publication, part 2: duplicate publishing, salami slicing, and large retrospective multicenter case series, 2018. [DOI: 10.1055/a-0582-9274](https://doi.org/10.1055/a-0582-9274)
30. J. Wawer. How to stop salami science: Promotion of healthy trends in publishing behavior, 2018. [DOI: 10.1080/08989621.2018.1556099](https://doi.org/10.1080/08989621.2018.1556099)
31. D. Ding; B. Nguyen; K. Gebel; A. Bauman; L. Bero. Duplicate and salami publication: a prevalence study of journal policies, 2019. [DOI: 10.1093/ije/dyz187](https://doi.org/10.1093/ije/dyz187)
32. R. Janghorban; F. Azarkish. Salami Publication in Qualitative Research: An Ethical Challenge, 2019. [PMID: 32292748](https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/32292748/)
33. M.G. Tolsgaard; R. Ellaway; N. Woods; G. Norman. Salami-slicing and plagiarism: How should we respond?, 2019. [DOI: 10.1007/s10459-019-09876-7](https://doi.org/10.1007/s10459-019-09876-7)
34. A.G. Pflieger; M. Katz; M.T. Bowers. Publish, Perish, or Salami Slice? Authorship Ethics in an Emerging Field, 2019. [DOI: 10.1007/s10551-017-3578-3](https://doi.org/10.1007/s10551-017-3578-3)
35. T.A. Collyer. 'Salami slicing' helps careers but harms science, 2019. [DOI: 10.1038/s41562-019-0687-2](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41562-019-0687-2)
36. M.U. Werner. Salami-slicing and duplicate publication: gatekeepers challenges, 2021. [DOI: 10.1515/sjpain-2020-0181](https://doi.org/10.1515/sjpain-2020-0181)
37. M. Koul; P. Majumder; S. Laskar. Salami Publication: An Outlook from the Lens of Ethical Perspective, 2021. [DOI: 10.5005/jp-journals-10062-0099](https://doi.org/10.5005/jp-journals-10062-0099)
38. N.N. Adams. Salami Slicing: clarifying common misconceptions for social science early-career researchers, 2022. [DOI: 10.1007/s43545-022-00389-6](https://doi.org/10.1007/s43545-022-00389-6)
39. W. Mendes-Da-Silva; C.C. Leal. Salami Science in the Age of Open Data: Deja lu and Accountability in Management and Business Research, 2021. [DOI: 10.1590/1982-7849rac2021200194](https://doi.org/10.1590/1982-7849rac2021200194)
40. S. Sullivan-Bolyai; C.D. Ratta; J. Flanagan; S. Pudasainee-Kapri; J.S. Sefcik. Salami slicing and other fatal flaws to avoid in publishing qualitative findings, 2022. [DOI: 10.1016/j.pedn.2022.08.003](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pedn.2022.08.003)
41. G. Szeto; G. Jull. Defining the scope of your manuscript - Beware of "salami slicing", 2022. [DOI: 10.1016/j.msksp.2022.102540](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.msksp.2022.102540)
42. J.S. Xie; M.J. Ali. To Slice or Perish, 2023. [DOI: 10.1080/08820538.2023.2172813](https://doi.org/10.1080/08820538.2023.2172813)
43. K. Subedi; N. Subedi. Misconduct in research: The troubling practice of salami slicing, 2023. [DOI: 10.3126/jgmcn.v16i1.56137](https://doi.org/10.3126/jgmcn.v16i1.56137)
44. B.R. Waterman; J.H. Lubowitz; J.C. Brand; M.J. Rossi. Strategies to Mitigate Against

Least-Publishable Units in Medical and Scientific Research Publications, 2023. DOI: [10.1016/j.arthro.2023.08.003](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.arthro.2023.08.003)

45. Salami Slicing.
46. ‘Salami slicing’ and improper authorship plague Italian research.
47. Salami Slicing.
48. Think Twice Before ‘Salami Slicing’ Your Research.
49. Salami slicing tactics.
50. Least publishable unit.
51. Understanding Redundant Publication and Salami Slicing in Research.
52. Think Twice Before ‘Salami Slicing’ Your Research.
53. Recent encounters with atom-thin salami slicing.
54. Salami slicing- bad for you, bad for society.
55. Little White Lies in Healthcare Publishing.
56. The wheels of Science: The Salami Slicing Theory.
57. Salami Slicing: What Is it and Is it Ethical?.
58. ‘Salami Slicing’ Found in Analyses of Antipsychotic Trials.
59. Professionalism/Salami Slicing and the Least Publishable Unit.
60. The Minimal Publishable Unit.
61. Salami Slicing Science.
62. The pitfalls of "salami slicing": Focus on quality and not quantity of publications.

9 Collaboration and Collusion

Also see § 15.

1. R.T. Pennock. Inappropriate Authorship in Collaborative Science Research, 1996. Source: <https://www.jstor.org/stable/40435966>
2. R. Barrett; A.L. Cox. ‘At least they’re learning something’: the hazy line between collaboration and collusion, 2010. DOI: [10.1080/0260293042000264226](https://doi.org/10.1080/0260293042000264226)
3. S. McGowan. Breaches of Academic Integrity Using Collusion, 2016. DOI: [10.1007/978-981-287-098-8_36](https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-287-098-8_36)
4. T.E. Gladwin. Educating students and future researchers about academic misconduct and questionable collaboration practices, 2018. DOI: [10.1007/s40979-018-0034-9](https://doi.org/10.1007/s40979-018-0034-9)
5. R.S. Hessels; A. Kingstone. Fake collaborations: Interdisciplinary science can undermine

- research integrity, 2019. DOI: [10.31234/osf.io/rqwea](https://doi.org/10.31234/osf.io/rqwea)
6. El. Smith; B. Williams-Jones; Z. Master; et al. Misconduct and Misbehavior Related to Authorship Disagreements in Collaborative Science, 2020. DOI: [10.1007/s11948-019-00112-4](https://doi.org/10.1007/s11948-019-00112-4)
 7. C.H. Chaves; C.R.H.R. Herrera. Collusion or collaborative work? University students' perception of academic integrity, 2022. DOI: [10.22458/ie.v24iEspecial.4330](https://doi.org/10.22458/ie.v24iEspecial.4330)
 8. Z. Barta. Publication games: In the web of reciprocity, 2022. DOI: [10.1371/journal.pone.0270618](https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0270618)
 9. S. Ngwenya; N. Boshoff. Self-interestedness in Research Collaboration and its Association with Career Stage and Nature of Collaboration: A Survey of Zimbabwean Researchers, 2023. DOI: [10.1177/15562646231192808](https://doi.org/10.1177/15562646231192808)
 10. A. Amigud; S. Hosseini. Collaboration, collusion, and barter-cheating: an analysis of academic help-seeking behaviors, 2023. DOI: [10.1080/02602938.2023.2259631](https://doi.org/10.1080/02602938.2023.2259631)
 11. A. Abalkina. Publication and collaboration anomalies in academic papers originating from a paper mill: Evidence from a Russia-based paper mill, 2023. DOI: [10.1002/leap.1574](https://doi.org/10.1002/leap.1574)
 12. G. Young; A. Serbati; K.N. Sim. Collaboration and co-authorship in academic development: what should we be considering?, 2024. DOI: [10.1080/1360144X.2024.2397418](https://doi.org/10.1080/1360144X.2024.2397418)
 13. H. Zwart; Y. Tenhagen; M. Hosseini; J. Dore. Consortium Authorship: Ethical Tensions in Emerging Authorship Practices in Interdisciplinary Collaborative Research, 2024. DOI: [10.1007/s10805-024-09592-x](https://doi.org/10.1007/s10805-024-09592-x)
 14. C.-H. Kuan; D.-Z. Chen; M.-H. Huang. Dubious cross-national affiliations obscure the assessment of international research collaboration, 2024. DOI: [10.1016/j.joi.2024.101496](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.joi.2024.101496)
 15. M.S. Boampong; J. Boakye-Danquah; Y.A. Boafo; et al. Experiences of inequality in international collaborative research - Perspectives from environmental and sustainability scholars from Ghana, West Africa. DOI: [10.1016/j.envsci.2023.103661](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2023.103661)
 16. T. Thomas. Parachute science and collaboration in protected areas, 2025. DOI: [10.1038/s44358-024-00010-z](https://doi.org/10.1038/s44358-024-00010-z)
 17. [Student collaboration or academic collusion? How to tell the difference.](#)
 18. [Understanding and Avoiding Collusion.](#)
 19. [Collaboration with Professor who does unethical research.](#)
 20. [Questionable Research Practices in Collaboration.](#)
 21. [Crossing the line: Collusion or collaboration in university group work?.](#)
 22. [The push for interdisciplinary teams can lead to fake collaborations.](#)

23. [Student collaboration or academic collusion? How to tell the difference.](#)
24. [Plagiarism, collusion and other examples of misconduct.](#)
25. [Sharing isn't always caring: collusion and how to avoid it.](#)
26. [What are fake interdisciplinary collaborations and why do they occur?.](#)
27. [Scientific Collaborations and Authorship Disputes.](#)
28. [Pandemic sees rise in suspected exam cheating and collusion cases.](#)
29. [Authorship abuse is the dark side of collaboration.](#)

10 Questionable Affiliation Practices

1. H. Xin. Frustrations Mount Over China's High-Priced Hunt for Trophy Professors, 2006. DOI: [10.1126/science.313.5794.1721](https://doi.org/10.1126/science.313.5794.1721)
2. Y. Bhattacharjee. Saudi Universities Offer Cash in Exchange for Academic Prestige, 2011. DOI: [10.1126/science.334.6061.1344](https://doi.org/10.1126/science.334.6061.1344)
3. M. Dadkhah; A.M. Alharbi; M.H. Al-khresheh; et al. Affiliation Oriented Journals: Don't Worry About Peer Review If You Have Good Affiliation, 2015. DOI: [10.11591/ijece.v5i4.pp621-625](https://doi.org/10.11591/ijece.v5i4.pp621-625)
4. M.R. Safaei; M. Goodarzi; O. Mahian; M. Dahari; S. Wongwises. A survey of using multiple affiliations by scholars in scientific articles, 2016. DOI: [10.1007/s11192-016-1875-8](https://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-016-1875-8)
5. H. Hottenrott; C. Lawson. A first look at multiple institutional affiliations: a study of authors in Germany, Japan and the UK, 2017. DOI: [10.1007/s11192-017-2257-6](https://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-017-2257-6)
6. V.C. Bachelet; F.A. Uribe; R.A. Diaz; et al. Author misrepresentation of institutional affiliations: protocol for an exploratory case study, 2019. DOI: [10.1136/bmjopen-2018-023983](https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjopen-2018-023983)
7. V.C. Bachelet; F.A. Uribe; R.A. Diaz; et al. Misrepresentation of institutional affiliations: The results from an exploratory case study of Chilean authors, 2019. DOI: [10.1002/leap.1257](https://doi.org/10.1002/leap.1257)
8. K. Moustafa. Octopus affiliations, 2020. DOI: [10.1007/s11192-020-03600-8](https://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-020-03600-8)
9. H. Hottenrott; M.E. Rose; C. Lawson. The rise of multiple institutional affiliations in academia, 2021. DOI: [10.1002/asi.24472](https://doi.org/10.1002/asi.24472)
10. H. Hottenrott; C. Lawson. What is behind multiple institutional affiliations in academia?, 2022. DOI: [10.1093/scipol/scab086](https://doi.org/10.1093/scipol/scab086)
11. S. Alhuthali; A.A. Sayed. Saudi Universities Rapid Escalation in Academic Ranking

- Systems: Implications and Challenges, 2022. DOI: [10.35995/jci02010008](https://doi.org/10.35995/jci02010008)
12. J.A.T. da Silva. When academic papers' stated emails do not match authors' affiliations: A new budding crisis in paper mill-ridden academic publishing?, 2022. DOI: [10.12681/eml.31441](https://doi.org/10.12681/eml.31441)
 13. T. Lemmens; S. Srinivasan. Authorship controversies in academic publication: implications for science and the research environment, 2022. DOI: [10.20529/IJME.2022.051](https://doi.org/10.20529/IJME.2022.051)
 14. G. Halevi; G. Rogers; V.P. Guerrero-Bote; F. De-Moya-Anegón. Multi-affiliation: a growing problem of scientific integrity, 2023. DOI: [10.3145/epi.2023.jul.01](https://doi.org/10.3145/epi.2023.jul.01)
 15. M. Catanzaro. Saudi universities lose highly cited researchers after payment schemes raise ethics concerns, 2023. DOI: [10.1126/science.zhs1429](https://doi.org/10.1126/science.zhs1429)
 16. C.-H. Kuan; D.-Z. Chen; M.-H. Huang. Dubious cross-national affiliations obscure the assessment of international research collaboration, 2024. DOI: [10.1016/j.joi.2024.101496](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.joi.2024.101496)
 17. L.I. Meho; E.A. Akl. Using bibliometrics to detect questionable authorship and affiliation practices and their impact on global research metrics: A case study of 14 universities, 2025. DOI: [10.1162/qss_a_00339](https://doi.org/10.1162/qss_a_00339)
 18. C.-s. Lin; M.-h. Huang; D.-z. Chen. The inter-institutional and intra-institutional multi-affiliation authorships in the scientific papers produced by the well-ranked universities, 2025. DOI: [10.1016/j.joi.2024.101635](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.joi.2024.101635)
 19. What's in a name? How false author affiliations are damaging academic research.
 20. False affiliations and fake authors.
 21. Potentially fake academic affiliation.
 22. Institutions paying authors to be named on papers.
 23. Navigating the Challenges of Questionable Research Practices in Academic Publishing.
 24. A turning point for Saudi Arabian affiliations in the 2023 Highly Cited Researchers list from Clarivate.
 25. A turning point for Saudi Arabian affiliations in the 2023 Highly Cited Researchers™ list from Clarivate.
 26. Full International Edition (2014-22): The affiliation game of Saudi Arabian higher education & research institutions.
 27. Short 2022 Spanish Edition: The affiliation game between Spanish and Saudi Arabian higher education & research institutions.
 28. False affiliations boost Saudi university rankings.
 29. Saudi Universities Engage in Academic Fraud to Rank Among the World's Best - What's the Story?.

30. [Saudi scientist tells colleagues, ‘Stop this academic fraud’](#).
31. [Saudi universities suffer from purge of list of highly cited researchers](#).
32. [The affiliation game of Saudi Arabian higher education & research institutions](#).
33. [The global rise in academic authors reporting multiple institutional affiliations reflects the unanticipated influence of research assessment on academia](#).

11 Manipulation of Knowledge

1. C.B. Begg; J.A. Berlin. Publication Bias: A Problem in Interpreting Medical Data, 1988. DOI: [10.2307/2982993](#)
2. P.J. Easterbrook; J.A. Berlin; R. Gopalan; D.R. Matthews. Publication bias in clinical research, 1991. DOI: [10.1016/0140-6736\(91\)90201-y](#)
3. J.M. Stern; R.J. Simes. Publication bias: evidence of delayed publication in a cohort study of clinical research projects, 1997. DOI: [10.1136/bmj.315.7109.640](#)
4. BMJ. Why journals should not publish articles funded by the tobacco industry, 2000. DOI: [10.1136/bmj.321.7268.1074](#)
5. Nature. Tobacco industry vs science, 2000. DOI: [10.1038/35020709](#)
6. H. Melander; J. Ahlqvist-Rastad; G. Meijer; B. Beermann. Evidence b(i)ased medicine – selective reporting from studies sponsored by pharmaceutical industry: review of studies in new drug applications, 2003. DOI: [10.1136/bmj.326.7400.1171](#)
7. R. Smith. Medical journals and pharmaceutical companies: uneasy bedfellows, 2003. DOI: [10.1136/bmj.326.7400.1202](#)
8. A.-W. Chan; A. Hrobjartsson; M.T. Haahr; et al. Empirical Evidence for Selective Reporting of Outcomes in Randomized Trials: Comparison of Protocols to Published Articles, 2004. DOI: [10.1001/jama.291.20.2457](#)
9. R. Smith. Medical Journals Are an Extension of the Marketing Arm of Pharmaceutical Companies, 2005. DOI: [10.1371/journal.pmed.0020138](#)
10. L.A. Bero. Tobacco Industry Manipulation of Research, 2005. DOI: [10.1177/003335490512000215](#)
11. M. Angell. *The Truth About the Drug Companies: How They Deceive Us and What to Do About It*. 2005. ISBN: [9780375760945](#)
12. T. Gruning; A.B. Gilmore; M. McKee. Tobacco industry influence on science and scientists in Germany, 2005. DOI: [10.2105/AJPH.2004.061507](#)
13. E. Decullier; V. Lheritier; F. Chapuis. Fate of biomedical research protocols and publica-

- tion bias in France: retrospective cohort study, 2005. DOI: [10.1136/bmj.38488.385995.8F](https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.38488.385995.8F)
14. B. Moffatt; C. Elliott. Ghost marketing: pharmaceutical companies and ghostwritten journal articles, 2007. DOI: [10.1353/pbm.2007.0009](https://doi.org/10.1353/pbm.2007.0009)
 15. P.C. Gotzsche; A. Hrobjartsson; H.K. Johansen; et al. Ghost Authorship in Industry-Initiated Randomised Trials, 2007. DOI: [10.1371/journal.pmed.0040019](https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pmed.0040019)
 16. S. Sismondo. Ghost Management: How Much of the Medical Literature Is Shaped Behind the Scenes by the Pharmaceutical Industry?, 2007. DOI: [10.1371/journal.pmed.0040286](https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pmed.0040286)
 17. D.B. Resnik. *The Price of Truth: How Money Affects the Norms of Science*. 2007. ISBN: 9780195309782
 18. E. Berger. Ghostwriters, Data Manipulation and Dollar Diplomacy: How Drug Companies Pull the Strings in Clinical Research, 2008. DOI: [10.1016/j.annemergmed.2008.06.009](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.annemergmed.2008.06.009)
 19. S.N. Ghaemi; A.A. Shirzadi; M. Filkowski. Publication Bias and the Pharmaceutical Industry: The Case of Lamotrigine in Bipolar Disorder, 2008. PMID: 19008973
 20. P.J. Jacques; R.E. Dunlap; M. Freeman. The organisation of denial: Conservative think tanks and environmental scepticism, 2008. DOI: [10.1080/09644010802055576](https://doi.org/10.1080/09644010802055576)
 21. V. Barbour; J. Clark; S. Jones; et al. Ghostwriting: The Dirty Little Secret of Medical Publishing That Just Got Bigger, 2009. DOI: [10.1371/journal.pmed.1000156](https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pmed.1000156)
 22. P.C. Gotzsche; J.P. Kassirer; K.L. Woolley; et al. What Should Be Done To Tackle Ghostwriting in the Medical Literature?, 2009. DOI: [10.1371/journal.pmed.1000023](https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pmed.1000023)
 23. E. Dolgin. Publication bias continues despite clinical-trial registration, 2009. DOI: [10.1038/news.2009.902](https://doi.org/10.1038/news.2009.902)
 24. F. Song; S. Parekh-Bhurke; L. Hooper; et al. Extent of publication bias in different categories of research cohorts: a meta-analysis of empirical studies, 2009. DOI: [10.1186/1471-2288-9-79](https://doi.org/10.1186/1471-2288-9-79)
 25. V. Barbour; J. Clark; S. Jones; et al. Ghostwriting Revisited: New Perspectives but Few Solutions in Sight, 2011. DOI: [10.1371/journal.pmed.1001084](https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pmed.1001084)
 26. A. Fugh-Berman; J. Siwek. Compromising the medical literature: the hidden influence of industry-biased articles, 2011. PMID: 21888299
 27. A. Brown. Understanding pharmaceutical research manipulation in the context of accounting manipulation, 2013. DOI: [10.1111/jlme.12070](https://doi.org/10.1111/jlme.12070)
 28. C. Elliott. Relationships between physicians and Pharma, 2014. DOI: [10.1212/CPJ.0000000000000012](https://doi.org/10.1212/CPJ.0000000000000012)
 29. BMJ. Should journals stop publishing research funded by the drug industry?, 2014.

- DOI: [10.1136/bmj.g171](https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.g171)
30. K. Dwan; D.G. Altman; M. Clarke; et al. Evidence for the Selective Reporting of Analyses and Discrepancies in Clinical Trials: A Systematic Review of Cohort Studies of Clinical Trials, 2014. DOI: [10.1371/journal.pmed.1001666](https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pmed.1001666)
 31. M. Peplow. Social sciences suffer from severe publication bias, 2014. DOI: [10.1038/nature.2014.15787](https://doi.org/10.1038/nature.2014.15787)
 32. K.P.S. Raghav; S. Mahajan; J.C. Yao; et al. From Protocols to Publications: A Study in Selective Reporting of Outcomes in Randomized Trials in Oncology, 2015. DOI: [10.1200/JCO.2015.62.4148](https://doi.org/10.1200/JCO.2015.62.4148)
 33. BMJ. Sugar's web of influence 2: Biasing the science, 2015. DOI: [10.1136/bmj.h215](https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.h215)
 34. S.B. Nissen; T. Magidson; K. Gross; C.T. Bergstrom. Research: Publication bias and the canonization of false facts, 2016. DOI: [10.7554/eLife.21451](https://doi.org/10.7554/eLife.21451)
 35. D. Mandrioli; C.E. Kearns; L.A. Bero. Relationship between Research Outcomes and Risk of Bias, Study Sponsorship, and Author Financial Conflicts of Interest in Reviews of the Effects of Artificially Sweetened Beverages on Weight Outcomes: A Systematic Review of Reviews, 2016. DOI: [10.1371/journal.pone.0162198](https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0162198)
 36. A.W. Brown; T.S. Mehta; D.B. Allison. Publication Bias in Science: What Is It, Why Is It Problematic, and How Can It Be Addressed?, 2017. DOI: [10.1093/oxfordhb/9780190497620.013.10](https://doi.org/10.1093/oxfordhb/9780190497620.013.10)
 37. M. Rubin. When Does HARKing Hurt? Identifying When Different Types of Undisclosed Post Hoc Hypothesizing Harm Scientific Progress, 2017. DOI: [10.1037/gpr0000128](https://doi.org/10.1037/gpr0000128)
 38. R. Salandra. Knowledge dissemination in clinical trials: Exploring influences of institutional support and type of innovation on selective reporting, 2018. DOI: [10.1016/j.respol.2018.04.005](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.respol.2018.04.005)
 39. A. Fabbri; A. Lai; Q. Grundy; L.A. Bero. The Influence of Industry Sponsorship on the Research Agenda: A Scoping Review, 2018. DOI: [10.2105/AJPH.2018.304677](https://doi.org/10.2105/AJPH.2018.304677)
 40. C. Pisinger; N. Godtfredsen; A.M. Bender. A conflict of interest is strongly associated with tobacco industry-favourable results, indicating no harm of e-cigarettes, 2019. DOI: [10.1016/j.ypmed.2018.12.011](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ypmed.2018.12.011)
 41. Y.H. Hendlin; M. Vora; J. Elias; P.M. Ling. Financial Conflicts of Interest and Stance on Tobacco Harm Reduction: A Systematic Review, 2019. DOI: [10.2105/AJPH.2019.305106](https://doi.org/10.2105/AJPH.2019.305106)
 42. M. Krsticevic; D. Saric; F. Saric; et al. Selective reporting bias due to discrepancies between registered and published outcomes in osteoarthritis trials, 2019. DOI: [10.1136/bmj.g171](https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.g171)

[10.2217/cer-2019-0068](https://doi.org/10.2217/cer-2019-0068)

43. E.K.C. Wong; C.C. Lachance; M.J. Page; et al. Selective reporting bias in randomised controlled trials from two network meta-analyses: comparison of clinical trial registrations and their respective publications, 2019. DOI: [10.1136/bmjopen-2019-031138](https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjopen-2019-031138)
44. R. Salandra; J.-M. Ross. Does Rivalry Influence Selective Reporting in Scientific Publications?, 2019. DOI: [10.5465/AMBPP.2019.17529abstract](https://doi.org/10.5465/AMBPP.2019.17529abstract)
45. A.S. Nair. Publication bias - Importance of studies with negative results!, 2019. DOI: [10.4103/ija.IJA_142_19](https://doi.org/10.4103/ija.IJA_142_19)
46. D. Michaels. *The Triumph of Doubt: Dark Money and the Science of Deception*. 2020. ISBN: [9780190922665](https://www.isbn-international.org/product/9780190922665)
47. C.D. Chambers. Frontloading selectivity: A third way in scientific publishing?, 2020. DOI: [10.1371/journal.pbio.3000693](https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pbio.3000693)
48. A. Marks-Anglin; Y. Chen. A historical review of publication bias, 2020. DOI: [10.1002/jrsm.1452](https://doi.org/10.1002/jrsm.1452)
49. S. Sismondo. Epistemic Corruption, the Pharmaceutical Industry, and the Body of Medical Science, 2021. DOI: [10.3389/frma.2021.614013](https://doi.org/10.3389/frma.2021.614013)
50. E.H. Morreim. Corporations, high-stakes biomedical research, and research misconduct: yes they can (and sometimes do), 2021. DOI: [10.1093/jlb/ljab014](https://doi.org/10.1093/jlb/ljab014)
51. T. Legg; J. Hatchard; A.B. Gilmore. The Science for Profit Model - How and why corporations influence science and the use of science in policy and practice, 2021. DOI: [10.1371/journal.pone.0253272](https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0253272)
52. T. Legg; M. Legendre; A.B. Gilmore. Paying lip service to publication ethics: scientific publishing practices and the Foundation for a Smoke-Free World, 2021. DOI: [10.1136/tobaccocontrol-2020-056003](https://doi.org/10.1136/tobaccocontrol-2020-056003)
53. G. Reed; Y. Hendlin; A. Desikan; et al. The disinformation playbook: how industry manipulates the science-policy process-and how to restore scientific integrity, 2021. DOI: [10.1057/s41271-021-00318-6](https://doi.org/10.1057/s41271-021-00318-6)
54. I. van Beurden; M.J. van de Beek; J.A.A. van Heteren; et al. Selective Reporting of Outcomes in Tinnitus Trials: Comparison of Trial Registries With Corresponding Publications, 2021. DOI: [10.3389/fneur.2021.669501](https://doi.org/10.3389/fneur.2021.669501)
55. J. Rouan; G. Velazquez; J. Freischlag; M.R. Kibbe. Publication bias is the consequence of a lack of diversity, equity, and inclusion, 2021. DOI: [10.1016/j.jvs.2021.03.049](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jvs.2021.03.049)
56. L. Glenna; A. Bruce. Suborning science for profit: Monsanto, glyphosate, and private science research misconduct. DOI: [10.1016/j.respol.2021.104290](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.respol.2021.104290)
57. D.G. Arnold; L.H. Amato; J.L. Troyer; O.J. Stewart. Innovation and misconduct in the

- pharmaceutical industry, 2022. DOI: [10.1016/j.jbusres.2022.02.026](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2022.02.026)
58. A. Morabia. Scientific Publishing and the Tobacco Industry, 2022. DOI: [10.2105/AJPH.2022.306916](https://doi.org/10.2105/AJPH.2022.306916)
59. J. Briggs; D. Vallone. The Tobacco Industry's Renewed Assault on Science: A Call for a United Public Health Response, 2022. DOI: [10.2105/AJPH.2021.306683](https://doi.org/10.2105/AJPH.2021.306683)
60. D.S. Chawla. Tobacco publishing ban for researchers at industry-owned firms, 2022. DOI: [10.1038/d41586-022-00197-1](https://doi.org/10.1038/d41586-022-00197-1)
61. K. Abbasi. How Big Oil is manipulating climate science, 2022. DOI: [10.1136/bmj.o2226](https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.o2226)
62. P. Gottesfeld. Lead Industry Influence in the 21st Century: An Old Playbook for a "Modern Metal", 2022. DOI: [10.2105/AJPH.2022.306960](https://doi.org/10.2105/AJPH.2022.306960)
63. H. Suzuki; N. Aono; Y. Zhang; et al. Comparison of Publications on Heated Tobacco Products With Conventional Cigarettes and Implied Desirability of the Products According to Tobacco Industry Affiliation: A Systematic Review, 2023. DOI: [10.1093/ntr/ntad205](https://doi.org/10.1093/ntr/ntad205)
64. J. Gannon; K. Bach; M.S. Cattaruzza; et al. Big tobacco's dirty tricks: Seven key tactics of the tobacco industry, 2023. DOI: [10.18332/tpc/176336](https://doi.org/10.18332/tpc/176336)
65. L. Ruggia. E-cigarettes 95% less dangerous? Myth, scientific lies, and manipulations, 2023. DOI: [10.53127/tblg-2023-A016](https://doi.org/10.53127/tblg-2023-A016)
66. O.R. van den Akker; M.A.L.M. van Assen; M. Enting; et al. Selective Hypothesis Reporting in Psychology: Comparing Preregistrations and Corresponding Publications, 2023. DOI: [10.1177/25152459231187988](https://doi.org/10.1177/25152459231187988)
67. K. Komukai; S. Sugita; S. Fujimoto. Publication Bias and Selective Outcome Reporting in Randomized Controlled Trials Related to Rehabilitation: A Literature Review, 2023. DOI: [10.1016/j.apmr.2023.06.006](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apmr.2023.06.006)
68. F.M. Mnisi. Conflict of Interest and Think Tanks - What are the Possible Challenges and Impact, 2023. DOI: [10.5772/intechopen.1001459](https://doi.org/10.5772/intechopen.1001459)
69. S. Lewandowsky; U.K.H. Ecker; J. Cook; et al. Misinformation and the epistemic integrity of democracy, 2023. DOI: [10.1016/j.copsy.2023.101711](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.copsy.2023.101711)
70. S.W. Rose; A.S.L. Tan; P. Bandi; et al. Commercial Tobacco and Nicotine Industry-Funded Research Has No Place in SRNT and Nicotine & Tobacco Research, 2024. DOI: [10.1093/ntr/ntae109](https://doi.org/10.1093/ntr/ntae109)
71. S. Braznell; L. Laurence; I. Fitzpatrick; A.B. Gilmore. "Keep it a secret": Leaked Documents Suggest Philip Morris International, and Its Japanese Affiliate, Continue to Exploit Science for Profit, 2024. DOI: [10.1093/ntr/ntae101](https://doi.org/10.1093/ntr/ntae101)
72. S. Braznell; A.V.D. Akker; C. Metcalfe; G.M.J. Taylor; J. Hartmann-Boyce. Critical

- appraisal of interventional clinical trials assessing heated tobacco products: a systematic review, 2024. DOI: [10.1136/tc-2022-057522](https://doi.org/10.1136/tc-2022-057522)
73. M. Braun; D. Klingelhofer; D. Bruggmann; D.A. Groneberg. Activity of the Tobacco Industry in Research and Scientific Literature, 2024. DOI: [10.1177/1179173X241271566](https://doi.org/10.1177/1179173X241271566)
 74. T. Legga; A.B. Gilmore. Tobacco industry conflicts of interest cannot go undeclared in scientific publishing, 2024. DOI: [10.1016/S0140-6736\(24\)01032-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(24)01032-8)
 75. BMJ. Tobacco funded research: how even journals with bans find it hard to stem the tide of publications, 2024. DOI: [10.1136/bmj.q1153](https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.q1153)
 76. S. Hiltner; E. Eaton; N. Healy; et al. Fossil fuel industry influence in higher education: A review and a research agenda, 2024. DOI: [10.1002/wcc.904](https://doi.org/10.1002/wcc.904)
 77. K. Matvienko-Sikar; J. O'Shea; S. Kennedy; et al. Selective outcome reporting in trials of behavioural health interventions in health psychology and behavioural medicine journals: a review, 2024. DOI: [10.1080/17437199.2024.2367613](https://doi.org/10.1080/17437199.2024.2367613)
 78. S. Braznell. Recent Developments Relevant to Debates Around the Dissemination of Industry-Funded Science, 2025. DOI: [10.1093/ntr/ntae183](https://doi.org/10.1093/ntr/ntae183)
 79. ; et al. E.K. Soule; M.E. Rossheim; M.D. Livingston. Hidden flaws in e-cigarette industry-funded studies, 2025. DOI: [10.1136/tc-2024-058609](https://doi.org/10.1136/tc-2024-058609)
 80. BMJ. Fossil fuel industry funding undermines the integrity of scientific findings, 2025. DOI: [10.1136/bmj.r107](https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.r107)
 81. [The ethics of collaborations between academia and commercial parties.](#)
 82. [When it comes to conflicts of interest, affiliations are apparently no smoking gun.](#)
 83. [Insight into how pharma manipulates research evidence: a case study.](#)
 84. [The Cost of Manipulation: The Irresponsible Abuse of Technological Opacity in the Pharmaceutical Industry.](#)
 85. [When big companies fund academic research, the truth often comes last.](#)
 86. [The Hidden Manipulation: The Influence of Pharmaceutical Companies on Physicians and Researchers .](#)
 87. [Data Manipulation Prevalent in Drug Industry? .](#)
 88. [How drug companies' PR tactics skew the presentation of medical research.](#)
 89. [Medical publishing and the drug industry: IS MEDICAL SCIENCE FOR SALE?.](#)
 90. [Experts Conclude Pfizer Manipulated Studies.](#)
 91. [Should Drug Industry Research All Get Rejected For Publication?.](#)
 92. [Pharma's influence over published clinical evidence.](#)
 93. [How Drug Company Money Is Undermining Science.](#)

94. Tobacco funded research still appearing in top medical journals.
95. Tobacco giant accused of ‘manipulating science’ to attract non-smokers.
96. Threatening public health: new documents shed light on PMI’s secret science.
97. The smokescreen of the tobacco industry’s use of science.
98. Big tobacco, big conflict of interest.
99. Industry Approaches to Science on Newer Products.
100. Publishing ban for researchers at tobacco industry-owned firms - Nature.
101. PMI Accused of ‘Manipulating Science’.
102. Book Review: Probing the Corporate Manipulation of Science.
103. UC Study Uncovers Tobacco Industry Efforts to Undermine Secondhand Smoke Link to Cardiovascular Dise.
104. How the oil industry made us doubt climate change.
105. How the oil industry made us doubt climate change.
106. Tracing Big Oil’s PR war to delay action on climate change.
107. Lethal Greed: How Corporate Manipulation of Science and Regulation Makes People Sick.
108. Scientists Shouldn’t Listen to the Fossil Fuel Industry. Geoengineering is a Scam.
109. The Manipulation of Science.
110. Tobacco and Oil Industries Used Same Researchers to Sway Public.
111. How vested interests tried to turn the world against climate science.
112. Climate sceptics and the manipulation of scientific data.
113. Climatic Research Unit email controversy.
114. Climate sceptics claim leaked emails are evidence of collusion among scientists.
115. Climategate scientists cleared of manipulating data on global warming.
116. Climategate 10 years on: what lessons have we learned?.
117. Fossil Fuel Funding Is ‘Embedded’ Across Academia. What Does That Mean for Climate Research?.
118. Manipulation of Global Warming Science.
119. Former NOAA Scientist Confirms Colleagues Manipulated Climate Records.
120. I Left Out the Full Truth to Get My Climate Change Paper Published.
121. A scientist manipulated climate data. Conservative media celebrated.
122. Scientists Accused of Manipulating Information to Promote Their Position.
123. Climate Scientists Manipulated Temperature Data to Fool Politicians and Public, Claims ‘Whistleblower’.
124. Publication and reporting bias: a long history towards open science.

125. [Publication bias and selective reporting.](#)
126. [Selective Reporting of Literature.](#)
127. [Publication Bias.](#)
128. [The art of deception: How pseudo think tanks and researchers influence policy.](#)
129. [Before you read another health study, check who's funding the research.](#)
130. [50 Years Ago, Sugar Industry Quietly Paid Scientists To Point Blame At Fat.](#)
131. [How Fossil Fuel Funding Impacts Learning At Colleges & Universities.](#)
132. [How the Sugar Industry Shifted Blame to Fat.](#)
133. [Sugar industry secretly paid for favorable Harvard research.](#)
134. [‘Bias at all levels’: Scathing review published into sweetener-funded research.](#)
135. [The business of bias: balancing the role of private money in scientific research.](#)
136. [Industry Sponsorship bias.](#)
137. [Science in the Service of Untruth: A Century of Lead Poisoning.](#)

12 Authorship and Credit Disputes

1. A. Abbott. Dispute over first authorship lands researchers in dock, 2002. DOI: [10.1038/419004b](#)
2. M.M. Afifi. Authorship. Credit and disputes, 2004. PMID: [15573219](#)
3. H.S. Ahmed; A. Hadi; N. Choudhury. Authorship conflict in Bangladesh: an exploratory study, 2010. DOI: [10.1087/20100406](#)
4. J.I. Seeman; M.C. House. Authorship Issues and Conflict in the U.S. Academic Chemical Community, 2015. DOI: [10.1080/08989621.2015.1047707](#)
5. Z. Faulkes. Resolving authorship disputes by mediation and arbitration, 2018. DOI: [10.1186/s41073-018-0057-z](#)
6. S. Beshyah; D. Abdelmanna; A.-N. Elzouki; E. Elkhammas. Authorship disputes: Do they result from inadvertent errors of judgment or intentional unethical misconduct?, 2018. DOI: [10.4103/ijmbs.ijmbs_58_18](#)
7. N.R. Smilowitz; J.J. Ferguson; G. Weisz. Controversies surrounding authorship of manuscripts by industry employees: academic and industry perspectives, 2018. DOI: [10.4244/EIJ-D-16-00918](#)
8. El. Smith; B. Williams-Jones; Z. Master; et al. Misconduct and Misbehavior Related to Authorship Disagreements in Collaborative Science, 2020. DOI: [10.1007/s11948-019-00112-4](#)

9. C. Ni; E. Smith; H. Yuan; et al. The gendered nature of authorship, 2021. DOI: [10.1126/sciadv.abe4639](https://doi.org/10.1126/sciadv.abe4639)
10. D.S. Chawla. Women in science face authorship disputes more often than men, 2021. DOI: [10.1063/PT.6.2.20210901a](https://doi.org/10.1063/PT.6.2.20210901a)
11. T. Lemmens; S. Srinivasan. Authorship controversies in academic publication: implications for science and the research environment, 2022. DOI: [10.20529/IJME.2022.051](https://doi.org/10.20529/IJME.2022.051)
12. P. Nelson; M.G. Petrova. Research assistants: Scientific credit and recognized authorship, 2022. DOI: [10.1002/leap.1467](https://doi.org/10.1002/leap.1467)
13. A.A. Khalifa. Losing young researchers in the authorship battle, under-reported casualties, 2022. DOI: [10.1016/j.jemep.2021.100735](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jemep.2021.100735)
14. T. Shamim. Authorship disputes and amicable solutions in scholarly publication: the road ahead, 2023. DOI: [10.22034/ncm.2023.410729.1109](https://doi.org/10.22034/ncm.2023.410729.1109)
15. E. Savchenko; A. Rosenfeld. Authorship conflicts in academia: an international cross-discipline survey, 2024. DOI: [10.1007/s11192-024-04972-x](https://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-024-04972-x)
16. M. Kumar. Handle with care: authorship challenges and conflicts in research publication, 2024. DOI: [10.18203/2394-6040.ijcmph20243677](https://doi.org/10.18203/2394-6040.ijcmph20243677)
17. B.L. Tang. Authorship credit disputes should all be considered potential cases of plagiarism unless proven otherwise, 2025. DOI: [10.3897/ese.2025.e151110](https://doi.org/10.3897/ese.2025.e151110)
18. [Authorship: contributions, disputes, and misconduct.](#)
19. [Authorship Dispute.](#)
20. [Plagiarism and Authorship Disputes.](#)
21. [Authorship dispute among the League of Extraordinary Gentlemen.](#)
22. [The Problem: Authorship Disputes in Academic Publishing.](#)
23. [Authorship Disputes: Retractions & Case Studies.](#)
24. [Authorship wars: academics outline the rules for recognition.](#)
25. [Exploring the Role of Gender in Scholarly Authorship Disputes.](#)
26. [What can be done to resolve academic authorship disputes?.](#)
27. [First authorship dispute between the research leader and the person who did the most important analysis. What is the solution?.](#)
28. [Authorship in Academia: Guidelines, Challenges, and Best Practices.](#)
29. [Academic Authorship Controversy: Navigating the Ethical Landscape.](#)
30. [Authorship Disputes.](#)
31. [Scientific Collaborations and Authorship Disputes.](#)
32. [The problem of academic credit and the value of diversity in the research community.](#)

33. [Authorship Dispute Erupts Over Published Journal Article.](#)

13 Questionable Research Practices

1. L.K. John; G. Loewenstein; D. Prelec. Measuring the Prevalence of Questionable Research Practices With Incentives for Truth Telling, 2012. DOI: [10.1177/0956797611430953](https://doi.org/10.1177/0956797611430953)
2. K. Fiedler; N. Schwarz. Questionable Research Practices Revisited, 2015. DOI: [10.1177/1948550615612150](https://doi.org/10.1177/1948550615612150)
3. G.C. Banks; S.G. Rogelberg; H.M. Woznyj; R.S. Landis; D.E. Rupp. Editorial: Evidence on Questionable Research Practices: The Good, the Bad, and the Ugly, 2016. DOI: [10.1007/s10869-016-9456-7](https://doi.org/10.1007/s10869-016-9456-7)
4. D.J. Bierman; J.P. Spottiswoode; A. Bijl. Testing for Questionable Research Practices in a Meta-Analysis: An Example from Experimental Parapsychology, 2016. DOI: [10.1371/journal.pone.0153049](https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0153049)
5. L.M. Bouter; J. Tjeldink; N. Axelsen; et al. Ranking major and minor research misbehaviors: results from a survey among participants of four World Conferences on Research Integrity, 2016. DOI: [10.1186/s41073-016-0024-5](https://doi.org/10.1186/s41073-016-0024-5)
6. N. Butler; H. Delaney; S. Spoelstra. The Gray Zone: Questionable Research Practices in the Business School, 2017. DOI: [10.5465/amle.2015.0201](https://doi.org/10.5465/amle.2015.0201)
7. H. Fraser; T. Parker; S. Nakagawa; A. Barnett; F. Fidler. Questionable research practices in ecology and evolution, 2018. DOI: [10.1371/journal.pone.0200303](https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0200303)
8. S. Janke; M. Daumiller; S.C. Rudert. Dark Pathways to Achievement in Science: Researchers' Achievement Goals Predict Engagement in Questionable Research Practices, 2018. DOI: [10.1177/1948550618790227](https://doi.org/10.1177/1948550618790227)
9. A.R. Artino; E.W. Driessen; L.A. Maggio. Ethical Shades of Gray: International Frequency of Scientific Misconduct and Questionable Research Practices in Health Professions Education, 2019. DOI: [10.1097/ACM.0000000000002412](https://doi.org/10.1097/ACM.0000000000002412)
10. R. Ulrich; J. Miller. Meta-Research: Questionable research practices may have little effect on replicability, 2020. DOI: [10.7554/eLife.58237](https://doi.org/10.7554/eLife.58237)
11. R.G. Gerrits; J. Mulyanto; J.D. Wammes; et al. Individual, institutional, and scientific environment factors associated with questionable research practices in the reporting of messages and conclusions in scientific health services research publications, 2020. DOI: [10.1186/s12913-020-05624-5](https://doi.org/10.1186/s12913-020-05624-5)

12. C. Linder; S. Farahbakhsh. Unfolding the Black Box of Questionable Research Practices: Where Is the Line Between Acceptable and Unacceptable Practices?, 2020. DOI: [10.1017/beq.2019.52](https://doi.org/10.1017/beq.2019.52)
13. R. van de Schoot; S.D. Winter; E. Griffioen; et al. The Use of Questionable Research Practices to Survive in Academia Examined With Expert Elicitation, Prior-Data Conflicts, Bayes Factors for Replication Effects, and the Bayes Truth Serum, 2021. DOI: [10.3389/fpsyg.2021.621547](https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2021.621547)
14. B.N. Bakker; K. Jaidka; T. Dorr; N. Fasching; Y. Lelkes. Questionable and Open Research Practices: Attitudes and Perceptions among Quantitative Communication Researchers, 2021. DOI: [10.1093/joc/jqab031](https://doi.org/10.1093/joc/jqab031)
15. M.C. Makel; J. Hodges; B.G. Cook; J.A. Plucker. Both Questionable and Open Research Practices Are Prevalent in Education Research, 2021. DOI: [10.3102/0013189X211001356](https://doi.org/10.3102/0013189X211001356)
16. J.D. Troy; F. Rockhold; G.P. Samsa. Institutional approaches to preventing questionable research practices, 2021. DOI: [10.1080/08989621.2021.1986017](https://doi.org/10.1080/08989621.2021.1986017)
17. C. Andrade. HARKing, Cherry-Picking, P-Hacking, Fishing Expeditions, and Data Dredging and Mining as Questionable Research Practices, 2021. DOI: [10.4088/JCP.20f13804](https://doi.org/10.4088/JCP.20f13804)
18. S.D. Sivasubramanian; M. Cosentino; L. Ribeiro; F. Marino. Unethical practices within medical research and publication - An exploratory study, 2021. DOI: [10.1007/s40979-021-00072-y](https://doi.org/10.1007/s40979-021-00072-y)
19. J. de Vrieze. Landmark research integrity survey finds questionable practices are surprisingly common, 2021. DOI: [10.1126/science.abk3508](https://doi.org/10.1126/science.abk3508)
20. J. de Vrieze. Large survey finds questionable research practices are common, 2021. DOI: [10.1126/science.373.6552.265](https://doi.org/10.1126/science.373.6552.265)
21. Y. Xie; K. Wang; Y. Kong. Prevalence of Research Misconduct and Questionable Research Practices: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis, 2021. DOI: [10.1007/s11948-021-00314-9](https://doi.org/10.1007/s11948-021-00314-9)
22. J.M. Chin; J.T. Pickett; S. Vazire; A.O. Holcombe. Questionable Research Practices and Open Science in Quantitative Criminology, 2021. DOI: [10.1007/s10940-021-09525-6](https://doi.org/10.1007/s10940-021-09525-6)
23. M. Kaiser; L. Drivdal; J. Hjellbrekke; H. Ingierd; O.B. Rekdal. Questionable Research Practices and Misconduct Among Norwegian Researchers, 2022. DOI: [10.1007/s11948-021-00351-4](https://doi.org/10.1007/s11948-021-00351-4)
24. G. Gopalakrishna; G. ter Riet; G. Vink; et al. Prevalence of questionable research practices, research misconduct and their potential explanatory factors: A survey among academic researchers in The Netherlands, 2022. DOI: [10.1371/journal.pone.0263023](https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0263023)

25. E.H. O'Boyle; M. Gotz. Questionable Research Practices, 2022. DOI: [10.1093/oso/9780190938550.003.0010](https://doi.org/10.1093/oso/9780190938550.003.0010)
26. S. Kepes; S.K. Keener; M.A. McDaniel; N.S. Hartman. Questionable research practices among researchers in the most research-productive management programs, 2022. DOI: [10.1002/job.2623](https://doi.org/10.1002/job.2623)
27. N. Fox; N. Honeycutt; L. Jussim. Better Understanding the Population Size and Stigmatization of Psychologists Using Questionable Research Practices, 2022. DOI: [10.15626/MP.2020.2601](https://doi.org/10.15626/MP.2020.2601)
28. W. O'Donohue; A. Masuda; S. Lilienfeld (Editors). *Avoiding Questionable Research Practices in Applied Psychology*. 2022. ISBN: [9783031049675](https://doi.org/9783031049675)
29. R.G. Gerrits; T. Jansen; J. Mulyanto; et al. Occurrence and nature of questionable research practices in the reporting of messages and conclusions in international scientific Health Services Research publications: a structured assessment of publications authored by researchers in the Netherlands, 2022. DOI: [10.1136/bmjopen-2018-027903](https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjopen-2018-027903)
30. J.A. Damen; P. Heus; H.J. Lamberink; et al. Indicators of questionable research practices were identified in 163,129 randomized controlled trials, 2023. DOI: [10.1016/j.jclinepi.2022.11.020](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclinepi.2022.11.020)
31. T. Larsson; L. Plonsky; S. Sterling; et al. On the frequency, prevalence, and perceived severity of questionable research practices, 2023. DOI: [10.1016/j.rmal.2023.100064](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rmal.2023.100064)
32. S. Conix; S. De Peuter; A. De Block; K. Vaesen. Questionable research practices in competitive grant funding: A survey, 2023. DOI: [10.1371/journal.pone.0293310](https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0293310)
33. A.M. Clark; D.R. Thompson. Questionable research practices, careerism, and advocacy: why we must prioritize research quality over its quantity, impact, reach, and results, 2023. DOI: [10.1093/eurjcn/zvac012](https://doi.org/10.1093/eurjcn/zvac012)
34. R. Brooker; N. Allum. Investigating the links between questionable research practices, scientific norms and organisational culture, 2024. DOI: [10.1186/s41073-024-00151-x](https://doi.org/10.1186/s41073-024-00151-x)
35. S.F. Karabag; C. Berggren; J. Pielaszkiwicz; B. Gerdin. Minimizing Questionable Research Practices - The Role of Norms, Counter Norms, and Micro-Organizational Ethics Discussion, 2024. DOI: [10.1007/s10805-024-09520-z](https://doi.org/10.1007/s10805-024-09520-z)
36. J.W. Schneider; N. Allum; J.P. Andersen; et al. Is something rotten in the state of Denmark? Cross-national evidence for widespread involvement but not systematic use of questionable research practices across all fields of research, 2024. DOI: [10.1371/journal.pone.0304342](https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0304342)
37. T. Nagy; J. Hergert; M.M. Elsherif; et al. Bestiary of Questionable Research Practices in Psychology, 2025. DOI: [10.1177/25152459251348431](https://doi.org/10.1177/25152459251348431)

38. A.M. Clark; B.J. Sousa; C.F. Ski; D.R. Thompson. Honest yet unacceptable research practices: when research becomes a health risk, 2025. DOI: [10.1136/bmjopen-2024-097757](https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjopen-2024-097757)
39. M. Rubin. A Brief Review of Research that Questions the Impact of Questionable Research Practices, 2025. DOI: [10.31222/osf.io/6xzaw_v1](https://doi.org/10.31222/osf.io/6xzaw_v1)
40. Defining the spectrum of Questionable Research Practices (QRPs).
41. Catalogue of questionable research practices.
42. Questionable Research Practices.
43. Open Scientific Practices.
44. It's a slippery slope to research misconduct.
45. Navigating the Challenges of Questionable Research Practices in Academic Publishing.
46. Scientific misattribution: Academia's worst-kept secret.
47. Questionable Research Practices & the Emergence of a Stigmatized Academic Class.
48. Questionable Metascience Practices.
49. The Resistible Rise of Questionable Research Practices.
50. Questionable Research Practices: Definition, Detection, and Recommendations for Better Practices.
51. The Prevalence of Questionable Research Practices in Social Psychology.
52. The Prevalence of Questionable Research Practices (QRPs) in Education Research.
53. Questionable research practices.
54. Questionable research practices.
55. Questionable Research Practices (and research misbehaviors).
56. Questionable Research Practices: an Introductory Reflection on Causes, Patterns and Possible Responses.
57. Questionable Research Practices Surprisingly Common.
58. Why questionable research practices occur.

14 Reproducibility and Replicability

1. M.C. Makel; J.A. Plucker; B. Hegarty. Replications in Psychology Research: How Often Do They Really Occur?, 2012. DOI: [10.1177/1745691612460688](https://doi.org/10.1177/1745691612460688)
2. K.S. Button; J.P.A. Ioannidis; C. Mokrysz; et al. Power failure: why small sample size undermines the reliability of neuroscience, 2013. DOI: [10.1038/nrn3475](https://doi.org/10.1038/nrn3475)

3. M. McNutt. Reproducibility, 2014. DOI: [10.1126/science.1250475](https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1250475)
4. J.P.A. Ioannidis. How to Make More Published Research True, 2014. DOI: [10.1371/journal.pmed.1001747](https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pmed.1001747)
5. W. Stroebe; F. Strack. The Alleged Crisis and the Illusion of Exact Replication, 2014. DOI: [10.1177/1745691613514450](https://doi.org/10.1177/1745691613514450)
6. L.P. Freedman; I.M. Cockburn; T.S. Simcoe. The Economics of Reproducibility in Preclinical Research, 2015. DOI: [10.1371/journal.pbio.1002165](https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pbio.1002165)
7. S.E. Maxwell; M.Y. Lau; G.S. Howard. Is psychology suffering from a replication crisis? What does "failure to replicate" really mean?, 2015. DOI: [10.1037/a0039400](https://doi.org/10.1037/a0039400)
8. Open Science Collaboration. Estimating the reproducibility of psychological science, 2015. DOI: [10.1126/science.aac4716](https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aac4716)
9. C.G. Begley; J.P.A. Ioannidis. Reproducibility in Science: Improving the Standard for Basic and Preclinical Research, 2015. DOI: [10.1161/CIRCRESAHA.114.303819](https://doi.org/10.1161/CIRCRESAHA.114.303819)
10. S.B. Nissen; T. Magidson; K. Gross; C.T. Bergstrom. Research: Publication bias and the canonization of false facts, 2016. DOI: [10.7554/eLife.21451](https://doi.org/10.7554/eLife.21451)
11. D.B. Resnik; A.E. Shamoo. Reproducibility and Research Integrity, 2016. DOI: [10.1080/08989621.2016.1257387](https://doi.org/10.1080/08989621.2016.1257387)
12. M. Baker. 1,500 scientists lift the lid on reproducibility, 2016. DOI: [10.1038/533452a](https://doi.org/10.1038/533452a)
13. D.B. Allison; A.W. Brown; B.J. George; K.A. Kaiser. Reproducibility: A tragedy of errors, 2016. DOI: [10.1038/530027a](https://doi.org/10.1038/530027a)
14. Editorial. Reality check on reproducibility, 2016. DOI: [10.1038/533437a](https://doi.org/10.1038/533437a)
15. D.P. Broom; M. Hirscher. Irreproducibility in hydrogen storage material research, 2016. DOI: [0.1039/C6EE01435F](https://doi.org/10.1039/C6EE01435F)
16. R.G. Bergman; R.L. Danheiser. Reproducibility in Chemical Research, 2016. DOI: [10.1002/anie.201606591](https://doi.org/10.1002/anie.201606591)
17. M.R. Munafo; B.A. Nosek; D.V.M. Bishop; et al. A manifesto for reproducible science, 2017. DOI: [10.1038/s41562-016-0021](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41562-016-0021)
18. G.N. Martin; R.M. Clarke. Are Psychology Journals Anti-replication? A Snapshot of Editorial Practices, 2017. DOI: [10.3389/fpsyg.2017.00523](https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2017.00523)
19. W. Swiatkowski; B. Dompnier. Replicability Crisis in Social Psychology: Looking at the Past to Find New Pathways for the Future, 2017. DOI: [10.5334/irsp.66](https://doi.org/10.5334/irsp.66)
20. E. Loken; A. Gelman. Measurement error and the replication crisis, 2017. DOI: [10.1126/science.aal3618](https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aal3618)
21. K. Mullane; M.J. Curtis; M. Williams. Reproducibility in Biomedical Research, 2018. DOI: [10.1016/B978-0-12-804725-5.00001-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-804725-5.00001-X)

22. P.D. Schloss. Identifying and Overcoming Threats to Reproducibility, Replicability, Robustness, and Generalizability in Microbiome Research, 2018.
[DOI: 10.1128/mBio.00525-18](https://doi.org/10.1128/mBio.00525-18)
23. F.G. Hillary; J.D. Medaglia. What the replication crisis means for intervention science, 2019. [DOI: 10.1016/j.ijpsycho.2019.05.006](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijpsycho.2019.05.006)
24. F. Anvari; D. Lakens. The replicability crisis and public trust in psychological science, 2019. [DOI: 10.1080/23743603.2019.1684822](https://doi.org/10.1080/23743603.2019.1684822)
25. F. Romero. Philosophy of science and the replicability crisis, 2019.
[DOI: 10.1111/phc3.12633](https://doi.org/10.1111/phc3.12633)
26. S. Guttinger. The limits of replicability, 2020. [DOI: 10.1007/s13194-019-0269-1](https://doi.org/10.1007/s13194-019-0269-1)
27. S. Lewandowsky; K. Oberauer. Low replicability can support robust and efficient science, 2020. [DOI: 10.1038/s41467-019-14203-0](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-019-14203-0)
28. F. Hendriks; D. Kienhues; R. Bromme. Replication crisis = trust crisis? The effect of successful vs failed replications on laypeople's trust in researchers and research, 2020.
[DOI: 10.1177/0963662520902383](https://doi.org/10.1177/0963662520902383)
29. H. Else. Errors in genetic sequences mar hundreds of studies, 2021.
[DOI: 10.1038/d41586-021-02136-y](https://doi.org/10.1038/d41586-021-02136-y)
30. P. Diaba-Nuhoho; M. Amponsah-Offeh. Reproducibility and research integrity: the role of scientists and institutions, 2021. [DOI: 10.1186/s13104-021-05875-3](https://doi.org/10.1186/s13104-021-05875-3)
31. M. Andreoletti. Replicability Crisis and Scientific Reforms: Overlooked Issues and Unmet Challenges, 2021. [DOI: 10.1080/02698595.2021.1943292](https://doi.org/10.1080/02698595.2021.1943292)
32. P.G. Hensel. Reproducibility and replicability crisis: How management compares to psychology and economics - A systematic review of literature, 2021.
[DOI: 10.1016/j.emj.2021.01.002](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.emj.2021.01.002)
33. M. Serra-Garcia; U. Gneezy. Nonreplicable publications are cited more than replicable ones, 2021. [DOI: 10.1126/sciadv.abd1705](https://doi.org/10.1126/sciadv.abd1705)
34. A.C. Chang; P. Li. Is Economics Research Replicable? Sixty Published Papers From Thirteen Journals Say "Often Not", 2022. [DOI: 10.1561/104.00000053](https://doi.org/10.1561/104.00000053)
35. B.A. Nosek; T.E. Hardwicke; H. Moshontz; et al. Replicability, Robustness, and Reproducibility in Psychological Science, 2022. [DOI: 10.1146/annurev-psych-020821-114157](https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-psych-020821-114157)
36. A.B. Rouphael. The replicability crisis in science and protected area research: Poor practices and potential solutions, 2022. [DOI: 10.1016/j.jnc.2022.126236](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jnc.2022.126236)
37. M. Korbmacher; F. Azevedo; C.R. Pennington; et al. The replication crisis has led to positive structural, procedural, and community changes, 2023.
[DOI: 10.1038/s44271-023-00003-2](https://doi.org/10.1038/s44271-023-00003-2)

38. R. Ciriminna; G. Angellotti; G.L. Petri; M. Pagliaro. Reproducibility in chemistry research, 2024. DOI: [10.1016/j.heliyon.2024.e33658](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2024.e33658)
39. Y.J. Erden. Hyper-ambition and the Replication Crisis: Why Measures to Promote Research Integrity can Falter, 2025. DOI: [10.1007/s10805-024-09528-5](https://doi.org/10.1007/s10805-024-09528-5)
40. [Replication crisis.](#)
41. [The importance of reproducibility in open research.](#)
42. [New Report Examines Reproducibility and Replicability in Science, Recommends Ways to Improve Transparency and Rigor in Research.](#)
43. [Why is Replication in Research Important?.](#)
44. [Six factors affecting reproducibility in life science research and how to handle them.](#)
45. [Challenges in irreproducible research.](#)
46. [Why failure to replicate findings can actually be good for science.](#)
47. [The Reproducibility Crisis Is Good for Science.](#)
48. [Reproducibility: The science communities' ticking timebomb. Can we still trust published research?.](#)
49. [Reproducibility: why it matters and how it can be nurtured.](#)
50. [Position Paper: Reproducibility and Research Integrity.](#)
51. [Reproducibility of Scientific Results.](#)
52. [Limited Reproducibility of Research Findings: Implications for the Welfare of Research Participants and Considerations for Institutional Review Boards.](#)
53. [Replication Crisis.](#)
54. [Improving the Credibility of Scientific Research.](#)
55. [The replication crisis and how it affects the scientific world.](#)
56. [Most scientists 'can't replicate studies by their peers'.](#)
57. [The Reproducibility Crisis: How Open Science Can Save Research.](#)
58. [Opinion: The science 'reproducibility crisis' - and what can be done about it.](#)
59. [How Psychological Study Results Have Changed Since the Replication Crisis Began.](#)
60. ['An Existential Crisis' for Science: What IPR scholars are doing to solve the replication crisis.](#)
61. [A New Replication Crisis: Research that is Less Likely to be True is Cited More.](#)
62. [The curious case of the reproducibility crisis.](#)
63. [Threats of a Replication Crisis in Empirical Computer Science.](#)
64. [Replication Crisis in Medical Research Clinical Trials.](#)
65. [Reproducibility and reliability of biomedical research: improving research practice.](#)

66. [Reproducibility and Replicability in Research: Challenges and Way Forward.](#)
67. [Science Is Not Broken, But It Can Be Better.](#)
68. [Reproducibility and Replicability in Science: Report Highlights.](#)

15 Parachute and Helicopter Research

Also see § 9.

1. R. Horton. [Offline: Is global health neocolonialist?](#), 2013.
DOI: [10.1016/S0140-6736\(13\)62379-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(13)62379-X)
2. Editorial. [Closing the door on parachutes and parasites](#), 2018.
DOI: [10.1016/S2214-109X\(18\)30239-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2214-109X(18)30239-0)
3. M. Sheel; M.D. Kirk. [Parasitic and parachute research in global health](#), 2018. DOI: [10.1016/S2214-109X\(18\)30310-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2214-109X(18)30310-3)
4. M. Bockarie; S. Machingaidze; T. Nyirenda; O.F. Olesen; M. Makanga. [Parasitic and parachute research in global health](#), 2018.
DOI: [10.1016/S2214-109X\(18\)30342-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2214-109X(18)30342-5)
5. J. Smith. [Parasitic and parachute research in global health](#), 2018.
DOI: [10.1016/S2214-109X\(18\)30315-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2214-109X(18)30315-2)
6. P.P. Harawaa; E. Mbalea; M. Mallewa; et al. [Parasitic and parachute research in global health](#), 2018. DOI: [10.1016/S2214-109X\(18\)30324-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2214-109X(18)30324-3)
7. R. Mbaye; R. Gebeyehu; S. Hossmann; et al. [Who is telling the story? A systematic review of authorship for infectious disease research conducted in Africa, 1980-2016](#), 2019.
DOI: [10.1136/bmjgh-2019-001855](https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjgh-2019-001855)
8. K. Baker; M.P. Eichhorn; M. Griffiths. [Decolonizing field ecology](#), 2019.
DOI: [10.1111/btp.12663](https://doi.org/10.1111/btp.12663)
9. M.A. North; W.W. Hastie; L. Hoyer. [Out of Africa: The underrepresentation of African authors in high-impact geoscience literature](#), 2020. DOI: [10.1016/j.earscirev.2020.103262](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.earscirev.2020.103262)
10. V. Amarante; R. Burger; G. Chelwa; et al. [Underrepresentation of developing country researchers in development research](#), 2021. DOI: [10.1080/13504851.2021.1965528](https://doi.org/10.1080/13504851.2021.1965528)
11. B. Morton; A. Vercueil; R. Masekela; et al. [Consensus statement on measures to promote equitable authorship in the publication of research from international partnerships](#), 2021.
DOI: [10.1111/anae.15597](https://doi.org/10.1111/anae.15597)
12. P.V. Stefanoudis; W.Y. Licuanan; T.H. Morrison; et al. [Turning the tide of parachute science](#), 2021. DOI: [10.1016/j.cub.2021.01.029](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cub.2021.01.029)

13. E. Heinz; K.E. Holt; C.J. Meehan; S.K. Sheppard. Addressing parachute research and removing barriers for LMIC researchers in Microbial Genomics, 2021.
DOI: [10.1099/mgen.0.000722](https://doi.org/10.1099/mgen.0.000722)
14. D. Haelewaters; T.A. Hofmann; A.L. Romero-Olivares. Ten simple rules for Global North researchers to stop perpetuating helicopter research in the Global South, 2021.
DOI: [10.1371/journal.pcbi.1009277](https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pcbi.1009277)
15. C.H. Trisos; J. Auerbach; M. Katti. Decoloniality and anti-oppressive practices for a more ethical ecology, 2021. DOI: [10.1038/s41559-021-01460-w](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41559-021-01460-w)
16. F. Adame. Meaningful collaborations can end 'helicopter research', 2021.
DOI: [10.1038/d41586-021-01795-1](https://doi.org/10.1038/d41586-021-01795-1)
17. Editorial. Nature addresses helicopter research and ethics dumping, 2022.
DOI: [10.1038/d41586-022-01423-6](https://doi.org/10.1038/d41586-022-01423-6)
18. Editorial. Tackling helicopter research, 2022. DOI: [10.1038/s41561-022-01010-4](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41561-022-01010-4)
19. C.J. Gomez; A.C. Herman; P. Parigi. Leading countries in global science increasingly receive more citations than other countries doing similar research, 2022. DOI: [10.1038/s41562-022-01351-5](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41562-022-01351-5)
20. B. Odeny; R. Bosurgi. Time to end parachute science, 2022.
DOI: [10.1371/journal.pmed.1004099](https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pmed.1004099)
21. A. de Vos; M.W. Schwartz. Confronting parachute science in conservation, 2022. DOI: [10.1111/csp2.12681](https://doi.org/10.1111/csp2.12681)
22. C. O'Grady. 'Helicopter research' comes under fire at Cape Town conference, 2022.
DOI: [10.1126/science.add3544](https://doi.org/10.1126/science.add3544)
23. J. Miller; T.B. White; A.P. Christie. Parachute conservation: Investigating trends in international research, 2023. DOI: [10.1111/conl.12947](https://doi.org/10.1111/conl.12947)
24. K. McIntosh; L. Messin; P. Jin; Z. Mullan. Countering helicopter research with equitable partnerships, 2023. DOI: [10.1016/S2214-109X\(23\)00278-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2214-109X(23)00278-4)
25. E. Landis. Addressing Helicopter Research: Journal Policies for Equitable Collaborations, 2023. DOI: [10.36591/SE-D-4603-07](https://doi.org/10.36591/SE-D-4603-07)
26. M.S. Boampong; J. Boakye-Danquah; Y.A. Bofo; et al. Experiences of inequality in international collaborative research - Perspectives from environmental and sustainability scholars from Ghana, West Africa. DOI: [10.1016/j.envsci.2023.103661](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2023.103661)
27. I.P.J. Smit; R.J. Fernandez; M.F. Menvielle; et al. From parachuting to partnership: Fostering collaborative research in protected areas, 2024. DOI: [10.1111/1365-2664.14814](https://doi.org/10.1111/1365-2664.14814)
28. W.M. Lambert; M. Camacho-Rivera; C. Boutin-Foster; et al. Ending "domestic helicopter research", 2024. DOI: [10.1016/j.cell.2024.02.027](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cell.2024.02.027)

29. T. Thomas. Parachute science and collaboration in protected areas, 2025.
DOI: [10.1038/s44358-024-00010-z](https://doi.org/10.1038/s44358-024-00010-z)
30. Helicopter research is bad but there are other extractive and unethical practices that can harm researched communities.
31. Parachute science falls to earth.
32. Neo-colonial science.
33. The Problem of ‘Colonial Science’.
34. Recommendations to reduce parachute science in coral reef biodiversity research.
35. We need to end "parachute" research which sidelines the work of African scientists.
36. The perils of parachute research.
37. Reflections on Parachute Science.
38. Scientists Say It’s Time To End ‘Parachute Research’.
39. Why Conversations on Parachute Science Are a Necessary Discomfort.
40. Leave "Parachute Science" Behind When Jumping Into Global Microbiome Research.
41. Parachute Science - A Dirty Dark Side of Research: Colonialism has never fully gone away.
42. Parachute science and Caribbean plastic pollution.
43. Moving Beyond Parachute Science in the Sea Turtle Community.
44. ‘Helicopter research’: who benefits from international studies in Indonesia?.
45. How a South African community’s request for its genetic data raises questions about ethical and equitable research.
46. ‘Helicopter Research’ by Genetic Scientists Comes under Scrutiny in South Africa.
47. The Harms of ‘Helicopter Research’ in the Life Sciences.
48. The fossil skull that rocked the world - 100 years later scientists are grappling with the Taung find’s complex colonial legacy.
49. SUNY Downstate Leads Call To End ‘Domestic Helicopter Research’, Advocating for Equity-Centered Collaborations.
50. Avoiding ‘helicopter science’ - first steps towards finding solutions.

16 Patents

1. T. Caulfield; E. Einsiedel; J.F. Merz; D. Nicol. Trust, patents and public perceptions: the governance of controversial biotechnology research, 2006.

- [DOI: 10.1038/nbt1106-1352](https://doi.org/10.1038/nbt1106-1352)
2. J.B. Kadane. Patent Misconduct, 2008. [DOI: 10.1093/oso/9780195309232.003.0016](https://doi.org/10.1093/oso/9780195309232.003.0016)
 3. A.J. Stevens; G.A. Johnson; P.R. Sanberg. The Role of Patents and Commercialization in the Tenure and Promotion Process, 2011. [DOI: 10.3727/194982411X13189742259479](https://doi.org/10.3727/194982411X13189742259479)
 4. A. Furka. Plagiarism in Scientific Publishing - the Issue of Patent Holder (War Between Developed and Undeveloped Countries) - Letter to Editor, 2018. [DOI: 10.5455/aim.2018.26.73-74](https://doi.org/10.5455/aim.2018.26.73-74)
 5. J.L. Contreras. Patent Fakes: How Fraudulent Inventions Threaten Public Health, Innovation, and the Economy, 2020. [Source: https://dc.law.utah.edu/scholarship/230/](https://dc.law.utah.edu/scholarship/230/)
 6. J.L. Contreras. Patent Reality Checks: Eliminating Patents on Fake, Impossible and Other Inoperative Inventions, 2022. [Source: https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=3997942](https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=3997942)
 7. J. Gibson. Predatory ‘patents’ and design deceit: when the intellectual property system is recruited in academic fraud, 2025. [DOI: 10.4337/qmjip.2025.02.00](https://doi.org/10.4337/qmjip.2025.02.00)
 8. C. O’Grady. ‘Patent mills’ sell scientists inventorship of bizarre medical devices, 2025. [DOI: 10.1126/science.znietux](https://doi.org/10.1126/science.znietux)
 9. C. O’Grady. ‘Patent mills’ offer intellectual property for sale, 2025. [DOI: 10.1126/science.adx0333](https://doi.org/10.1126/science.adx0333)
 10. R.A.K. Richardson; N.H. Wise; S.S. Hong; M.J. Draper; S. Fackrell. Exploitation of intellectual property systems for the manipulation of academic reputations, 2025. [DOI: 10.1007/s40979-025-00185-8](https://doi.org/10.1007/s40979-025-00185-8)
 11. T.K. Goswami. Patent Mill and Paper Mill: Can it Build the Scientific Career or Act as an Academic Barrier, 2025. [DOI: 10.31080/ASMS.2025.09.2089](https://doi.org/10.31080/ASMS.2025.09.2089)
 12. [Patent Ethics Misconduct Guide.](#)
 13. [Patent Ethics: The Dark Side.](#)
 14. [Patent Fakes: How Fraudulent Inventions Threaten Public Health, Innovation, and the Economy.](#)
 15. [Remedies for Fraud on the Patent Office.](#)
 16. [Patently fraudulent.](#)
 17. [Fictitious Data, Real Patents.](#)
 18. [Patently fraudulent deceptions.](#)
 19. [‘Double fraud’: end Indian academics’ fake patent scam, UK urged.](#)
 20. [Patent Office Terminates 3,100 Applications for Fraudulent Signatures.](#)
 21. [Scientifically Speaking: Sale of fake designs as patents undermine academic integrity.](#)

22. [Eight companies are selling authorships of UK ‘design patents’.](#)
23. [No research? No problem: India’s booming market for fake patents and research papers.](#)
24. [Rampant Rise of Research/Patent Rackets Plagues India’s Education System: Problems & Solutions.](#)
25. [The Dark Side of Intellectual Property: How Academics Pay to be Named Inventors on Patents and Design Registrations.](#)
26. [The Dark Side of Intellectual Property: How Academics Pay to be Named Inventors on Patents and Design Registrations.](#)
27. [The patent-for-sale scheme ensnaring Indian academics.](#)
28. [The Fraud-Tainted Cloning Patent: Scandalous in Theory, a Storm in a Teacup in Reality.](#)
29. [The Great American Fraud: A Series of Articles on the Patent Medicine Evil, Reprinted from Collier’s Weekly.](#)
30. [Weekend reads: ‘The Discipline of Last Resort’; universities with the most retractions; ‘patent mills’.](#)
31. [India’s Hack Spirit Takes a Weird Turn.](#)

17 Quality of Academic Writing and Gobbledegook

1. D.P. Hayes. The growing inaccessibility of science, 1992. DOI: [10.1038/356739a0](#)
2. J. Knight. Scientific literacy: Clear as mud, 2003. DOI: [10.1038/423376a](#)
3. K. Sand-Jensen. How to write consistently boring scientific literature, 2007. DOI: [10.1111/j.0030-1299.2007.15674.x](#)
4. A. Gazni. Are the abstracts of high impact articles more readable? Investigating the evidence from top research institutions in the world, 2011. DOI: [10.1177/0165551511401658](#)
5. P. Plaven-Sigra; G.J. Matheson; B.C. Schiffler; W.H. Thompson. The readability of scientific texts is decreasing over time, 2017. DOI: [10.7554/eLife.27725](#)
6. P. Ball. It’s not just you: science papers are getting harder to read, 2017. DOI: [10.1038/nature.2017.21751](#)
7. C. Demir. The Needless Complexity in Academic Writing: Simplicity vs. Flowery Language, 2019. Source: <https://www.readingmatrix.com/files/21-n15v144o.pdf>
8. S. Balan. English as the language of research: But are we missing the mark?, 2021. DOI: [10.1016/j.rcsop.2021.100043](#)
9. L. Graf-Vlachy. Is the readability of abstracts decreasing in management research?,

2021. DOI: [10.1007/s11846-021-00468-7](https://doi.org/10.1007/s11846-021-00468-7)

10. L. Ante. The relationship between readability and scientific impact: Evidence from emerging technology discourses, 2022. DOI: [10.1016/j.joi.2022.101252](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.joi.2022.101252)
11. [Why Academics Stink at Writing.](#)
12. [Academic gobbledygook.](#)
13. [The Needless Complexity of Academic Writing.](#)
14. [Academia Still Has a Terrible Gobbledygook Problem.](#)
15. [Why can't academics say what they mean, instead of using gobbledygook?.](#)
16. [Academic gobbledygook.](#)
17. [Why Academic Writing Stink.](#)
18. [Academia Still Has a Terrible Gobbledygook Problem.](#)
19. [The real reason why academics write in gobbledygook.](#)
20. [Why Academic Writing Sucks: Building on Pinker's Perspective on why academic writing is terrible\).](#)
21. [Academic writing is getting harder to read-the humanities most of all.](#)
22. [Most Common Issues in Academic Writing.](#)
23. [Why can't academics write?.](#)
24. [Why is Academic Writing So Bad?.](#)
25. [Why Is Academic Writing So Bad?.](#)
26. [Why is academic writing so bad?.](#)
27. [Academic Writing Doesn't Have to Be Awful \(But Most Times That's What It Is\).](#)
28. [Why Most Academics Will Always Be Bad Writers.](#)
29. [Why Academics Revel in Bad Writing.](#)
30. [The Science of Scientific Writing.](#)
31. [The curse of knowledge: Why are academic papers so difficult to read?.](#)
32. [Science is getting harder to read.](#)
33. [Unnecessary complexity is ruining academic writing; it's up to us to save it.](#)
34. [Academic Language and the Problem of Meaninglessness.](#)
35. [Scientific Papers: Is Readability Declining?.](#)
36. [Scientific articles are increasingly complex and cryptic due to excessive use of jargon and acronyms.](#)

18 Metrics and Assessment of Academia and Research

1. M.A. Ferber. Citations: Are They an Objective Measure of Scholarly Merit?, 1986. DOI: [10.1086/494230](https://doi.org/10.1086/494230)
2. P.O. Seglen. The skewness of science, 1992. DOI: [10.1002/\(SICI\)1097-4571\(199210\)43:9<628::AID-ASI5>3.0.CO;2-0](https://doi.org/10.1002/(SICI)1097-4571(199210)43:9<628::AID-ASI5>3.0.CO;2-0)
3. D.G. Altman. The scandal of poor medical research, 1994. DOI: [10.1136/bmj.308.6924.283](https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.308.6924.283)
4. P.O. Seglen. Why the impact factor of journals should not be used for evaluating research, 1997. DOI: [10.1136/bmj.314.7079.497](https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.314.7079.497)
5. T.J. Phelan. A compendium of issues for citation analysis, 1999. DOI: [10.1007/BF02458472](https://doi.org/10.1007/BF02458472)
6. L. Langfeldt. The Decision-Making Constraints and Processes of Grant Peer Review, and Their Effects on the Review Outcome, 2001. DOI: [10.1177/030631201031006002](https://doi.org/10.1177/030631201031006002)
7. D. Colquhoun. Challenging the tyranny of impact factors, 2003. DOI: [10.1038/423479a](https://doi.org/10.1038/423479a)
8. D. Colquhoun. Playing the numbers game, 2006. DOI: [10.1038/442357a](https://doi.org/10.1038/442357a)
9. A. Weale. Metrics versus Peer Review?, 2009. DOI: [10.1111/j.1478-9299.2008.00169.x](https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1478-9299.2008.00169.x)
10. J. Taylor. The Assessment of Research Quality in UK Universities: Peer Review or Metrics?, 2010. DOI: [10.1111/j.1467-8551.2010.00722.x](https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-8551.2010.00722.x)
11. S. Bloxham. 'You can see the quality in front of your eyes': grounding academic standards between rationality and interpretation, 2012. DOI: [10.1080/13538322.2012.711071](https://doi.org/10.1080/13538322.2012.711071)
12. J.A. Eisen; C.J. MacCallum; C. Neylon. Expert Failure: Re-evaluating Research Assessment, 2013. DOI: [10.1371/journal.pbio.1001677](https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pbio.1001677)
13. Editorial. The maze of impact metrics, 2013. DOI: [10.1038/502271a](https://doi.org/10.1038/502271a)
14. L. Bornmann; L. Leydesdorff. Scientometrics in a changing research landscape: Bibliometrics has become an integral part of research quality evaluation and has been changing the practice of research, 2014. DOI: [10.15252/embr.201439608](https://doi.org/10.15252/embr.201439608)
15. P. O'Connor; C. O'Hagan. Excellence in university academic staff evaluation: a problematic reality?, 2015. DOI: [10.1080/03075079.2014.1000292](https://doi.org/10.1080/03075079.2014.1000292)
16. J. Wilsdon; L. Allen; E. Belfiore; et al. The Metric Tide: Report of the Independent Review of the Role of Metrics in Research Assessment and Management, 2015. DOI: [10.13140/RG.2.1.4929.1363](https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.4929.1363)
17. R. Benedictus; F. Miedema; M.W.J. Ferguson. Fewer numbers, better science, 2016. DOI: [10.1038/538453a](https://doi.org/10.1038/538453a)
18. M. Goos; A. Salomons. Measuring teaching quality in higher education: assessing

- selection bias in course evaluations, 2016. DOI: [10.1007/s11162-016-9429-8](https://doi.org/10.1007/s11162-016-9429-8)
19. A.D. Higginson; M.R. Munafo. Current Incentives for Scientists Lead to Underpowered Studies with Erroneous Conclusions, 2016. DOI: [10.1371/journal.pbio.2000995](https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pbio.2000995)
 20. Y. Gingras. *Bibliometrics and Research Evaluation: Uses and Abuses*. 2016. ISBN: [9780262337656](https://doi.org/9780262337656)
 21. L. Zhang; R. Rousseau; G. Sivertsen. Science deserves to be judged by its contents, not by its wrapping: Revisiting Seglen's work on journal impact and research evaluation, 2017. DOI: [10.1371/journal.pone.0174205](https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0174205)
 22. B. Duyx; M.J.E. Urlings; G.M.H. Swaen. Scientific citations favor positive results: a systematic review and meta-analysis, 2017. DOI: [10.1016/j.jclinepi.2017.06.002](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclinepi.2017.06.002)
 23. S. Curry. Let's move beyond the rhetoric: it's time to change how we judge research, 2018. DOI: [10.1038/d41586-018-01642-w](https://doi.org/10.1038/d41586-018-01642-w)
 24. D.W. Aksnes; L. Langfeldt; P. Wouters. Citations, Citation Indicators, and Research Quality: An Overview of Basic Concepts and Theories, 2019. DOI: [10.1177/2158244019829575](https://doi.org/10.1177/2158244019829575)
 25. A.V. Grinav. The Disadvantages of Using Scientometric Indicators in the Digital Age, 2020. DOI: [10.1088/1757-899X/940/1/012149](https://doi.org/10.1088/1757-899X/940/1/012149)
 26. BMJ. Academic criteria for promotion and tenure in biomedical sciences faculties: cross sectional analysis of international sample of universities, 2020. DOI: [10.1136/bmj.m2081](https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.m2081)
 27. M. Biagioli; A. Lippman (Editors). *Gaming the Metrics: Misconduct and Manipulation in Academic Research*. 2020. ISBN: [9780262356565](https://doi.org/9780262356565)
 28. E. Gadd. Mis-Measuring Our Universities: Why Global University Rankings Don't Add Up, 2021. DOI: [10.3389/frma.2021.680023](https://doi.org/10.3389/frma.2021.680023)
 29. B.V. Calster; L. Wynants; R.D. Riley; et al. Methodology over metrics: current scientific standards are a disservice to patients and society. DOI: [10.1016/j.jclinepi.2021.05.018](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclinepi.2021.05.018)
 30. L. Langfeldt; I. Reymert; D.W. Aksnes. The role of metrics in peer assessments, 2021. DOI: [10.1093/reseval/rvaa032](https://doi.org/10.1093/reseval/rvaa032)
 31. N. Pontika; T. Klebel; A. Correia; et al. Indicators of research quality, quantity, openness, and responsibility in institutional review, promotion, and tenure policies across seven countries, 2022. DOI: [10.1162/qss_a_00224](https://doi.org/10.1162/qss_a_00224)
 32. J.Q. Sumner; C.H. Vitale; L.D. McIntosh. RipetaScore: Measuring the Quality, Transparency, and Trustworthiness of a Scientific Work, 2022. DOI: [10.3389/frma.2021.751734](https://doi.org/10.3389/frma.2021.751734)
 33. A.N. Holding; K.R. McIntyre; P.T. Lynch. Is it possible to measure good science?, 2022. DOI: [10.1111/febs.16674](https://doi.org/10.1111/febs.16674)
 34. S. Alhuthali; A.A. Sayed. Saudi Universities Rapid Escalation in Academic Ranking

- Systems: Implications and Challenges, 2022. DOI: [10.35995/jci02010008](https://doi.org/10.35995/jci02010008)
35. M. Thelwall; K. Kousha; E. Stuart; et al. Do bibliometrics introduce gender, institutional or interdisciplinary biases into research evaluations?, 2023.
DOI: [10.1016/j.respol.2023.104829](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.respol.2023.104829)
 36. E. Hengel; A. Sevilla; S. Smith. Measuring research quality in a more inclusive way: Evidence from the UK Research Excellence Framework, 2024.
DOI: [10.1093/reseval/rvae013](https://doi.org/10.1093/reseval/rvae013)
 37. M. Montazerian; N. Shaghaei; T.M. Drachen; B.F. Dorch. Quality and quantity in research assessment: examining the merits of metrics, volume II, 2024.
DOI: [10.3389/frma.2024.1400009](https://doi.org/10.3389/frma.2024.1400009)
 38. G. Abramo. The forced battle between peer-review and scientometric research assessment: Why the CoARA initiative is unsound, 2024. DOI: [10.1093/reseval/rvae021](https://doi.org/10.1093/reseval/rvae021)
 39. M. Catanzaro. Citation cartels help some mathematicians - and their universities - climb the rankings, 2024. DOI: [10.1126/science.zcl2s6d](https://doi.org/10.1126/science.zcl2s6d)
 40. Understanding research metrics.
 41. Rethinking research assessment: 7 sources of bias to watch out for at your institution.
 42. Global Biases in Research Metrics: A fundamental challenge to knowledge equity.
 43. Why Metrics Cannot Measure Research Quality: A Response to the HEFCE Consultation.
 44. Research Assessment: Reducing bias in the evaluation of researchers.
 45. Evaluating research assessment: Metrics-based analysis exposes implicit bias in REF2014 results.
 46. Exploring Researchers' Views on Metrics and Research Impact.
 47. Columbia whistleblower on exposing college rankings: 'They are worthless'.
 48. Can the research excellence framework run on metrics?.
 49. The metric tide: review of metrics in research assessment.
 50. Responsible metrics.
 51. The rejection of metrics for the REF does not take account of existing problems of determining research quality.
 52. Despite becoming increasingly institutionalised, there remains a lack of discourse about research metrics among much of academia.
 53. Limitations of using Altmetrics in impact analysis.
 54. Measuring Research Impacts and Quality.
 55. Responsible Research Assessment & Use of Metrics.

56. [All impact metrics are wrong, but \(with more data\) some are useful.](#)
57. [This professor exposed Columbia University's false ranking. He says it's only the tip of the scandal.](#)
58. [Statement on the Responsible Use of Research Metrics.](#)
59. [The Battle of Peer Review and Scientometric Assessment: Analyzing the CoARA Initiative.](#)
60. [The role of scientometrics in the pursuit of responsible research assessment.](#)
61. [Research Evaluation Should be Pragmatic, Not a Choice Between Peer Review and Metrics.](#)
62. [How Metrics Affect Peer Review for Academic Jobs and Grants.](#)
63. [Metrics cannot replace peer review in the next REF.](#)
64. [How should universities be run to get the best out of people?.](#)

19 Waste in Academia and Research

1. I. Chalmers; P. Glasziou. Avoidable waste in the production and reporting of research evidence, 2009. DOI: [10.1016/S0140-6736\(09\)60329-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(09)60329-9)
2. P. Glasziou; D.G. Altman; P. Bossuyt; et al. Reducing waste from incomplete or unusable reports of biomedical research, 2014. DOI: [10.1016/S0140-6736\(13\)62228-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(13)62228-X)
3. J.P.A. Ioannidis; S. Greenland; M.A. Hlatky; et al. Increasing value and reducing waste in research design, conduct, and analysis, 2014. DOI: [10.1016/S0140-6736\(13\)62227-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(13)62227-8)
4. A.-W. Chan; F. Song; A. Vickers; et al. Increasing value and reducing waste: addressing inaccessible research, 2014. DOI: [10.1016/S0140-6736\(13\)62296-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(13)62296-5)
5. BMJ. Avoidable waste of research related to inadequate methods in clinical trials, 2015. DOI: [10.1136/bmj.h809](https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.h809)
6. D. Moher; P. Glasziou; I. Chalmers; et al. Increasing value and reducing waste in biomedical research: who's listening?, 2016. DOI: [10.1016/S0140-6736\(15\)00307-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(15)00307-4)
7. BMJ. Research waste is still a scandal-an essay by Paul Glasziou and Iain Chalmers, 2018. DOI: [10.1136/bmj.k4645](https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.k4645)
8. B. von Niederhausern; G.H. Guyatt; M. Briel; C. Pauli-Magnus. Academic response to improving value and reducing waste: A comprehensive framework for INcreasing QUality In patient-oriented academic clinical REsearch (INQUIRE), 2018. DOI: [10.1371/journal.pmed.1002580](https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pmed.1002580)
9. N. Pandis; P.S. Fleming; C. Katsaros; J.P.A. Ioannidis. Dental Research Waste in

- Design, Analysis, and Reporting: A Scoping Review, 2021.
DOI: [10.1177/0022034520962751](https://doi.org/10.1177/0022034520962751)
10. S. Panda; H.C. Williams. Research waste is universal, 2022.
DOI: [10.25259/IJDVL_564_2022](https://doi.org/10.25259/IJDVL_564_2022)
 11. G.M. Sogi. Research Waste, 2023. DOI: [10.4103/ccd.ccd_434_23](https://doi.org/10.4103/ccd.ccd_434_23)
 12. L. Uttley. Research Culture's Role in Contributing to Research Waste, 2024. DOI: [10.31273/eirj.v11i3.1539](https://doi.org/10.31273/eirj.v11i3.1539)
 13. ; et al. C. Lord; A. Friday; A. Jackson. The World is Not Enough: Growing Waste in HPC-enabled Academic Practice, 2025. DOI: [10.1145/3706598.3713919](https://doi.org/10.1145/3706598.3713919)
 14. [How much of modern academia is waste? A painful question that we need to ask.](#)
 15. [Waste in Academic Research.](#)
 16. [Against Research Waste - How the Evidence-Based Research paradigm promotes more ethical and innovative research.](#)
 17. [Why is waste in research an ethical issue?.](#)
 18. [Reducing Research Waste: Can research ethics committees help minimize research waste?.](#)
 19. [85% of Health Research is Wasted: How to do great research, get it published, and improve health outcomes.](#)
 20. [Academic Waste From funding to publishing, academic research needlessly burns through time and money.](#)
 21. [How much money do we waste on research?.](#)
 22. [Why academic research in AI is a total waste of time.](#)
 23. [Death By a Thousand Emails: How Administrative Bloat is Killing American Higher Education.](#)
 24. [Great wealth: the privilege academia really doesn't want to discuss.](#)
 25. [Houston Oil Professor Really, Really Likes \\$500 Pens and Fogo De Chao.](#)
 26. [Why doing a PhD is often a waste of time.](#)
 27. [How to free the universities: Woke waste is ruining academia.](#)
 28. [Paul Glasziou and Iain Chalmers: Is 85% of health research really "wasted"?](#)
 29. [Taxpayers foot £6bn bill for 'nonsense' research despite Reeves crackdown on waste.](#)
 30. [Is Higher Education Spending Excessive? In Some Ways Maybe Yes, in Others Perhaps Not.](#)
 31. [The Case Against Education: Why the Education System Is a Waste of Time and Money by Bryan Caplan.](#)

20 General

1. H.S. Siegel. Ethics in Research, 1991. DOI: [10.3382/ps.0700271](https://doi.org/10.3382/ps.0700271)
2. A.C. Justice; M.K. Cho; M.A. Winker. Does Masking Author Identity Improve Peer Review Quality? A Randomized Controlled Trial, 1998. DOI: [10.1001/jama.280.3.240](https://doi.org/10.1001/jama.280.3.240)
3. J.P.A. Ioannidis. Why Most Published Research Findings Are False, 2005. DOI: [10.1371/journal.pmed.0020124](https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pmed.0020124)
4. J.M. Henshaw. *Does Measurement Measure Up?: How Numbers Reveal and Conceal the Truth*. 2006. ISBN: 9780801889370
5. I. Roberts; R. Smith; S. Evans. Doubts over head injury studies, 2007. DOI: [10.1136/bmj.39118.480023.BE](https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.39118.480023.BE)
6. D. Colquhoun. Science degrees without the science, 2007. DOI: [10.1038/446373a](https://doi.org/10.1038/446373a)
7. B.L. Benderly. Academia's Crooked Money Trail, 2012. DOI: [10.1126/science.caredit.a1200001](https://doi.org/10.1126/science.caredit.a1200001)
8. M. Cleary; G. Walter; D. Jackson. Editorial: 'Is that for real?': curriculum vitae padding, 2013. DOI: [10.1111/jocn.12161](https://doi.org/10.1111/jocn.12161)
9. S. Necker. Scientific misbehavior in economics, 2014. DOI: [10.1016/j.respol.2014.05.002](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.respol.2014.05.002)
10. S. Syed; D.Q. Tran; A.R. Kemper; J.W. St Geme III; J.D. Lantos. Authorship Concerns and Who Truly Owns a Research Idea?, 2015. DOI: [10.1542/peds.2015-1421](https://doi.org/10.1542/peds.2015-1421)
11. I. Roberts; K. Ker; P. Edwards; et al. The knowledge system underpinning healthcare is not fit for purpose and must change, 2015. DOI: [10.1136/bmj.h2463](https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.h2463)
12. D. Fanelli; R. Costas; V. Larivière. Misconduct Policies, Academic Culture and Career Stage, Not Gender or Pressures to Publish, Affect Scientific Integrity, 2015. DOI: [10.1371/journal.pone.0127556](https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0127556)
13. S. Singh; D. Remenyi. Plagiarism and ghostwriting: The rise in academic misconduct, 2016. DOI: [10.17159/sajs.2016/20150300](https://doi.org/10.17159/sajs.2016/20150300)
14. S.P.J.M. Horbach; W. Halffman. The ghosts of HeLa: How cell line misidentification contaminates the scientific literature, 2017. DOI: [10.1371/journal.pone.0186281](https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0186281)
15. J. Christopher. Systematic fabrication of scientific images revealed, 2018. DOI: [10.1002/1873-3468.13201](https://doi.org/10.1002/1873-3468.13201)
16. G. Helgesson; N. Juth; J. Schneider; et al. Misuse of Coauthorship in Medical Theses in Sweden, 2018. DOI: [10.1177/1556264618784206](https://doi.org/10.1177/1556264618784206)
17. J. Gomez-Ferri; G. Gonzalez-Alcaide; R. Llopis-Goig. Measuring dissatisfaction with coauthorship: An empirical approach based on the researchers' perception, 2019. DOI: [10.1016/j.joi.2019.100980](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.joi.2019.100980)

18. I. Boutron. Spin in Scientific Publications: A Frequent Detrimental Research Practice, 2019. DOI: [10.1016/j.annemergmed.2019.11.002](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.annemergmed.2019.11.002)
19. D.A. Zarin; S.N. Goodman; J. Kimmelman. Harms From Uninformative Clinical Trials, 2019. DOI: [10.1001/jama.2019.9892](https://doi.org/10.1001/jama.2019.9892)
20. D.R. Thompson; A.M. Clark. The Ego Has Landed! What Can Be Done About Research Misconduct, Scandals, and Spins?, 2019. DOI: [XXX](https://doi.org/XXX)
21. J.B. Carlisle. False individual patient data and zombie randomised controlled trials submitted to Anaesthesia, 2020. DOI: [10.1111/anae.15263](https://doi.org/10.1111/anae.15263)
22. S.H. Bradley; N.J. DeVito; K.E. Lloyd; et al. Reducing bias and improving transparency in medical research: a critical overview of the problems, progress and suggested next steps, 2020. DOI: [10.1177/0141076820956799](https://doi.org/10.1177/0141076820956799)
23. M.A.G. van der Heyden. The 1-h fraud detection challenge, 2021. DOI: [10.1007/s00210-021-02120-3](https://doi.org/10.1007/s00210-021-02120-3)
24. S.L. Boughton; J. Wilkinson; L. Bero. When beauty is but skin deep: dealing with problematic studies in systematic reviews, 2021. DOI: [10.1002/14651858.ED000152](https://doi.org/10.1002/14651858.ED000152)
25. H. Else. Errors in genetic sequences mar hundreds of studies, 2021. DOI: [10.1038/d41586-021-02136-y](https://doi.org/10.1038/d41586-021-02136-y)
26. A.R. Gaby. Is There an Epidemic of Research Fraud in Natural Medicine?, 2022. PMID: [PMC9173852](https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/39173852/)
27. T. You; J. Park; J.Y. Lee; J. Yun; W.-S. Jung. Disturbance of questionable publishing to academia, 2022. DOI: [10.1016/j.joi.2022.101294](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.joi.2022.101294)
28. T. Maryon; V. Dubre; K. Elliott; et al. COVID-19 Academic Integrity Violations and Trends: A Rapid Review, 2022. DOI: [10.3390/educsci12120901](https://doi.org/10.3390/educsci12120901)
29. R.M. Frederickson; R.W. Herzog. Addressing the big business of fake science, 2022. DOI: [10.1016/j.ymthe.2022.06.001](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ymthe.2022.06.001)
30. D.S. Chawla. How a site peddles author slots in reputable publishers' journals, 2022. DOI: [10.1126/science.abq4276](https://doi.org/10.1126/science.abq4276)
31. J.A.T. da Silva. "Tortured phrases" in preprints, 2023. DOI: [10.1080/03007995.2023.2201098](https://doi.org/10.1080/03007995.2023.2201098)
32. J. Brainard. Fake scientific papers are alarmingly common, 2023. DOI: [10.1126/science.adi6523](https://doi.org/10.1126/science.adi6523)
33. E. Owens. Authorship in Academic Librarianship Journals, 2015-2019: Evaluating Author Occupations, National and Institutional Affiliations, and Coauthorship, 2023. DOI: [10.5860/crl.84.5.712](https://doi.org/10.5860/crl.84.5.712)
34. R. Van Noorden. Medicine is plagued by untrustworthy clinical trials. How many

- studies are faked or flawed?, 2023. DOI: [10.1038/d41586-023-02299-w](https://doi.org/10.1038/d41586-023-02299-w)
35. D.S. Chawla. Fake research papers flagged by analysing authorship trends, 2024. DOI: [10.1038/d41586-024-00344-w](https://doi.org/10.1038/d41586-024-00344-w)
 36. J. Wittau; R. Seifert. How to fight fake papers: a review on important information sources and steps towards solution of the problem, 2024. DOI: [10.1007/s00210-024-03272-8](https://doi.org/10.1007/s00210-024-03272-8)
 37. M. Jakab; E. Kittl; T. Kiesslich. How many authors are (too) many? A retrospective, descriptive analysis of authorship in biomedical publications, 2024. DOI: [10.1007/s11192-024-04928-1](https://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-024-04928-1)
 38. D.E. Wright. Five problems plaguing publishing in the life sciences-and one common cause, 2024. DOI: [10.1002/1873-3468.15018](https://doi.org/10.1002/1873-3468.15018)
 39. Secret Lecturer. *The Secret Lecturer: What Really Goes on at University*. 2024. ISBN: [9781914487217](https://www.isbn-international.org/product/9781914487217)
 40. D. Johann; J. Neufeld; K. Thomas; et al. The impact of researchers' perceived pressure on their publication strategies, 2024. DOI: [10.1093/reseval/rvae011](https://doi.org/10.1093/reseval/rvae011)
 41. J. Decius; M. Schilbach. Fair credit? The impact of shared first authorship on academic career evaluation, 2025. DOI: [10.1007/s11192-025-05262-w](https://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-025-05262-w)
 42. Most published author ever: Man uses algorithms to write more than 200,000 books.
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